

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES TOWARDS HIV/AIDS AMONG FEMALE ADOLESCENTS

Thesis submitted for award of degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in Home Science

By

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Registration Number – 268/2007

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GUIDE'S CERTIFICATE

I certify that this thesis entitled “**Knowledge, Attitude and Practices towards HIV/AIDS among Female Adolescents**” submitted Ms. Jyotsnarani Singh, for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Home Science to the Berhamru University, Odisha, India is a bonafied research work carried by her under my supervision and guidance. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the results embodied in this thesis have not been submitted to any other University for the award of any degree or diploma.

Place: Berhampur

(**Dr. Aparajita Chowdhury**)

Date:

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the thesis entitled, “**Knowledge, Attitude and Practices towards HIV/AIDS among Female Adolescents,**” as a partial fulfillment of the Doctorate of Philosophy (Department of Home Science) is done by me under the supervision of **Prof. Aparajita Chowdhury**, Professor & Head, Post Graduate Department of Home Science, Berhampur University, Bhanjavihar, Odisha; and that this thesis has not previously formed the basis for the award of the degree or fellowship or other similar study of any other university.

Place: Berhampur

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AIDS	: Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
ART	: Antiretroviral Therapy
CBO-	: Community- based organization
FHI-	: Family Health Organization
GOI-	: Government of India
HIV-	: Human Immunodeficiency Virus
IEC-	: information, Education and Communication
IPC-	: Interpersonal Communication
LSE-	: Life Skills Education
OGAC-	: The U.S Office of Global AIDS Coordinator
OI-	: Opportunistic infection
OVC-	: Orphans and vulnerable children
PLHA-	: People living with AIDS
STI-	: Sexually transmitted infection
STD-	: Sexually transmitted disease
TB-	: tuberculosis
USAD-	: U.S Agency for International Development

AMO	: Assistant Medical Officer
APEP	: AIDS Prevention Education Programme
BSS	: Behavioral Surveillance Survey
CMIS	: Computerized Management Information System
CRT	: Community Resource Team
DEO	: District Educational Officer
DIET	: District Institute of Education and Training
DLO	: District Leprosy Officer
DRP	: District Resource Person
DTC	: District Training Center
DTERT	: Directorate of Teachers Educational Research and Training
FAQ	: Frequently Asked Questions
FGD	: Focus Group Discussion
HFWTC	: Health and Family Welfare Training Center
NACO	: National AIDS Control Organization
M&E	: Monitoring and Evaluation
PLHWS	: People Living With HIV/AIDS
SACS	: State AIDS Control Society
SCERT	: State Council of Education Research Training
SPARSHA	: Society for Positive Atmosphere and Related Support to HIV/AIDS
SRP	: State Resource Person
TISS	: Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai

TOT	: Training of Trainers
UNGASS	: United Nations General Special Session on HIV/AIDS
AIIMS	: Assessing the impact of Microenterprise Services (Project)
BRAC	: Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee
Camfed	: Campaign for Female Education (International)
CCT	: conditional cash transfer
CEDPA	: Center for Development and Population Activities
CGAP	: Consultative Group to Assist the Poor
DHS	: Demographic and Health Survey
Emergency Plan	: President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (United States)
FA	: Families in Action
FFH	: Freedom for Hunger
FINCA	: Foundation for International Community Assistance
FOCCAS	: Foundation for Credit and Community Assistance (Uganda)
GDP	: Gross Domestic Product
GOB	: Government of Bangladesh
GTWG	: Gender Technical Working Group
ICRW	: International Center for Research on Women
IGVGD	: Income Gender for Vulnerable Groups Development (Bangladesh)
IMAGE	: Intervention with Microfinance for AIDS and Gender Equity South Africa)
IPV	: Inter Personal Violence

KDA	: K-Rep Development Agency (Kenya)
MF	: Microfinance
MFI	: Microfinance Institution
NGO	: Nongovernmental Organization
PATH	: Programme of Advancement through Health and Education (Jamaica)
PDA	: Population and Community Development Association
PPP	: Positive Partnership Programme (Thailand)
PRAF	: Family Allowance Programme (Honduras)
PROGRESA	: Education, Health, A nutrition Programme (Mexico)
RH	: Reproductive Health
ROI	: Return on Investment
ROSCA	: Revolving Saving and Credit Association
RPS	: Society Safety Net Programme (Nicaragua)
SCF	: Small Enterprise Foundation
SFL	: Sisters for Life
SHAZ	: Shaping the Health of Adolescent in Zimbabwe
SKI	: Street Kids International (Zambia)
TRY	: Tap and Reposition youth (Kenya)
USAID	: United States Agency for International Development
USG	: United States Government
UNAIDS	: United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS

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UNESCO : United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural
Organization

UNFPA : United Nations Population Fund

UNICEF : United Nations Children's Fund

VCT : Vocational Training Center

WFP : World Food Programme

ABSTRACT

The HIV/AIDS is undoubtedly the most devastating pandemic mankind has ever faced. Today, the global community seems to be struggling as the disease rips apart the social and economic fabric of the society by killing people in prime of their youth, rendering millions of children orphans and shattering homes and hopes alike. With remote prospects for a cure, the challenge to contain the spread of HIV has become imperative. Although no culture or community is known to be immune to AIDS yet, certain populations are more vulnerable to the disease because of their high-risk behaviours. Adolescents are the most at – risk group for such type of disease than others.

Any country can develop the resources only when the country's citizens are wise, healthy, educated and properly trained. Thus, the real resources of any country depend on its people. While India is being propelled to a position of international eminence, it faces a major threat in its health perspectives especially in dealing effectively with communicable diseases. Among these communicable diseases HIV/AIDS plays a vital role in bringing down the massive development shown by the country in ever so many ways. Adolescents are a rich human resource and an important part of the development process. Good health of adolescents will help in raising the health status of the community. Adolescents, especially girls, mostly from disadvantaged communities and families, are trafficked for the purposes of early forced marriages, domestic labour, commercial sex work and are forced to work in inhospitable, unsafe and exploitative conditions. It is still a great burden that most of the infected people are in the young age. Hence this is posing a great threat to the human resources of the country. It is estimated that around 2.4 million people in India are currently living with HIV/AIDS. Health of adolescent girls has an intergenerational effect. Adolescents constitute nearly 22% of the Indian population. In India, there are 8.3 crore girls in the age group of 11-18 years which constitute 17% of the total female population of 49.65 crores. The female literacy rate is only 53.87%. Nearly one third of the adolescent girls are undernourished.

Misconceptions about HIV/AIDS are widespread. UNICEF statistics (2003-2008) show that only 36% of adolescent males in India have comprehensive knowledge of HIV, while their female counterparts lag behind with just 20% of them having complete and accurate HIV information. A national study by NACO (National Behavioral Surveillance Survey, 2001) among young people (15-24 years) found that the level of awareness about HIV was higher in urban adolescents compared to their rural counterparts, more in males than females and that education increased the levels of awareness. Thus, in order to analysis the reasons for HIV/AIDS intention, to understand adolescent girls' knowledge, attitude and practices towards HIV/AIDS in Odisha both in rural and urban area the following specific objectives were set for the present study as follows:

1. To study the socio-demographic profile of the adolescent respondents ;
2. To assess knowledge pertaining to HIV/AIDS among adolescent girls,
3. To determine the adolescent girls, attitude towards HIV/AIDS,
4. To collect information regarding sexual experiences, practices prevalent among the adolescent girls under study.

By using exploratory and descriptive study design, the researcher attempts to describe female adolescents' knowledge and understanding regarding HIV/AIDS, nature, causes, treatment, channels of transmission, the sources of information, the risk groups and the preventive measures. The attitude of female adolescents towards HIV/AIDS also another important component of the study; which attempts the various aspects of sex and sexuality, such as negative and positive attitude towards the disease and its victims. There are also some myths and misconceptions associated with the dreaded disease and people who infected with HIV/AIDS, have been discussed. In order to understand and study the knowledge, attitude and practices among adolescent girls, present study adopted multi method approaches to elicit intimation form different stockholders. A scheduled questionnaire was used covering all aspects of HIV/ AIDS and observation methods were also used to collect the data from the adolescent girls.

The study shows that more than 80 per cent of the respondents belong to the age group of 13-16 years; more than half of the respondents belong to nuclear family and majority of them local based family being included in Below Poverty Line (BPL) category. Correct knowledge about HIV/AIDS; its nature, channels of transmission, preventive measures and treatment reduces the risk of being infected by HIV virus. The study reveals that a significant proportionate of the respondents i.e. 60 per cent of them do not have exact information about HIV/AIDS. The rural adolescents do not have access to modern information technology such as Television, Radio, etc. as a result their knowledge on different aspects of HIV/AIDS is incomplete and often misleading.

Adolescence is the most important formative period of a human being. Many of the vital perceptions, crucial emotions and very importantly attitudes towards religion, caste, sex, etc. are formed. Almost half of the respondents realized that being infected with HIV virus is not God's punishment for one's immoral behavior, sixty-three per cent of the respondents strongly feel that the persons being infected with HIV/AIDS need not be discriminated and they are to be protected and cared for. More than half, i.e. 60.3 per cent of the respondents are not easily fall prey to common myths and misconceptions with regard to HIV/AIDS; like having sex with a virgin girl will cure the disease.

Sexual experiences are important elements of being an adult and young people do not practice problems that may come in future, especially when they concern them as sexual beings. The present study revealed that a few adolescents reported having penetrative sex and experience of touching private parts. The study observed that a majority of the respondents i.e. 54.8 % have taken to reading sex books and magazines. A majority of them i.e. 48.5 % have indulged in masturbation, while kissing, hugging, fondling genitals of a person of the opposite sex and watching pornography have been the activities of many of them with the range of 43% - 46%. Twenty two per cent of them reported having experience of forced sex like fondling the genitals forcefully, caressing the breasts, stimulating sexual desire, etc.

Further, the finding reveled that, the rural adolescent girls do not have adequate knowledge on human sexuality and reproductive health. Similarly their knowledge on

HIV/AIDS is incomplete and insufficient to live a healthy life without being succumbed to various deadly infections. On the other hand the information they obtained from the various channels are not authoritative. The adolescent girls in schools or out of schools do not have access to sex education which sometimes leads them towards risky behavior. The teachers in the present study are also not so comfortable and competent enough to provide sex education to the students, and especially to adolescent girls. Sexual health being a sensitive issue in the traditional society; it is neither the parents nor the teachers who feel comfortable in providing education to the adolescent girls on sexual and reproductive health. Thus the knowledge could be imparted in different community setting with the help of the peer educators. The establishment of Youth Friendly Information Centers (YFIC) starting from the village to the National level which would create a band of youth volunteers who will be adequately reoriented and sensitized on social, biological, emotional and health risks of the young people, on stigma, discrimination, gender violence, human rights, etc. to promote a confidential and enabling environment for counseling, life skill education, recreation and guidance to reduce the extent of vulnerabilities of adolescent girls towards HIV/AIDS and live a rich, meaningful and productive life.

A significant proportion of the rural adolescent girls do not have proper knowledge about HIV/AIDS. This can lead adolescent girls to increase myth, practice risky sexual behavioral that can result with HIV/AIDS infection ultimately causing burden to their life and society. Knowledge about mode of HIV transmission is poor and interestingly (28%) of adolescent of respondents had no idea about, what is condom, its use or its availability whereas (49.5%) do not have adequate knowledge about treatment.

A good number of respondents responded that the major problem faced by the people living with HIV/AIDS is the discrimination in the society. It is not the disease that kills a HIV + rather it is the attitude of the people nearly 3/4th percent of adolescents feel sex education is most needed for reduce the risky behavior while more than (50%) of them do feel faithful to one another will be the better preventive of disease. Less than (40%) respondents have negative attitude towards the HIV infected people, they avoid such people, and they also frightened to meet with them, even they feel that all HIV + people should be killed because they cannot lead a normal life. A vast majority (76.3%) of the respondent girls reported of not having been tried by someone having sexual intercourse but 24% admitted that they had the experience of forced sex. A majority of respondents 54.8% have interested on pornography. This reveals that risky sexual encounters continued to exist among adolescent girls.

The study conducted on the adolescents it has been noticed that most of the adolescents tend to be largely on aware of human sexuality and reproductive health. So their knowledge on HIV/AIDS is incomplete and insufficient to live a healthy life without being succumbed to various deadly infections. Thus the knowledge could be imparted in different community setting with the help of the peer educators. Government need to be committed to tackle the arrangement of strong and informative mass media campaign for care and treatment for HIV+ person should be advocated and undertake innovative sex education programs. It is an urgent need to provide training for HIV support groups – AIDs service organization and health care providers and NGO workers to provide accurate, comprehensive up to date and easy to

understand information on cusses, prevention and treatment of the lathes disease. Further, an affective media can raise the awareness level and can also bring about sustainable behaviour change thereby vulnerability to the virus. Moreover, further studies need to be carried out to find out all aspects of stigma and discrimination associated with HIV/AIDs and infected people, so that better world can be created for one and all

Chapter 1:Introduction

This chapter deals with the introduction about female adolescents' knowledge attitude and practices towards HIV/AIDS in India in general and particularly in the context of the state of Odisha. Various concepts are associated with this present study such as HIV/AIDS as a pandemic, history of the pandemic in India, adolescents, their situation, their sources of knowledge, attitude and sexual practices that are concerned with the spread of HIV/AIDS among the adolescent ages are described in detail. Moreover, details about the HIV/AIDS in Odisha state are also given importance and these are the major highlight of this present chapter.

The period of adolescence is the second decade of life and it is a powerful formative period of transition from childhood to adulthood. It is a time of physical development, identity formation, relationship development and a time when vocational direction and life goals are expected to be formulated and create a conducive environment for their implementation. It is also one of the most crucial periods in the life of an individual, because between the ages of 10-19 years, many key biological, social, economical, demographic and cultural events occur that set the stage for adult life. It is the period during which rapid physical growth, physiological and psychosocial changes occur. Changes that occur within adolescents are manifold and their sexuality is characterized by experimentation, developing intimacy and relationship. During adolescence an intensive sexual drive develops and adolescents typically start exploring relationship with the opposite sex. Their engagement in sex related activities with known or unknown partners is risky and may lead to the spread of HIV/AIDS (Prabhakar, et.al, 2009).

Unfortunately adolescence lack of adequate knowledge about the sexual health and convergences of its mal adjustments, sexual activity in the light of poor knowledge is associated with increased risk behaviour. The concern for understanding the sexual behaviour of adolescents need to be increased as there is an increase in the sexual activity and also vulnerability to HIV infection caused due to increased early sexual debut. It is also important that adolescents need to be supported with adequate information so as to exhibit better sexual behaviour and protect them against the HIV infection. The health of adolescents has become a subject of increasing importance throughout the world. This is especially true with regard to their sexual health. Adolescent females experiencing early sexual debut are always been at greater risk of contracting HIV/AIDS. Adolescents become sexually active without knowing the facts and risks involved in it for its short term and long term health effects. This study helps in analyzing the knowledge base of female adolescents, their attitude towards the infection and also the current practices contributing to vulnerability to HIV/AIDS and helps in reducing such vulnerability among the female adolescents.

1.1 RATIONAL OF THE STUDY: For adolescents to take the risks that are important for their development and avoid those that will do them irreparable harm, in terms of their rights to health and development need to be fulfilled. This includes their rights to information and skills, a range of services, a safe and supportive environment, and opportunities to participate. However, this is not the case of HIV/AIDS affected adolescents where human rights are not

protected. Adolescents are vulnerable because they often do not know how serious the problem of HIV/AIDS is, how it is caused or what they can be done to protect themselves. Many adolescents do not even go to school, and do not have access to information about AIDS, or opportunities to develop the life skills that they need to turn this information into action. They also do not have access to services that take their specific needs into consideration. In addition to the individual characteristics of young people themselves, they are also influenced by other young people and made vulnerable by the attitudes and behaviour of the significant adults in their lives, such as parents, teachers and service providers. The wider context in which they live, learn and work, including social values and norms, policies and legislation, and their economic situation are also very important.

Some young people are particularly vulnerable. In countries where the predominant mode of transmission is by hero sex, girls are often more vulnerable than boys, for both biological and social reasons. Young people involved with sex work, migrants and refugee, and adolescents living on the street, in war situations or who are marginalized and discriminate against, are all likely to be especially vulnerable. Of course vulnerability is also increased by HIV/AIDS itself, for example young people who are living with HIV/AIDS and AIDS orphans (of whom large proportions are adolescents) become even more vulnerable to HIV/AIDS. Young People - a window of hope in the HIV/AIDS pandemic. The HIV-AIDS pandemic is one of the most important and urgent public health challenges facing governments and civil societies around the world. Adolescents are at the centre of the pandemic in terms of transmission, impact, and potential for changing the attitudes and behaviours that underlie in this disease. It is estimated that 50 percent of all new HIV infections are among young people (about 7,000 young people become infected even in one day), and that 30 percent of the 40 million people living with HIV/AIDS are in the 15-24 year age group. The vast majority of young people who are HIV positive do not know that they are infected and few young people who are engaging in sex know the HIV status of their partners.

1.2 IMPORTANCE OF HIV/AIDS AND ITS PREVALENCE: Adolescents are a rich human resource and an important part of the development process. Good health of adolescents will help in raising the health status of the community. Adolescents in India are highly vulnerable to human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Health of adolescent girls has an intergenerational effect. Adolescents are distinct population group with particular needs and capacities. Sexuality is one of the most sensitive issues associated with adolescence. Despite 35 percent of the population being in the 10-24 age groups, the health needs of the adolescents have neither been researched nor addressed adequately; particularly their reproductive health needs are often misunderstood, unrecognized or underestimated. Limited research shows that adolescents are indulging in premarital sex more frequently at an early age, the incidence of pregnancies among them is rising and most of them face the risk of induced abortions under unsafe conditions, and contracting sexually transmitted infections including HIV. Awareness about reproductive and sexual health is required to make adolescent girls responsible in their behavior. This will enable to enjoy their reproductive and sexual rights, including their rights to information, education and services. Further being

aware would facilitate adolescent girls to use crucial skills that will help them negotiate life's more difficult passages. It is a matter of real concern that most of adolescents do not talk about the issues and afflictions involving their private parts. This is due to the culture of silence in society regarding these diseases. Complete treatment is available but if left untreated or treated wrongly they can cause havoc to the person's health and society by making them all the more vulnerable to HIV and AIDS, infertility, etc. The importance of focusing on young people has been recognized at a global level by the 2001 UN General Assembly Special Session on HIV/AIDS, which endorsed a number of goals for young people, including: By 2003, establish time-bound national targets to achieve the internationally agreed global prevention goal to reduce; by 2005 HIV prevalence among both men and women aged 15-24 years in the most affected countries by 25 percent and by 25 percent globally by 2010. By 2005 ensure that at least 90 percent, and by 2010 at least 95 percent of both men and women have access to the information, education including peer education and youth-specific education, and services necessary to develop the life skills required to reduce their vulnerability to HIV infection: in full partnership with youth, parents, families, educators and health care providers.

Focusing on young people is likely to be the most effective approach, confronting the epidemic, particularly in high prevalence countries. In March 2013, WHO organized a global consultation, in collaboration with UNAIDS, UNFPA, UNICEF and Youth Net on the health services response to the prevention and care of HIV/AIDS among young people. Protecting young people from HIV and AIDS publication, on the role of health services is based on the outcome of this consultation, and has been developed for a wide leadership of policy makers and programmers. The publication provides an overview of the evidence on health service interventions that are important for achieving the global goals on young people and HIV/AIDS: information and counseling reducing risk through condoms and harm reduction; and the diagnosis, treatment and care of STIs and HIV/AIDS.

Myths and Misconceptions regarding HIV/AIDS: It is important to keep in mind that HIV is not transmitted by casual contacts like talking, sharing clothes and sitting together, shaking hands, sharing utensils and eating together; coughing and sneezing through the air we breathe or any insect and mosquito bite. HIV can be transmitted from person to person only if body fluid like blood, semen and vaginal fluid comes in contact with body fluids of an HIV infected or AIDS patient. The key to avoid infection is never allowing anyone's fluid to enter in one's body.

Impact of Social Discrimination people with HIV/AIDS: Some vital social issues unfold from these incidents. First and the most obvious are the gross callousness and cruelty meted out towards people with HIV/AIDS. They suffer all kinds of discrimination, intolerance and prejudice at all levels. The groups most affected by societal discrimination are women and adolescents. The discrimination and inhuman treatment includes public lynching of the victims, cruel refusal by the hospital staff for giving admission for treatment, deprivation from the sources of sustenance and livelihood, social ostracism, restriction of movement and association and other forms of victimization, marginalization and violence.

Secondly and strikingly, cases of gross violations of human rights and loss of dignity occur in all communities and among all sections of society. The above-mentioned cases show that the personnel of health care institutions, the villagers, the family members and even the school authorities have the tendency to exclude those with HIV/AIDS. Clearly, a high economic, educational or social status has no automatic linkage with enlightened or democratic or humanitarian practices. Moreover, the rising incidence of inhuman treatment and indignities heaped upon the HIV/AIDS patients raises another important question on our current perceptions of 'growth', 'development', 'modernization' and 'sophistication' of the 21st century (an era of knowledge and humanism) that leave untouched and often gives an added strength to our prejudiced mentality and to such barbaric practices. The HIV/AIDS positive victim finds herself in a helpless, defenseless and resource less state. The helplessness, isolation, marginalization and resourcelessness make the victims fearful and weak in standing up and challenging the power that is used against them in society. They become extremely frightened to seek redress. They and their relatives suffer from lack of access to employment, education, health care services, association, freedom of movement and above all, the right to live with dignity.

The studies have shown that discriminatory social environment has an adverse impact upon HIV/AIDS prevention and care programmes. Discrimination in access to social and economic rights creates an increased vulnerability to HIV infection and produces a negative effect upon the lives of the victims. Fear of social boycott and threats drive the infected people away from the health and social services programmes, which are created to restrict HIV transmission. Expulsion from the mainstream of society and victimization on the ground of the disease may lead to an increase in the risk of HIV infection. The project director, West Bengal State AIDS Control Society attributed the increasing number of HIV/AIDS cases to fear of ostracism and discrimination and said, "Discrimination has driven patients underground. This causes immense problems and delay, in their detection and treatment leading to more risk in further infection" (The Statesman: 08/03/2008). The President of Indian Network of People Living with HIV/AIDS stated: "we should look at treatments as kind of prevention programmes but no one talks about care, support and sympathy for the victims" (The Statesman: 08/03/ 2008). A Programme Officer of NSS of an educational institution has observed: "To isolate the HIV/AIDS infected persons from society is a crime which has a bad effect" (The Statesman: 12/03/2009).

Each year an estimated 333 million new cases of curable sexually transmitted infections (STIs) occur worldwide with the highest rates among 20-24 year olds, followed by 15-19 year olds. One in 20 young people are believed to be infected with STI each year, excluding HIV and other viral infections. Only minority of adolescents has access to any acceptable and affordable STI services.

1.3 Consequence of HIV/AIDS: HIV (Human immunodeficiency virus) major public infection has now spread to every country in the world and continues to be a -health issue. Statistics show that approximately 40 million people currently living with HIV infection and an estimated 40 million have died from this disease since the beginning of the epidemic. The scourge of HIV has been particularly devastating in sub-Saharan Africa which account for

almost 70% of new HIV infections globally. However, infection rates in other countries also remain high. In the United States, approximately 1 million people are currently infected, about 50,000 new HIV infections per year. In 2012 an estimated 156 youth died, out of 1% of the 13,712 people who died that year. Sub-Saharan Africa continues to have the highest number of HIV/AIDS cases, with close to 70 percent of the global total of HIV positive people. A vast majority will die in the next 10 years or so due to the infection and the existing poor socio-economic condition of that region (UNDP 2012). In Odisha 1276 died and in Ganjam 421 died due to HIV/AIDS (ICTC- REPORT-2012).

In Africa, the private sector is feeling the cumulative impact of the epidemic. A recent study of commercial farm in Kenya revealed high levels of Havoc one sugar estate, a quarter of the entire work force was infected with HIV. Direct cash costs related to HIV rose dramatically as company spending on funerals increased five-fold and direct health expenditure increased ten-fold. Due to the increasing health costs of the employees, the owners of a flower farm sold their company. Many companies have started prevention programmes in the work place so that they are able to protect their investment in human capital (IGNOU 2012). In the same time in Odisha Stigma and discrimination are very common among PLWHA. They experienced stigma and discrimination in many other spheres, including funeral proceeding, employment discrimination, broken confidentiality and community gossip and speculation (OSACS 2012). Many infected women were sent away from their husbands' houses, even infected daughters with children were sent out by their parents and many of them were excluded from access to family function. Many women experienced rejection from their in-laws and many widows were thrown out by their in-laws after the death of their husbands. Many women forced to do extra work because of their HIV positive status. Further they experienced stigma and discrimination as a result of having their confidentiality broken. Many women living with HIV/AIDS are never encouraged by their employers to be involved in the work force. This results into inadequate employment and also frequent loss of income (Solomon, S. & Buck, J., 2003).

The impact of HIV/AIDS is still not fully understood; particularly the long term nature of the disease is considered the epidemic comes in successive waves, first wave being HIV infection years later by a wave of opportunistic diseases and later still by a wave of AIDS illness and then death. The final wave, affects children societies and economy at various levels from the family and community to the national and international levels. In Kendrapara and Jagatsinghpur districts of Odisha there are about 72 couples in the past 12 months, two dozen women have had abortions because they were afraid of passing infection on to their children; the abortions were conducted in conformity with the medical termination of pregnancy Act, 1972. In recorded statements, the forced women expressed their willingness to abort their pregnancies (Samaj, 2011), since misconception and ill-conceived notion about HIV/AIDS are common in rural areas some of the couples who are HIV carriers are scared of being branded as AIDS patients. There are instances of AIDS Patient here being ostracized. Their family members also are ostracized as their neighbours maintain distance in their relationship. The Government provides free treatment and requisite medicines to the patients but many feel reluctant to come into the open to avail this medical care due to social stigma and security. Private source of medicines which are

expensive in Indian companies as the requisite raw materials for manufacturing these medicines to treat the killer disease come from abroad and that is quite expensive and not cost effective (Newmann, S. & Sarin, P., 2006).

Researchers found that average monthly expenditure exceeded income among females of people with HIV partly because of purchase of medicines, while these families spent less on entertainment and on children education to cope with rising care support and treatment costs due to HIV, Most people were also forced to sell assets and borrow from friends and relatives. The impact of AIDS on children continuous to count in various part of the world currently children under 15 account for one in six AIDS related deaths worldwide and one in seven new HIV infections after illness and death itself. The harshest impact on children is the loss of their parents' affection, support and protection, separation from siblings is frequent as orphans from large families are often send to live in different households. In addition to the psychological trauma suffered by these children poverty and social dislocation as well as stigma and discrimination may also be added to their woes and increases their vulnerability to HIV. Children alone face the burnt, of the dreaded disease their lives are cut short before they began to understand the world.while some other live longer only to suffer social and ostracization and humiliation. Members belonging to the families of HIV/AIDS from the urban clusters of different districts of Odisha refused to receive the monthly pension scheme meant for such infected people. The fear of getting being identified and the consequent of social stigma, has forced the targeted beneficiaries to shun the plan.

1.4 Indian Scenario and Need for prevention: India is a nation housing the third largest number of people living with the Human Immunodeficiency Virus and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome in the world: 130000 people in India become infected every year with young people, especially men who have sex with men, female sex workers, injecting drug-users and marginalized populations being disproportionately affected. Worldwide, the majority of HIV infections are transmitted through sex between men and women, and half of all adults living with HIV are women. (The New Indian Express- 1/1/2014)

The estimated number of people living with HIV/AIDS in India was 20.89 lakh with as estimated adult (15.49 age group) HIV prevalence of 0.27 percent in 2011.India has devastated as overall reduction of 57percent in the annual new HIVinfections among adult population from 2.74 lakh in 200 to 1.16 lakh, in 2011. It is estimated that around 1.5 lakh.lives have been saved due to ART till 2011(NACO 2013-14).

Odisha State Scenario: The state has recorded 1,428 deaths due to AIDS that include 518 deaths in Ganjam district, accounting for 35 per cent of total deaths due to AIDS in the state. Koraput is another district where 149 deaths due to AIDS have been recorded at 10.4 per cent. In Khurda, so far, 49 deaths due to AIDS have been registered. Sexual transmission of the virus is the cause in 87 per cent of the total HIV cases registered. This is followed by seven per cent infections to babies who contacted HIV from their mothers while two per cent was due to infected syringes and needles. While the state authority Odisha State AIDS Control Society (OSACS) says the state has low prevalence of HIV victims, some of the

women living with HIV told **Odisha** POST the number of registered women victims might be far higher, as not enough victims come forward due to social stigma surrounding the disease. Compared to 18,125 male infected HIV through sexual transmission, there are 9,529 women who received the virus through sexual intercourse (Sagar, 2014).

Situational analysis of Ganjam District of Odisha State: Ganjam district tops the list of most HIV victims in the state of Odisha with 12,017 people: 35.9 per cent of the total cases. Cuttack is second with 13.2 per cent victims, followed by Koraput with 5.1 per cent, Sambalpur with 5.1 and Khurda at number four with 4.7 per cent of all HIV-infected people living in 30 districts, District AIDS Prevention and Control Unit (DAPCU, 2013). According to official reports, 3,427 AIDS patients were identified in Ganjam till November 2012. While Aska has highest number of AIDS patients of 456, Chikiti has the lowest 40. Similarly, 60 cases were identified in Chhatrapur, 63 in Ganjam, 204 in Khallikote, 120 in Beguniapada, 341 in Polsara, 138 in Purushottampur, 161 in Kavisuryanagar, 139 in Hinjilicut, 349 in rangeilunda, 53 in Kukudakhundi, 88 in Digapahandi, 124 in Sanakhemundi, 152 in Bhanjanagara, 206 in Belaguntha, 177 in Buguda, 44 in Jagannathprasad, 68 in Dharakote, 120 in Dorada and 173 in Sheragada (Odisha Post, 2013).

Over 1,400 people have lost their lives due to AIDS in Ganjam district in the last 14 years as per the latest figures released by Odisha State AIDS Control Society (OSACS), the State-level nodal agency for fighting the dreaded disease. By the end of October, 2014, 12,307 persons in the district were identified as HIV positive while 1,404 persons succumbed to AIDS between 2000 and 2014. Besides, HIV tests were conducted on 5-59,425 persons during the period (DAPCU, 2013) and as per the reports of 'ARUNA', 2013 (a social service non-governmental voluntary organization) working for prevention of AIDS, majority of PLWHAS (People Living with HIV/ AIDS) are from rural Ganjam. Large scale migration, ignorance, low female literacy, inadequate prevention activities, stigma and discrimination are the reasons behind the spread of AIDS.

Preventive measures like Targeted Intervention Project (TIP) with migrants from the State and those coming to the State, Female Sex Workers (FSWs) and Male having Sex with Male (MSMs) have been launched in the district. Besides 17 migration-friendly information centers have been running. But, the situation has not improved. More than half of the AIDS affected people in the State are from Ganjam. The district has 26 Integrated Counseling and Testing Centers (ICTCs) including a mobile ICTC, a 10-bed community care centre and a 10-bed child care home besides a home-based care and support project in Aska and Hinjili blocks in which the ICTCs provide prevention of parent to child transition training. The Anti-Retroviral Treatment Centre at MKCG Medical College, Berhampur provides various facilities including counseling, testing, CD4 Count Test, treatment referral for opportunistic infections and medicines free of cost to the patients. Though several welfare measures including BPL cards and monthly Rs. 200 to the patients under Madhu-babu Pension Scheme have been made by the State Government; the patients are reluctant to avail those due to social stigma." An HIV positive person is more open and friendly with another HIV patient," said Loknath Mishra, Director of Aruna. While over seven lakh people of Ganjam have mi-

grated to other States as labourers, 5.59 lakh have undergone HIV test in the last 14 years (Mishra 2014).

1.5 Adolescents Knowledge and their role on Prevention: Young Girls during their adolescent period are often particularly vulnerable to sexually transmitted HIV infection as a result of drug-use. Studies have proved that Young people (15-24 years old) account for half of all new HIV infections worldwide and more than 6,000 become infected with HIV every-day. More than a third of all people living with HIV or AIDS are under the age of twenty five years and almost two-thirds of them are women (NACO, 2008). HIV/AIDS awareness needs to be reinforced among the students right from school to college levels. College is a good platform as the students at this level are to understand themselves well and teacher is the most authentic person to pass on the information to students on HIV/AIDS Just adding a chapter in the syllabi will not improve the situation. What is more important is making the youngsters feel responsible for their behaviour and life style (APSACS -2009).

HIV/AIDS have assumed epidemic form in India. An estimated 4 million persons are reported to be affected with HIV infection. The magnitude of the problem is expected to increase further. Around 50% of the reported cases are among the sexually active young people aged below 25 years. Adolescents are more vulnerable to HIV by certain taboos, ideologies and social norms. This is particularly the case where young people are denied knowledge and skills on sexual and reproductive matters, barred from reproductive health services including HIV prevention. Adolescents are left along to deal with the biological and social transformation often with no caring adult to talk.

HIV/AIDS is now the worst dredged epidemic in the world. More than 42 million people are HIV infected and there is no known medical treatment till date. AIDS has the power to change national destinies, bring misery to families and communities and touch the deepest social taboos. Beyond the personal tragedies caused by AIDS, there are economic tolls for businesses, regions and nations. "If 15% of a country's population is HIV positive nine nations by 2010, its gross domestic product (GDP) declines by about 1% each year. For example, it is predicted that South Africa's GDP will be reduced by 17% by 2010. It strikes at the productive and reproductive population, the young, to whom society looks for future enterprise, economic contribution and ideas. A country's GDP is correlated with its people's longevity, thus as the young die, economies wither. In South Africa, Botswana and Zimbabwe, based on current trends, more than 80% of 15-year-old boys will die before the age of 40." *Worlds Economic Forum Annual Meeting. 2008 – Global Health Initiative.*

Prevention is critical as there is currently no cure for AIDS. However prevention should go hand-in-hand with high quality healthcare, efforts to mitigate the epidemic's impact on society and the provision of antiretroviral drugs. These drugs have been shown to prolong lives, even if they cannot provide a cure. HIV/AIDS is seen to be everybody's problem, although it is directly affects fewer people. There is a sea change when the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria gives money to major companies and civil society to run joint HIV programmes in their local communities. Government has support of broad corporate initiatives on HIV/AIDS through tax breaks and training. This is a world where

strong leadership and growing cooperation between governments, business people and society have begun to turn the tide, to end the epidemic.

In India there is growing evidence that adolescents are becoming more sexually active outside of the institution of marriage. It is feared that this will lead to an increase in the spread of HIV/AIDS among adolescents and sow the seeds of social disorganization and unrest. Adolescents have relatively poor access to health care and education. With cultural norms opposing extramarital sexual behaviour, these implications may acquire threatening dimensions for the society and the nation.

India has reached to the top position with the largest number of people carrying the deadly HIV, much more than South Africa. Richard Feachem in-charge of malaria, tuberculosis and HIV at The Global Fund, one of the largest AIDS donors said in an interview in Paris; that “figures are much higher than those given by the Government of India.” Feachem said that this is “a wake-up call as the government is not doing enough and millions might die due to the delay” (UNAIDS. 2005). The Indian government is also criticized for clinging to the idea that the epidemic is limited to “high risk groups”, such as sex workers, drug users and truck drivers and that targeting them is the best strategy to contain the epidemic further. But this approach no longer reflects the reality at least some Indian states, where the epidemic is among the general population. In these states women who only have sex with their husbands may be the group at highest risk of HIV transmission, and although in Indian society men experience sex outside of marriage, but women do not have status to demand condom use of their husbands. Comprehensive AIDS education can make pupils aware of the need to protect them against infection. It can also bring about gradual changes in the wider social environment, making safer sex. Educating people about HIV /AIDS and prevention is complicated as India has many major languages and hundreds of different dialects. Education can be done at the national level as well as state and local level also.

In many parts of the world, discrimination prevents people with AIDS securing a job or caring for their families. Discrimination can cause isolation and marginalizes people who have AIDS. This can prevent people from getting treatment, which could save their lives. In order to tackled AIDS effectively in international level efforts to be made to end the discrimination against people with AIDS, educating people for safer sex and motivate to use drug, using appropriate media, provide condoms freely to people in the developing world, provide financial and medical assistance. According to the (UNAIDS 2012) what is needed on a massive national and international level is: End the stifling silence that continues to surround HIV in many countries. Explode myths and misconceptions that translate into dangerous sexual practices. Expand prevention initiatives such as condom promotion.

A trail of successful responses has already been blazed by a small number of dedicated communities and governments. The challenge for even-one is to adapt and massively expand successful approaches that make it harder for the virus to spread, and that make it easier for those affected to live full and rewarding lives (WHO, 2005). There are a number of different methods, which can be used to educate the public about the dangers of

HIV. Peer education is quite simply; a social form of education without classrooms or notebooks; where people are educated outside a "school" environment but still have the opportunity to ask questions. Sometimes the 'peer educators' will be from the group that is to be educated - a group of workmates might pick someone from amongst them to become the educator. Only other occasions the educator may be someone who has a similar social background, age and gender to the target audience, sometimes a person who is HIV+ most peer education focuses on providing information about HIV transmission and answering questions. The sessions take place wherever it is convenient, sometimes in Schools/Colleges, workplace or where a group of women gather to wash clothes.

Education is an important part of AIDS prevention, but it is only part. AIDS prevention work being done around the world it covers the search for a vaccine, distribution of condoms and research. Education however is a crucial factor in preventing the spread of AIDS and reducing numbers of deaths. The importance of effective education cannot be under estimated.

Although the AIDS epidemic continues the basic AIDS education remains fundamental to the global effort to prevent HIV transmission. AIDS education can be target for all ages, and sexually active adults are one principal target. AIDS education is also vitally important for young people, however, Schools/Colleges one principal point-of-contact for them receiving this education. The World AIDS Campaign's theme for 2008 was "**Stop AIDS**". This theme is however not specific to World AIDS Day alone but it will also remain the focus until 2020. "Stop AIDS; Keep the Promise" is an appeal to governments and policy makers to ensure to meet the targets they have agreed to fight against spread of AIDS. Some of the most important of these promises are in the UN Declaration of Commitment, which was signed by all 189 members of the UN in June 2008. The governments of these countries committed to take action on HIV and AIDS in the fields of leadership, prevention, care and support, treatment, reducing vulnerability, and human rights. The following targets were set for the end of 2008:

- Reduce HIV prevalence by 25 percent among men and women aged 15-24 in the most affected countries.
- Ensure that at least 90 percent of young people aged 15 to 24 have access to the information, education and services necessary to develop the life skills required to reduce their vulnerability to HIV infection.
- Reduce the proportion of infants infected with HIV by 20 percent by increasing access to services, which prevent mother-to-child transmission.
- Increase annual spending on HIV and AIDS to 57-10 billion in low and middle-income countries and those countries experiencing or at risk of experiencing rapid expansion of HIV epidemics.

The epidemic of HIV has been steadily spreading for the past two decades and now affects every country in the world. Each year, more people die and the number of people living with AIDS continues to rise, in spite of the fact that we have developed many proven HIV prevention -methods. One of the key means of HIV prevention is education, teaching people about AIDS: what it is, and how people can protect themselves over half of the

world's population is now under 25 years old, and they are both the age group most vulnerable for AIDS. Educating young can help to prevent AIDS effectively.

Despite women's higher biological, social and economic disadvantages in most societies which increase their HIV vulnerability. Women's Adolescent girls are denied the knowledge and tools to protect themselves from HIV. Surveys in 38 countries found extremely low HIV-transmission knowledge among 15 - 24 year old women (UNFPA, 2011). It is vital to implement comprehensive strategies, including gender-specific and culturally specific services that help women counteract discriminatory social and economic factors. The key components include: access to education (particularly secondary education); strengthening legal protection for women's property and inheritance rights; eradicating violence against women and girls; and ensuring equitable access to HIV care and prevention services.

In June 2012, the World Health Organization and the International Center for Research on Women led a consultation of experts to rethink classic HIV prevention based on women's and girls' distinct needs. They also aimed to improve HIV interventions that target men. Gender-sensitive approaches, at a minimum, recognize that women and men have different prevention, care and support needs. For example, diagnosing and treating sexually transmitted infections need to be integrated into family planning, reproductive health clinics. Then women will be able to gain access to these centers without fear of social censure (WHO, 2003).

Interventions that empower women and girls attempt to equalize the power balance between women and men. Examples include increasing women's access to assets and resources, such as land and inheritance rights, and facilitating women's networks and strengthening grassroots community organizations. Other projects go beyond immediate gender-specific needs. They are based on the belief that empowerment can only be achieved when women take control of all aspects of their lives.

Although the epidemic is well spread into its third decade, basic AIDS education remains fundamental to the response. For instance, in India, behavioural survey data showed that 30 percent of women had not heard of HIV or AIDS; Rural women were the least informed: less than 25 percent of rural women in the states of Bihar (18.7 percent), Gujarat (22.7 percent) and Uttar Pradesh (24.3 percent) were aware that HIV could be transmitted sexually (NACO, 2008).

Several innovative programmes have been implemented to create awareness among general public as well as high risk population. School and College based AIDS education programme has been organized by Government and non government organizations encouraging students to adopt positive life styles required for prevention of HIV/AIDS. Often such efforts have become sporadic than regular feature in the schools and colleges. Hence, the present study is felt necessity to impart HIV/AIDS information to adolescent girls who have great potential to learn and increase their knowledge, develop positive attitude and

favourable practice regarding HIV/AIDS and also to reach out to their peers, families and the society at large with AIDS awareness message.

1.6 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

To understand adolescents' girls knowledge, attitude and practices towards HIV / AIDS in Odisha both rural urban as well as those who resides in the hostels under security

Specific objectives of the study:

1. To study the socio-demographic particulars of the respondents.
2. To assess their knowledge pertaining to HIV/AIDS, causes, treatment of the disease, mode of the transmission, curability nature of diseases, availability of ICTC, prevention strategy, myth and misconception, stigma, discrimination related to AIDS.
3. To determine the respondents' attitudes towards HIV/AIDS, attitude towards the disease, negative attitude, positive attitude of the victim, myth and misconceptions related to HIV/AIDS.
4. To collect information regarding sexual experiences, present practices prevalent among the respondents.

1.7 HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

1. As knowledge about HIV/AIDS increases, there is decline in the risky sexual practices among female adolescents.
2. Lower the family income higher the incidences of their sexual encounter.
3. Female adolescents from joint family demonstrate positive attitude towards HIV/AIDS.
4. Female adolescents from lack of proper knowledge encounter coercive sex without any safety measure.
5. Female adolescents from tribal domicile do not have myths about HIV/AIDS.

1.8 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The respondents may be dishonest in answering about their sexual encounters, behavior and current sexual activity. The interview schedule took a lot of time to complete this study, some respondents tired and some respondents were able to give out their data in two different sessions only. The school holidays which were a hindrance in collecting the data from the students and the researcher had to wait up to the end of the holidays to continue the process of data collection.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

In research, a body of literature is a collection of published information and data relevant to a research question, on a particular subject matter. Hence a review of the literature is an essential part of any scholar's academic research project. The review is a careful examination of a body of literature pointing towards the answer to your research question. Literature review typically includes journals, scholarly books, authoritative databases and primary sources. Sometimes it includes newspapers, magazines, other books, films, audio and video tapes, and other secondary sources. In this chapter, the consolidated and presented the various forms of secondary literature available pertaining to female adolescents' knowledge, attitude, experiences and practices towards HIV/AIDS. It contains concrete information about the existing shortcomings present in the body of knowledge and reveals the dire need for augmentation in the form of this present research. Hence this research originates from the existing shortcoming found in the body of knowledge by carefully reviewing the existing pieces of knowledge available through different sources of literature. The available literature has been organized and presented under the following subheadings keeping in view of the specific objectives of the present research study, they are:

- 2.1 Conceptual Understanding of HIV/AIDS:
- 2.2 Adolescents: The Immediate Future of the Country
- 2.3 Knowledge of Adolescents on HIV/AIDS
- 2.4 Attitude of Adolescent and HIV / AIDS
- 2.5 Existing Sexual Experience and Practices among Adolescents
- 2.6 Lack of Understanding on HIV/AIDS
- 2.7 Existing Policies & Programmes

2.1. CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING OF HIV/AIDS:

AIDS is a new disease. Being new, there is a certain amount of mystery. Where did it come from? Why the developed countries are did it first affect the individuals? What is the natural history of infection? What is to happen to all of us over a long period of time? These mysteries breed fear in some people causing "AIDS-phobia", which has further compounded the problem. As evident by its name, AIDS is not a single disease but a syndrome is a set of diseases, which results from the destruction of the body's defenses by the human immunodeficiency virus-HIV. Since HIV causes damage to the immune system, the antibodies detected in the blood of the carries of the HIV are ineffective in halting the damage caused by the virus, which may be present in large numbers in the body. Therefore, the body cannot be protected against other infections and cancers, some of which they form the direct causes of death. Because of the way that the virus infects cells, developing a cure or vaccine is extremely difficult. Here, understanding HIV/AIDS in totality is of greater importance and requires detail examinations on the subject matter.

No one knows exactly where the Human Immunodeficiency Virus originated, or the conditions that led to its spread among humans in the early 1980s. HIV-1 was identified in 1983 by Robert Gallo and other medical scientists at the National Cancer Institute in Bethesda, Maryland in USA. At about the same time, Luc Montagnier of the Pasteur Institute in Paris isolated HIV-2 from AIDS patients. These two HIV viruses are distinguishable by

their genome make up today, but are believed to have had a common ancestor in Africa (Singhal & Rogers, 2003). The first case of AIDS was diagnosed in the year 1981. Some physicians in California and New York in USA came across unusual opportunistic infections among homosexual men. These infections did not respond to medication. Therefore, the patients could not live longer and eventually they died. These patients did not show usual conditions of illness known to Medical Science at that time. Thus, it became evident that we have a new illness to be treated. This new disease was named: “Acquired Immune-deficiency Syndrome” (AIDS).

As it was thought before, neither HIV nor AIDS is the problem of commercial sex workers and their clients only. Neither it’s the problem of Homosexuals (LGTBI-Lesbians, gays, transgender, bisexual and interest) alone. Neither it’s a problem on injecting drug users alone; nor are those suffering from blood disorders that require frequent transmission only vulnerable to HIV. Maximum numbers of HIV positive patients are young adults in the age group of 15-49 years, which contribute 89% of HIV positive population. Young people aged 15-24 accounted for an estimated 45% of new HIV infections worldwide in 2007. Young people need to know how to protect themselves from HIV and have the means to do so. Better access to testing and counseling will inform young people about their HIV status, help them get the care they need, and avoid further spread of the virus.

HIV –Human Immuno deficiency virus, it is the name of the virus that causes AIDS. Human because it only infects, survives, multiply and exits from human body only and Immune deficiency because the virus the body’s protection mechanism (immune system) that fights against diseases. AIDS- Acquired Immune-deficiency Syndrome. AIDS is called Acquired, because it is always caught, received (become infected) from someone else. Immune deficiency, as mentioned above, because the virus destroys the body’s protection mechanism (immune system) that fights against diseases and syndrome, because this illness has a variety and cluster of signs and symptoms

Fig 2.1 Structure of HIV Virus

The HIV (Human Immune-deficiency Virus) is a unique virus, very small and fragile. It cannot survive outside the human body. HIV is a member of a group of viruses called Retroviruses. The virus enters the Helper T-cells of the immune system. In the helper T-cells it destroys genetic material and the damage caused is permanent. Thus, HIV hinders our immune system from protecting our body. Once HIV has attacked our immune system, our defense system becomes weakened with the absence of helper T-cells; opportunistic infections attack the human body. People with HIV thus will stay sick although and die eventually. All body fluids contain helper T-cells. The concentration is high in blood, semen and vaginal secretion (WHO SEARONo26). HIV was first identified as “Lymphadenopathy Associated Virus” by the French Scientists and Virus III by the researchers of USA and the present name that is HIV was given in May 1986 by International Committee on Taxonomy. Both HIV-1 and HIV-2 are found in India, although the majority of infections (91 percent) are from HIV-1, subtype C, HIV in India is overwhelmingly transmitted heterosexually. The three other known routes of transmission are through contaminated blood, use of unsterilized syringes and needles by injecting drug users, and prenatal transmission.

The word “virus” is Latin for “poison” an appropriate name for HIV, since no cure exists for it. The HIV which is so small that 16,000 can sit on the head of a pin, invades a living white blood cell, and reprograms it to reproduce the virus. One HIV virus can make an

astounding 10 billion copies of itself in a day, with a mutation can make HIV resistant to drugs. The rapid mutation also makes the development of a vaccine very difficult. The HIV infects a type of white blood cells known as T lymphocytes, also called t helper cells. They protect the human body against infections. The CD4 cells count measure the strength of an individual's immune system. A healthy adult has between 700 to 1,500 CD4 cells per cubic milliliter of blood. Over a period of years the T- cell count of an HIV positive individual drops to a critical level, below 500, a sign of a depressed immune system. Below 200, the individual usually develops opportunistic infections (Singhal and Rogers, 2003). Acquire Immune-Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) is a serious illness and public health crisis that merits the concerns of everyone. AIDS, which is one of the most dreaded diseases of humanity, has spread to every part of the world, threatening people from all spheres of life. The first case of HIV infection was reported in 1981 among the homosexuals in the United States of America, while HIV was first reported in India, in 1986 among the commercial sex workers from Chennai.

2.1.1 Definition and Magnitude of RTIs and STIs

Almost about 20% of HIV infected people are having STI infections. According to the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), about 25% of sexually active teenagers get a sexually transmitted disease (STDs) every year, and 80% of infected teens don't even know they have an STD, passing the diseases along to unsuspecting partners. One important intervention that can help in curbing HIV infection and AIDS menace in preventing and treating sexually transmitted diseases that increase the vulnerability of the people to HIV infections.

- Sexually Transmitted Infection (STI): Diseases which are transmitted during intimate contact unprotected sexual intercourse, vaginal, oral and anal are called sexually transmitted diseases commonly these diseases infect and damage sexual tract if not diagnosed and treated at right time and can also spread to other parts of body.
- Reproductive Tract Infections (RTI): Reproductive organs include testicles and seminal vesicles along with sexual organs like penis in males, uterus, ovaries, cervix, sexual tract including vagina that is a part of passage for giving birth to child, in females. These reproductive organs can get infected due to various reasons like poor hygiene of these parts especially during menstruation in females and also due to infections which spread through blood and can infect many other parts of body (NACO 2008).
- Common Sexually Transmitted Infections : The common sexually transmitted infected are presented in the Table-2.1

Table No. 2.1: Common Sexually Transmitted Infections:

Bacterial	Viral	Protozoal/fungal
Gonorrhoea	Genital Herpes	Chlamydia
Syphilis	Hepatitis B	Candida
Non specific, mixed infections	HIV	Trichomonas

- Signs and Symptoms of Common STIs:

These STIs have varied manifestations, but common symptoms are:

- Discharge which is foul smelling and itchy coming from the genital tract
- Ulceration on the genital organs
- Pain during urination
- Swelling in groin, testicular swelling
- Pain in lower abdomen or lower back particularly in females (AFE01-2011)

2.1.2 The Causes of HIV/AIDS-

The disease is caused by a new and deadly virus called HIV (The Human Immune Deficiency Virus). HIV can remain in the body for years perhaps even decades before any damage shows up as visible symptoms. The term AIDS (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome) refers strictly speaking only to the last fatal stage of HIV infection. This is often also “full-blown AIDS”. Viruses are the smallest of all disease-producing organisms: much smaller than the bacteria which are too small to be visible through an ordinary microscope only. For the virus which cause AIDS. The internationally accepted name is now HIV. The AIDS virus gradually disables the body’s immune system. The infected person becomes increasingly vulnerable to all most any infection by another virus, a bacterium, a fungus or a parasite. The infections mainly occur in the skin, the lungs, the digestive system, the nervous system and the brain. He or she suffers a long period of illness and disease.

(a) *Poverty* - HIV infection is mostly due to low socio- economic status, marked by low income levels, poverty, low educational levels, subordination especially in sexual decision making within the family and community. Economic hardship coupled with commercial sexual exploitation, sex tourism and negative attitude towards the women dignity and security, it further perpetuates the risk exposure HIV/AIDS.

Poverty is often cited as a cause of child prostitution. Many unfortunate girls are sold in various part of world by their parents. Who are unable to maintain their children due to acute poverty but those who act as pimps or brokers in flesh trade and brothel keepers, who hunt for these teenage girls to make money rather purchase or kidnap them by deceitful means and force them into the flesh trade. These victims are taken into the brothels where they are brutally treated and brutally treated and confined in complete seclusion in a tiny room without food until they give their consent to enter into prostitution. Poverty is driving children from small villages in to brothels of cities across the borders (Panu 2010).

(b) *Trafficking* - Because of increase in tourism, the trafficking in human beings has become an international phenomenon. Prostitution attracts foreign tourists and thus helps in bringing foreign exchange. Thousands of rural and women and girls from small towns are trafficked in to urban and city year where they work under conditions tantamount. Forms of international trafficking range from bride syndicates, forced marriages, abuse of entertainment work, to contract work as domestic helpers, all of such can result in sexual exploitation and yet occur under the legal cover of labour migration. Those are sending, transit or receiving centers for the trafficking of girls children.

(c) *Role of Family*- In general for juvenile prostitution family plays as essential role, this leads minor to prostitute them. Majority of girl prostitute had experience of sexual violence during infancy. Particularly on the part of family members like father, step father, uncles, brothers, step brothers and grandfathers. Usually it is the family itself that decides to trade its daughters as the item of trade.

(d) *Cultural tradition*- India has had a unique history linked to Jogin and Devdasi system of temple dances. From ancient times young girls were dedicated to Hindu temples at early ages and they become brides of god and were barred from marriage. Devdasis, little girls of just 12 or 13 from 80% of brothel population in Maharashtra and Karnataka. In certain communities religion sanction is given to child prostitution.

(e) *Natural disasters*- Natural disasters like earthquakes, floods, cyclones or manmade cause like displacement for mega projects, without proper rehabilitation schemes also form the reason for this evil. Thus the desire to escape from chronic economic and social crises makes many girl children highly vulnerable to sexual exploitation.

(f) *Biological Factors*- Biologically women are twice more likely to become infected with HIV through unprotected heterosexual intercourse with men. Women's susceptibility to infection is manifested in their proneness to get RTIs (reproductive tract infection), the complications of which are more serious in women as the infection is transmitted to the offspring. They are limited in their ability to protect themselves from high-risk sex or negotiate condom use with the partner, more apt to suffer from asymptomatic infections and remains untreated and less likely to seek treatments, even for symptomatic infections (BuragohainTurujyoti; 2008).

(g) *Lack of information*- Ignorance about the ways and means of HIV transmission leads to vulnerability of people to get HIV infection. In many societies women are expected to be ignorant about sex and passive in sexual interactions. The prevailing culture restricts women's ability to ask for information about sex out of fear that they will be thought to be sexually active (Caravano, 1992). Due to prevailing ignorance and lack of general sensitivity, women suffer in health silently, particularly when it is related to sexuality reproduction.

(h) *Adverse impact of social discrimination*- Discrimination in access to social and economy rights creates an increased vulnerability to HIV infection and produces a negative effective upon the lives of the victims. Fear of social boycott and threats drive the infected people away from the health and social services programmes, which are created to restrict HIV transmission. Expulsion from the main stream of society and victimization on the ground of the disease may lead to an increase in the risk of HIV infection. "Discrimination has driven patients underground. This causes immense problems and delay, in their detection and treatment leading to more risk in further infection" (The states man: 2004).

2.1.3 The Nature of the Virus:

HIV selectively infects specific white blood cells CD4 that are an essential part of the body's immune defense system. HIV attacks and inactivates these particular kinds of white

blood cells. The CD4 helper cells are vital in controlling the body's defense to many diseases. They also recognize disease organisms and cancer cells, which the white cells must destroy after an infection. The CD4 helper cells stimulate the production of a large army of white blood cells to fight the infection. Sometimes they are successful in this. Sometimes the infection of cancer is so overwhelming, or grows so rapidly, or it is composed of cells immune to the CD4 cells, that the illness wins. Sometimes the body itself suffers from a weakness of the cells that provide immunity, such as the CD4 cells, and so the disease overwhelms the body. This partly explains why people can die from any illness. In the case of HIV, the virus progressively destroys the ability of the CD4 cells to counter some of the many diseases to which the body is immune (Poricha, 2009). However the body remains able to counter many other diseases and cancers. This is why it is possible go living even if a person is HIV positive. The few diseases that do occur in such people can be treated. As more and more CD4 cells destroyed, the efficacy of this treatment is reduced, and so treatment becomes harder to maintain. When the CD4 cell counts falls to 200 or less then the individual develops AIDS. When the CD4 cells are destroyed, the infected person becomes susceptible to range of opportunistic infectious diseases and cancers and the group of such conditions is called AIDS. HIV may also directly infect nerve cells and cause neurological disorders. HIV takes a long time to cause damage. HIV infection is presumed to be live long and the infected person is likely to remain infectious for life (NACO-2008).

2.1.4 HIV Infection:

- *Natural history of HIV infection-* People Infected with HIV may take ten years before they develop AIDS as HIV takes a long time to do damage. It is therefore important to distinguish between being infected with HIV and having AIDS. Those infected with HIV may suffer from disorders and develop signs which are suggestive of being infected with HIV. Acute HIV syndrome, associated with sero conversion can occur as early as few weeks after a person infected. The person may be asymptomatic or develop 'flu like' symptoms and signs which are fever, lymphadenopathy (swelling of lymph glands), night sweats, skin rash and cough. The period before the development of an antibody response usually between 2-12 weeks is often referred to as the 'window period' when a person is infectious but not positive in HIV-antibody tests. Several years after the infection, generalized painless swelling of lymph glands develops which persists for few months to many years. People with persistent generalized lymphadenopathy (PGL) may also suffer from fever, night sweats, diarrhea, loss of weight and infections such as thrush and herpes. The cluster of these signs and symptoms is called AIDS related complex or ARC. The diagnosis of having AIDS, the end stage of the disease, is demonstrated by the presence of one or more of the several opportunistic infections, cancers and other infections like pneumonia, persistent diarrhea, TB, skin cancer called Kaposi's sarcoma and infections of the nervous system leading to deterioration of intellectual capacity (dementia). It is essential to do demonstrate the presence of HIV in the blood with the help of sensitive blood tests. The most widely used is the Enzyme Linked Immune Sorbent Assay (ELISA) which detects the antibody generated in response to infection by HIV. Western Blot, a more expensive test is no longer recommended for routine supplemental testing (NACO 2007).

- **Incubation Period-** While the natural history of HIV infection is not yet fully known current data suggest that the incubation period is uncertain, (from a few months to 6 years or even more) from HIV infection with HIV who will developed clinical disease remain uncertain –possibly 10-30 percent of those infected with HIV will developed AIDS by the end of ten years.
- **Window period:** The period of time after a person becomes infected with HIV, but before antibodies have been formed is called window period. This period is usually two to three weeks and is rarely longer than three months. The virus is present in the blood. It can be detected by an antigen test. But an antibody test will prove negative. It may be noted that the antibodies developed against HIV within the body are not capable of fighting off the germs.
- **Full-blown AIDS:** By the time an infected person reaches the fourth stage, his/her immune system collapse. The patient is now faced with major life-threatening infection. Pneumonia caused by the parasitic pneumocysts carinic is common. A type of cancer affecting the skin called Kapozi's Sarcoma is also common in many patients. The patient usually becomes thin and grossly fatigued. Very often the patient also suffers from multiple infections like herpes and tuberculosis. Full-blown AIDS seems to be fatal. Some patients with regular medication, exercise and care have lived longer. However, they survive for not more than three or four years. Experience in India shows that most patients diagnosed with full-blown AIDS die within less than six months of the diagnoses. In exceptional, cases some have survived for one to two years (AFE-01-2011).

- **Mode of Transmission-**

HIV has been isolated from the body fluids of infected persons, including saliva & tears. However, only blood, semen, vaginal infections, and breast milk has been implicated in transmission. Detailed epidemiological studies throughout the world have documented only three modes of transmissions: sexual, parental and mother-to- fetus/infant. The acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) and the entire spectrum of disease has become a problem of intense international interest. The causing virus is not transmitted through the air, casual contact, by insects, by food or water. Modes of transmissions are:

- (a) **Sexual Transmission:** - The infection can be transmitted during sexual intercourse and between men and women. Certain sexual patterns and practices increase the risk of infection more than others. Relation with multiple sexual partners which is increases the chances of encountering someone who is infected, especially in an area where HIV infection is very common. Among sexual practices, receptive anal intercourse with an infected partner is very likely to lead to infection. The mucosa lining of the rectum is delicate and tears ruptures easily during anal intercourse. This allows infected lymphocytes and virus in semen to enter the tissue and blood stream of the receptive partner, whether male or female. Apart from it person infected with sexual transmitted disease like syphilis can transmit the infection easily through exposed wound (NACO 2007).

Worldwide, sexual intercourse is the most frequent mode of transmission of HIV. The virus can be transmitted from an infected person to his or her sex partner (man to

woman, woman to man and man to man). Women are more at risk of getting the infection than men. During sexual intercourse (vaginal, anal, and possibly oral), damage to the linings of sexual organs such as vagina or rectum can facilitate transmission of HIV from the infected partner to the uninfected only by exchange of body fluids. The virus is also transmitted during vaginal intercourse. Both male and female partners can be infected in this way. Risk is equal for both men and women. Usually sexually transmitted diseases as stated are more readily transmitted from men to women than from women to men. It is also not clear how readily the virus is transmitted during vaginal intercourse or what are the chances of infections associated with a single act of intercourse with an infected person. In both vaginal and anal intercourse using a condom or vaginal contraceptives reduces the chances of transmission (Alexis et al 2012).

It is not known whether getting or other sexual practices, such as oral genital contact or kissing, transmit the virus less. Since HIV is found in semen and sometimes in saliva, and since oral-genital contact transmits other infections, most infectious disease experts recommend avoiding these and any other practices that might be transfer by body fluids. Hetero sexual intercourse may be the major route of HIV transmission in developing countries. In central Africa and in Haiti, women are as likely men to be infected and female prostitutes are thought to be transmitting the virus to their clients. Other sexually transmitted disease may facilitate transmission of HIV virus. Cancroids, herpes and some other sexually transmitted disease can cause open genital sores, possibly allowing the virus to enter the blood stream. Theoretically, the best way to avoid sexually transmitted HIV infection is to avoid intercourse with any unknown person. Since it is usually not possible to identify such persons by their appearance, sexually abstinence or consistent use of condoms and vaginal cream offers the best protection (Sethy 2007).

(b) Transmission through Blood and Blood Products Transfusion-Some blood components transmit the virus. Red blood cells, plasma, whole blood, and clotting factor of blood may contain the virus. Other product prepared from blood is albumin, globulin (gamma globulins), and hepatitis – B Vaccine which have not been shown to pose any risk. The process of separating and manufacturing these products from whole blood inactivates the virus. HIV antibodies may still be present and recipient's blood can give positive test for six months after they receive the products. This does not indicate infection. However heat treatment during the manufacture of Factor VIII concentrate (a blood clotting agent used by hemophiliacs) also inactivates most of the virus, greatly reducing the risk of infection. Blood transfusion seems to pose a greater risk to infants due to immature immune systems and they receive larger doses of the virus relative to their body size and due to shorter incubation period. Currently as per instruction all blood donors are initially screened and blood is not accepted from high-risk individuals in various countries. Blood that has been collected for use is tested for the presence of antibody to the AIDS virus; however, some people may have had a blood transfusion prior to March 1985. Before we knew how to screen blood for safe transfusion and may have become infected with the AIDS virus. Fortunately there are not how a large number of these cases. With routine testing of blood products, the blood supply for transfusion is now safer than it has ever been with regard to AIDS. In 1998 about 60% HIV patient were blood transfusion related. Most of these people were women. Who had

been subjected to transfusion for anemia? As a medical practitioner can play a part in at least preventing the spread of infection (NACO 2011).

(c) Transmission by sharing Contaminated Needles by Intravenous Drug Users (IDU): Drugs users, who injected drugs into their veins, are another population group at high risk and with high rates of infection by the AIDS virus. Users of intravenous drug make up 25 percent of the cases of AIDS throughout the country. The AIDS virus is carried in contaminated blood left in the needle, syringes, or other drug related implements and the virus is injected into the new victim by reusing (infected) dirty syringes and needles. Even the smallest amount of infected blood left in a used needle or syringe can contain live AIDS virus to be passed onto the next user of those dirty elements. Drugs users are addicted due to poor health, family disruption, emotional disturbances and sexual disruption either or one reason or another, but they are not going to be changed in their behavior. For these people, the only way not to get AIDS is to use a clean, previously unused needle, syringe or any other tool necessary for the injections of the drugs solution. A part from it by sharing razor and tooth brushes. AIDS virus can be infected in new victim by two reasons. One that blood is a good media which can be transmitted by erosion of mucous membrane of anal cavity or skin of face and secondly saliva is the media for transmission (NACO 2012).

(d) Parental Transmission-Parental transmission occurs through the transfusion of infected blood or blood products or the use of blood-contaminated needles, syringes or other skin-piercing instruments. The risk of acquiring HIV infection is related to the size of the inoculum: recipients of unit of HIV-infected blood for transfusion have virtually a 100% probability of becoming infected.

(e)

➤ **Maternal – fetal transmission (mother-to-child transmission)** -The infected mother can transmit the infection to the baby in the womb or at birth through exposure to infected maternal blood or after birth through breast feeding. The risk of transmission from the infected mother to the baby is not exactly known. It is expected due to high concentration of virus in the blood through infected maternal blood during pregnancy or transfusion of infected blood to the mother during pregnancy and child birth or through breast feeding. Though it has been reported that in mother's milk the concentration of the HIV virus is less but at the same time immune defence system of the baby is also very low in comparison to HIV. This means that one to two percent of newborn babies are already being infected with HIV. The proportion of those who will subsequently develop AIDS and the impact that infection with the virus has on the general health of these children are still being closely studied (OSACS 2012).

➤

➤ **Perinatal transmission-** Transmission of HIV infection from a woman to her fetus/fetus/infant may occur before, during and after birth. The overall risk of HIV transmission from and HIV-infected woman to her fetus or infant in utero or during delivery is 15-39%. Postnatal transmission through breast milk has been described in a small number of infants or mothers who acquired HIV infection after delivery.

In fact newborn baby can be infected in the following ways:

- a. Presence of infection in mother.

- b. Infection in mother during pregnancy (i) by sexual contact (ii) by infected blood transfusion during pregnancy (iii) by infected blood transfusion during childbirth.
- c. Breast feeding stage (infection occurs) (i) by sexual contact after child birth, (ii) by infected bold transfusion (iii) infected blood transfusion (iii) Infected blood transfusion to the baby (Sethy 2007).
- d.
- (f) **Attitude of the Health Personnel** - Alpanasagar public health analyst raised issue of the health care needs of HIV positives person's, their relationship with the structure of the health system and health sector reform the attitude of the health personnel and the burden of women by reliance on community care. She highlighted the issues of appropriate technology in the Indian context for the medical care of HIV positive persons. One of the issues that patients with AIDS are also patient with other disease. And especially patient with AIDS have opportunistic infection. General health services need an integrate approach because patient with AIDS can have tuberculosis, pneumonia and they can have variety of other disease. And therefore, in this kind of a situation how can you positively being about a condition where you can start talking about integration and general health services being given more importance. Another issue which has been raised in Dr. Kaushals papers the issues of using disposable syringes today. The reason why disposable syringes were that the risk of AIDS was supposed to be then decreased we were supposed to dispose them. This does not happen in India, thus it has quoted information about where it is being shown that doctors are thus transmitting AIDS through these syringes.
- (g) UNAIDS Country Coordinator Denis Broun said at a news conference, adding. "The need of the hour is to reach out to young women living in extremely difficult and marginal circumstances". Broun said that in addition to a lack of awareness about the virus in Indian communities, women's "vulnerability" to HIV often is because of their husbands, with about 80 percent of new HIV cases among women last year occurring within marriage. Archana Tamang, chief of the women's human rights said that women also are at greater risk of contracting HIV because of biological differences, gender disparities, lack of education and sex trafficking. More than two million HIV-positive girls and women live in India (New Indian express, 3rd March 2006). If one is infected with HIV, the virus can spread to another human being through the following ways.
- Unprotected Sex.
 - By Receiving HIV infected blood.
 - By using unsterilized needles
 - From an HIV positive mother to her baby

Fig 2.2: Channels of HIV/AIDS Transmission

Myth and Misconception about HIV/AIDS

The broad introduction on myths and misconceptions of HIV/AIDS/STDs deals effectively with the inaccurate information, which is quite often believed and passed on without the authenticity of the source. In this light, you have to focus on the various routine activities that are done with the anticipation of getting infected by HIV/AIDS person out of sheer fear, ignorance, anxiety etc.

Most people at work are safe because contact with blood is not the part of work. The virus is mainly transmitted through the transformer of blood or sexual fluids and is not transmitted through casual contact. There are no risks involved. You may share the same telephone or work side by side in a crowded factory with other HIV infected persons. HIV is not spread through routine contact in restaurants, workplace or schools. There is no harm in kissing, embracing or caressing an infected person provided it is a normal dry kiss or a gentle hold. Risk from a dry kiss is almost zero. Moreover the number of infected persons in general population is low and the risk of catching HIV from kissing someone on the lips or embracing an infected person is almost zero. However, the western practice of kissing

(French kiss) where tongue and saliva enter another person's mouth carries higher risk, especially if one person has sores in the mouth, cracked lips or bleeding gums. So far, we have come across only one such case of 'mouth to mouth' spread.

The chances of getting infection through a 'shake hand' is minimal, as long as the skin is intact without any breaks because in adults the virus is mainly transmitted through the transfer of blood or sexual fluids. Since there is no contact of blood or sexual fluids during a casual shake hand, there are no risks involved. Sharing the same telephone with other people in your office or working side by side in a crowded factory with other infected persons and even sharing the same cup of tea cannot transmit the infection. These acts will not expose a person to the risk of contracting the infection being in contact with the sweat. It is certain that no one will get HIV from a mosquito bite there are many "reasons to support this. Mosquito transmitted diseases are common in the world. All the organisms that are transmitting disease through the mosquito have a lifecycle in the mosquito. When the mosquito bites it ingest the blood and injects its saliva. HIV is not found in the saliva of the mosquito. Mosquito transmitted disease is more common in older children where as HIV is not common among older children. When an insect bites a person, it does not inject its own or a previously bitten person's or animal's blood into the next person bitten. Rather, it injects saliva, which acts as a lubricant so the insect can feed efficiently. Diseases such as dengue and malaria are transmitted through this manner. However, HIV lives for only a short time inside an insect and unlike organisms that are transmitted via insect bite HIV does not reproduce and does not survive in insects. Moreover; infected people do not have constantly high.

The chances of getting infection through the toilet seat are very remote. For this to happen there would have to be fresh infected blood on the toilet seat in contact with breaks in the skin or genitalia of the next user. Proper and clean use of the toilet can prevent this.

Saliva contains HIV virus in minute amounts. Saliva also contains an enzyme that inhibits the growth of the virus. A small amount of saliva is highly unlikely to transmit the virus. It has been shown that sharing of a toothbrush or a towel is unlikely to spread the virus. Antiseptics present in the toothpaste kill the virus. Till date only one report of a human bite transmitting the infection has been recorded and it occurred in a child (AFE-01). HIV is not transmitted through casual contact, mosquito bites, working together, sharing toilets, food, clothes, etc. as shown in the figure no 2.3.

Fig 2.3: Misconceptions about HIV/AIDS

2.1.5 Minor and major signs and symptoms of HIV infection:

- Prolonged, unexplained fatigue
- Swollen glands (lymph nodes)
- Fever lasting more than 10 days
- Chills and cough
- Excessive sweating, especially night sweats
- Mouth lesions including yeast lesions and painful, swollen gums
- Sore throat
- Shortness of breath
- Changes in bowel habits including constipation
- Frequent diarrhea
- Symptoms of specific opportunistic infections (such as tuberculosis (TB), cancer, Candida, pneumocystis, and so on) include:
 - Tumor
 - Skin rashes or lesions of various types
 - Unexplained 10% weight loss of the total body
 - General discomfort or uneasiness (malaise)
 - Headache (Health Action 2013).

Vulnerabilities of adolescent girls (related to gender): The male and female ratio of HIV positive people is changing very dramatically and feminization of epidemic is happening as

39% of all HIV positive persons are females. Reasons for this change in the profile of epidemic is due to many reasons while some of them are listed below (Health action 2013).

- a) **Biological Vaginal factors:** The thin lining and the relatively low level of acidity in the vagina render it more susceptible to infection. This thin lining is also more likely to be injured or damaged during the sexual act. Immature local immune system: young girls have had less lifetime exposure to STIs than older individuals and, consequently, fewer mucosal defenses. Protective hormonally driven mechanisms have not yet had time to develop fully.
- b) **Social:** Inability to say no to sex whether in wed lock or out of wedlock due to gender issues, lack of life skills and poor place in negotiations as they are economically dependent on the partner. Safe practices and health behavior helps in prevention of HIV/AIDS and STIs.

Risk Factors for STIs and HIV (relates to action and behaviors)

- Age at sexual debut.
 - Frequency and kind of sexual intercourse an adolescent in engaged in
 - Number and characteristics of sexual partners.
 - Extent of condom use.
 - Risk of violence
 - Prevalence of STIs and HIV locally
- ✓ **Who is At 'Risk' of getting HIV/AIDS Infection-? The key risk groups are:**
- High Risk Group (HRG)
- Female Sex Worker (FSW)
 - Men who have Sex with Men (MSM)
 - Transgender (TG)
 - Injecting Drug Users (IDU)
- Bridge Populations
- Truckers
 - Migrants
- ✓ **People of any age, sex, class can be infected by HIV/ADIS. However, certain practices carry high risk:**
- ❖ Those who have sex with multiple partners especially when condoms are not used.
 - ❖ Injecting drug users who share contaminated needles. It is not who the individual is but rather what an individual does that puts him/her at risk.
 - ❖ Adolescents and youth are at a greater risk of getting infected because of their high risk behavior.
 - ❖ People who receive HIV contaminated blood and blood products are also at risk.

Children vulnerable to HIV infection may fall under one or more of the following categories: Street Children, Working Children, Children of sex worker, Trafficked Children, Runaway Children, Abandoned Children, Sexually abused Children, Sexually Active Children, Children using Substances and Orphans. Be they men who have sex with men (MSN), injecting drug user (IDUs), sex worker or migrants. Sexual minorities includes people who are lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT)and covers men, women and

all those who don't identify either as men or women (that is transgender). Among the transgender are hijras, Hijras are essentially biologically born males who don't not identified as men and prefer to identify as women (Ramamurti, 2008).

2.1.6 Major Health Complications during HIV/AIDS:

HIV infection weakens your immune system, making highly susceptible to all types of infections and certain types of cancers. Major common infections are:

- **Tuberculosis (TB):** In resource-poor nations, TB is the most common opportunistic infection associated with HIV and a leading cause of death among people living with AIDS. Millions of people are currently infected with both HIV and tuberculosis, and many experts consider the two diseases twin epidemics.
- **Salmonellosis:** HIV/AIDS infected persons easily infected with bacterial infection from contaminated food or water. Symptoms include severe diarrhea, fever, chills, abdominal pain and, occasionally, vomiting. Although anyone exposed to salmonella bacteria can become sick, salmonellosis is far more common in HIV- positive people.
- **Cytomegalovirus (CMV):** This common herpes virus is transmitted in body fluids such as saliva, blood, urine, semen and breast milk. A healthy immune system inactivates the virus, and it remains dormant in the body. But if the immune system weakens, the virus resurfaces—causing damage to the eyes, digestive tract, lungs or other organs.
- **Candidiasis:** Candidiasis are a common HIV-related infection. It causes inflammation and a thick white coating on the mucous membranes of the mouth, tongue, esophagus or vagina. Children may have especially severe symptoms in the mouth or esophagus, which can make eating painful and difficult.
- **Cryptococcal meningitis:** Meningitis is an inflammation of the membranes and fluid surrounding the brain and spinal cord (meninges). Cryptococcal meningitis is a common central nervous system infection associated with HIV, caused by a fungus that is present in soil. It may also be associated with bird or bat droppings.
- **Toxoplasmosis:** This potentially deadly infection is caused by *Toxoplasma gondii*, a parasite spread primarily by cats. Infected cats pass the parasites in their stools, and the parasites may then spread to other animals.
- **Cryptosporidiosis:** This infection is caused by an intestinal parasite that's commonly found in animals. One can easily infect when ingested with contaminated food or water. The parasite grows in intestines and bile ducts, leading to severe, chronic diarrhea in people with HIV/AIDS (WHO 2007).

2.1.7 Prevention and Control of HIV Infections:-

The most important counter measure is to prevent women of child bearing age from becoming infected with the virus. Young men sex encounters must be avoided or intercourse must take place with a preventive measure and if she is pregnant a therapeutic abortion should be adopted. This makes prevention of HIV infection to new born baby the utmost important in all societies today. HIV Prevention means to stop something before it happens. HIV prevention means helping people avoid

getting or spreading HIV because there is no cure for HIV. Preventing is the only way we have to stop the spread of the virus. A vaccine is a good form of prevention for some disease, but there is no vaccine against. The best way to stop the virus is to teach people how to avoid HIV and how not to spread the virus if they are already infected. Thus knowledge is the only vaccine against HIV. Though there is no cure and vaccine against HIV, we have a distinct advantage, if we equipped ourselves with correct and complete information as HIV is easily preventable. There are only four routes of transmission of HIV and if we take proper precaution against these four routes of transmission, HIV can easily be prevented and controlled, present situation called on called on the youths who are the backbones of a nation to work towards HIV prevention and control.

Preventing Measures against AIDS- major preventive measures against AIDS can be as follows:

- Avoiding multiple sex partners
- Using fresh syringe and needle or dispensing syringe and needle in injections
- Demand in the saloon for the use of the fresh blade
- Ask for aids test before transfusion of blood
- Never recycle the blood stained bandage cloth needle or syringe.
- Breast milk is the best food and allows your child to be breast fed.
- Some physician's suggest that even a mother with aids disease need to feed her baby with breast milk.
- Milk banks established in hospitals need to test for aids and provide milk to the children.
- The blood banks need to regularly check for aids when the blood is donated and again test before giving blood transfusion. The government needs to strictly regulate this protocol and frame appropriate laws. Countries such as Kenya and Zambia are already ahead of us in strict monitoring of blood testing for aids in blood banks.
- Aids patients need to be strictly monitored for preventing further infection they need to be looked at sympathetically and their needs must be met urgently.
- Narcotics and drug addicts need to be monitored for a longer period in order to check for aids.
- Regular sexual partners need to be monitored for a longer period by the government and they need to be provided condoms free of cost
- Mexico has introduced a special chapter on aids in the biology text books used in their schools and have a round-the-clock counseling hot-line service. in India there is also a need to introduce a special chapter on aids in biology text books in schools and provide for a round-the-clock counseling hot-line service
- Video-films on aids and modes of preventive measures need to be shown to all students
- Film theatres must show documentary on aids before screening any movie
- The internet sites on aids and preventive measures need to be made more popular for the cyber net users
- Radio bulletins must be broadcasted periodically on aids and its prevention

- The literature on aids and its prevention must be made available to everyone at low cost in all Indian languages. Government must be subset the production of aids educational material and publications.
- The local folklore, skits, plays, dramas on aids prevention messages will educate the illiterate public.
- Government must produce condoms in great number and popularize its use.
- Billboard can be prepared in local languages about aids and its prevention and be displayed in public places prominently for education the public.
- P.H.Cs. in rural and paramedics aspects need to be educated to identify aids case if any and refer them to hospital for treatment and promote preventive measures.
- The research concerning immunological aspects need to be strengthened in order to understand the nature of virus and find suitable medicine within the country or abroad.
- Elisa and western Blot Test are costly. The Government of India through their national aids surveillance program me in 43 centers need to develop and strengthen testing facility at reasonably low cost.
- Illiteracy, poverty and malnutrition are prevalent in much state. These factors increase the chances for the development of the aids. The efforts need to be made to increase the general standard of living (Rajamanikam 2006).

While Anti-Retroviral Therapy and other prevention methodologies have been helped reduce the number of new cases, the adverse impact of HIV is acutely realized in the number of young and able-bodied people affected in the most productive part of their lives. In the absence of a cure, HIV poses a pressing health problem, significantly impacting the development of a nation. Scientists are using the four pillars of science, technology, innovation and knowledge to advance evidence that would help create new bio-medical tools of prevention, including vaccines. To continue this growth, the Government of India has adopted favorable policies, through the Ministry of Science and Technology and its dedicated departments of biotechnology as well as science and technology. These initiatives are facilitating India's emergence as a hub for design and development of novel, affordable and effective bio-pharmaceutical products and solutions including vaccines for infectious diseases like HIV.

The Government has only strengthened its commitment to investment in such scientific endeavors through progressive mechanisms that support creation of centers of excellence for research and facilitate emerging and frontline science and technology arenas, by establishing new knowledge-sharing platforms that encourage local and global public-private research and development partnerships. Such global efforts have connected key regional stakeholders working on new bio-medical tools of prevention for HIV, including vaccines, to the global scientific fraternity, resulting in inventive collaborations, both South-South and North-South; further enhancing knowledge gain, building capacities which updating scientific endeavours for diseases like HIV/AIDS. Moreover, research for an HIV/AIDS vaccine informs science to develop tools and products that would address correlates like TB, Malaria and other diseases of relevance to India. With innovative collaborations, come evident economic boost. India's current has a one-third share in the global vaccine market and its share is steadily increasing. India's bio-pharmaceutical sector, valued at \$26 billion, is one of the fastest developing

knowledge-based areas with a growth of 20 per cent in the last few years. India is roaring to progress. It stands in a good place, with 0.88 per cent of the current gross domestic product being spent off on R&P activities and there are plans to increase it to two per cent. This will let India make its mark as the world's leading provider of affordable high-quality biopharmaceutical products.

The field today is enthused with new energies and ready for new partnerships that will promote R&D on prevention interventions for HIV that are safe, effective and accessible to those who need it the most. A laser focus with sustained participation and investment from industry, visionary philanthropists and corporate that share a dream to develop new age technology to support Indians rise on the world stage, fostering new age knowledge-based leaders, owner the best antidote to the needless suffering, misery, and the financial, social and emotional costs of diseases like HIV/AIDS (Fernandes 2014).

- **Contraception:** As it suggests, contraception means 'control of conception'. In other words it is the prevention of conception and pregnancy. As we know how conception takes place earlier. If any of the stages of conception can be prevented, pregnancy cannot occur. Different contraceptive methods act at different points in this process. Some methods prevent ovulation from occurring; other destroys the sperm in the female genital tract. Some methods prevent the contact between the sperm and the ovum by acting as barriers, while other may prevent implantation of the fertilized ovum from occurring. Contraception may be temporary, permanent or emergency depending on the requirement of the couple. Let us discuss each in detail. Before proceeding further, it is important to know that ALL contraceptive methods have failure rates- even if they are very small. The only 100% sure method of contraception is abstinence. There is NO failure rate with this method.

- **Oral contraceptive pills (OCP):** You have already read about the menstrual cycle earlier the cycle is hormone dependent. If this cycle is interfered with, conception will not take place. The combined contraceptive pill contains artificial hormones. When taken correctly, it interferes with the normal cycle to prevent pregnancy by preventing the ovaries from releasing an egg, making the mucus at the cervix (neck between the vagina and womb) thicker so that it is more difficult for sperm to enter and making the lining of the womb unsuitable for implantation of a fertilized egg. It is a very effective method of contraception with a low failure rate and is appropriate for adolescents. However, since a pill has to be taken every day, it just may be forgotten and then the risk of pregnancy becomes high. Some girls may have certain side effects and there are certain medical conditions where the pills should not be taken. The first pill is taken on day 1 of the menstrual cycle and then it just continues throughout the month. The pack is usually a compliance pack i.e., the days of the week is written with the pills so that if a pill is missed out on some day, the person would know immediately. If one pill does get missed it should be taken immediately as soon as the person realizes and two pills may be taken together. But if this happens again, the pills will not be safe and effective for contraception in that month. However, they do not protect against HIV, STIs. They

are sometimes taken even to regulate the menstrual cycle, and to reduce excessive bleeding (FGNOCC 2011).

Fig. 2.4: A Pill Before and After Sex to Prevent HIV

For the first time, a study shows that a drug used to treat HIV infection also can help prevent it when taken before and after risky sex by gay men. The results after hope of a more appealing way to help prevent the disease beyond taking daily pills and using condoms, although those methods are still considered best, reported an international broadcaster. The study, done in France and Canada, is the first to test “on demand” use of truvada, a pill combining two AIDS drugs, by people planning to have risky sex. The uninfected men who took it were 86 per cent less likely to get HIV compared to men given dummy pills. Dr Susan Buchbinder, an AIDS specialist at the San Francisco Department of Public Health, called the results exciting but warned that it can’t be assumed they would apply to make-female sex, because different types of sex expose partners to differing amounts of virus (The New Indian Express 2015).

- **Control of the Disease**

In 1996, when officially it was stated that there are more than 1,000 AIDS cases and about 22,000 HIV carriers, and unofficially it was estimated that there were lakhs of HIV carriers in the country and when there is a projection that by the end of this century, the largest population of HIV carrier in the world (about one-fourth of the HIV population) will be in India. Its spread therefore can only be controlled through preventive education for behavioral change.

Some measures have been suggested for protection and preventing the AIDS and HIV infection. These are:

- ❖ Since sex with infected person is the highest risk factor in AIDS. The greatest need is to educate people to have “safe sex” by using condoms and avoiding multiple sexual partners. This could be done through TV, radio, newspapers, and others mass media. The required awareness can be produced through course content in the educational

institutions too. AIDS advisory centers may also be established for imparting the required knowledge to the people. Seminars, symposia and workshops too can be organized from time to time for imparting the required knowledge.

- ❖ Some training is necessary for doctors and nurses so that they can impart some knowledge to the patients regarding the symptoms of HIV infection on AIDS.
- ❖ Persons suffering from sexually transmitted disease (STDs) are also a significant risk factor in HIV transmission. Though data is limited, there appears to be a high incidence of STDs among tribal poor, rural poor and urban-slum dwellers in India, and these conditions do provide a fertile ground for the spread of the virus. Reported rates of HIV infection among STD cases have triplicate from 1986-1996. Unlike AIDS, STDs can be treated. Hence programme for the prevention and control for STDs should prevention and control of STDs should be given high priority.
- ❖ Blood or blood products must be tested for HIV before transfusion.
- ❖ The HIV tests should be made free and confidential for persons who indulge in the high risk activities or not and for persons who receive a transfusion of blood not properly screened for HIV infection.
- ❖ Doctor should ensure that injecting equipment is sterilized. As far as possible the use disposable syringes should be encouraged.
- ❖ Condoms should be freely distributed or supplied at cheap rates in red-light areas to prostitutes.
- ❖ Drug-users should be persuaded to stay away from intravenous drug use.
- ❖ And lastly, voluntary organizations should help spread knowledge on AIDs to different vulnerable groups through innovative and community-based approaches counseling families, individuals in neighborhood. And member of social support networks is also an important need because eventually they have to be a majority responsibility for the sick and the survivors (Rajmanikam-2006).

2.1.8 Treatment of the Disease:

Seven year after its first diagnosis in the United States, there is still no cure for AIDS. But treatment is improving and consists mainly of fighting the symptoms of the “opportunistic” infections which take advantage of the victims damaged immune system: pneumonia, fungal infection, tuberculosis, cancer and diarrhea. But when the treatment stops the same or a different infection eventually returns. A substance which eliminated the virus without poisoning the patient would be the ideal drug for treating AIDS. But even this would not be a cure if the virus had already destroyed a part of the person’s immune system Instead of focusing on antiviral agents much research is now being directed towards drugs, which prevent the virus from reproducing and colonizing more immune system cells. AIDS patients would have to take these drugs for life: unfortunately many of the drugs tested so far have toxic side effects, even in the short term. At present the leader in the field of AIDS drugs is AZT (zidovudine) it crosses the blood – brain barrier, can be taken orally and has been approved for use against AIDS in most industrialized countries.

ART is a combination of drugs that reduces the amount of HIV in the body (Viral load) by interfering with its replication. ATR does not completely destroy the

virus or cure the disease. With reduce virus in the body, the immune system can become stronger and fight infection more effectively, resulting in decreased morbidity for the patient. ART has been shown to benefit to both adults and children living with HIV/AIDS with effective treatments now available, HIV infection does not leads to AIDS. It is important to reflect reportage. Since HIV is not synonymous with AIDS, 'HIV/AIDS' as a term is no longer considered accurate. With AIDS not being a singular disease but a syndrome define by a verity of disease and cancer, a person does not die of AIDS. It would instate be accurate to report that he or she died of an HIV related illness. Researchers have been working hard for decades yet there is no known cure for HIV or AIDS although the infection is treatable with a positive impact on the quality of life (Ramamurti, 2008).

• **Cure/vaccine for AIDS:**

So far there is no cure for AIDS and a vaccine may be far away (NACO 2007). Presently, the disease is not curable. One way it is spreading with a high ratio and in other it is not curable. Such situation there needs awareness about the disease in every section of the society. There is a need of health education in India. People must think, getting Health Education is their fundamental rights. The government must procure the health education for all. Empirically, it is found that women are forced to unsafe sex. Even in the brothels prostitutes are forced for it. The other part of the reality of women life is also precarious. Forced sex with distance relatives, sexual relation through blackmailing, continuous gang rape etc. spread the disease. So, there is a need of controlling the life killing disease like AIDS. The health education may help the people to change their behavior, attitude, and practices, media, social scientists, social workers, teacher students and other professional have prime role for its eradication.

• **Triple dose of HIV+ expecting Mothers:** A triple-medicine dosage is being administered to 2,866 pregnant women suffering from HIV/AIDS in the state. The pilot project is being carried out in Andhra Pradesh to check the transmission from parent to child. Earlier, the single dosage give to HIV- infected dosage given to HIV-Infected women had shown a transmission rate of 25 per cent. But with the new medicine, the medical officers and doctors at AP State AIDS Control Society are optimist as the test results in a few children have shown 2 per cent transmission. But they have to wait till the child is 18 months old to confirm the results. So far, those children who have crossed a year have been tested every three months, and the results have encouraging. (The New Indian Express, 2015)

2.2 ADOLESCENTS: THE IMMEDIATE FUTURE OF THE COUNTRY:

“Adolescence is a period of change and, consequently, one of stress, characterized by uncertainties in regard to identity and position in the peer group, in society at large and in the context of one’s own responsibilities as an adult. The compulsions of parental approval often encounter the emerging aspirations of independence. Adolescents exhibit mood-swings and might even indulge in self-destructive activities, such as use of alcohol, drugs and violence (GOI, 2003). According to the World Health Organization’s (WHO) definition, youth is the period between the ages of 10 and 24 years. Adolescence is the period between the ages of 10 and 19 years, which is generally when puberty occurs. It is estimated that the adolescent

group constitutes about one fifth of India's population. There are almost 200 million adolescents in India and it is estimated that this age group will grow to over 214 million by 2020 (Gupta, 2003). However, estimating numbers is rendered more complicated by the fact that there is no clear consensus on the exact age group that comprises adolescence. Therefore, programmes and organizations use differing categories depending on their specific target groups (mine2005).

Adolescence, the second decade of life, is a powerful formative period of transition from childhood to adulthood. It is the period during which rapid physical growth, physiological, and psychosocial changes occur. Changes occurring in adolescence are often divided into five general domains physical (onset of puberty, etc.) cognitive (development of formal operational thought processes) moral (exploration of internal and external values and rules) identify (transitions form identity confusion to identity integration) and sexual (experimentation of sexuality, developing intimacy and relationship). It is the period when the development of secondary sexual characteristics and reproductive of secondary sexual characteristics and maturation occur. During adolescence, an intensive sexual drive development and adolescents typically starts exploring relationship with the opposite of the family. Their behavior is guided by an intense desire for independence and identity. In the process adolescent undergo intense psychological stress and personality change (Rao 1995). The difficulty of course is that these beliefs may mask the difficulty, of significant health issues.

Adolescence is a highly transitory period of life. The number and type of changes that adolescents experience in family structure, livelihoods, schooling, community bases, and identities are unparalleled in any other period. To cope with the multiple and rapid changes that occur in their lives, adolescents have specific needs for new types of decision making powers. Adolescents need "safe places" to meet with peers and mentors, as well as resources to find alternatives to pressures to leave school, engage in illegal or unsafe work, abuse substances, marry early, have unsafe sex, and exchange sex for gifts or money (Bruce, 2006). The type of sexual behavior combined with the low awareness and knowledge about its implications may have serious consequences. Few studies on youth sexual behavior in India reveal that they are engaged in sexual relations. These studies mainly focus on sexual behavior and very significantly in their objectives approaches and methodologies. However, they arrive at a common conclusion that sexual activity among youth is on increase especially in urban areas (Health action Sept.2012).

2.2.1 Significant Changes during Adolescent Period:

However, there are other very significant changes also taking place along with the physical changes. These are the cognitive, social and emotional changes. The adolescent is gradually turning into an adult in all respects, and not just in physical growth. Adolescence marks the beginning of the development of more complex thought processes. These are also called formal logical operations and include abstract thinking, the ability to reason and form their own new ideas or questions, the ability to consider many points of view and the ability to think about the process of thinking. Although there are marked individual differences in cognitive development among adolescents these new capacities allow adolescents to engage in the kind of introspection and mature decision making that was previously beyond their

cognitive capacity. Cognitive competence includes such things as the ability to reason effectively, problem solve, think abstractly and reflect, and plan for the future. Even though no significant differences have been identified in the cognitive development of adolescent boys and girls, it appears that they do differ in their confidence in certain cognitive abilities and skills. Girls tend to feel more confident about their reading and social skills than boys, and adolescent boys tend to feel more confident about their athletic and math skills. When studied as a group, these abilities have been seen to be roughly the same in both boys and girls. However, there will still be individual differences even in a group. These differences are usually more due to their conforming to gender stereotypes, rather than differences in ability. Adults can help to dispel these myths, which can otherwise lead adolescents to limit their choices or opportunities. For example, an adolescent girl may be encouraged to take advanced math or technology courses, and an adolescent boy to consider relationship-based volunteer opportunities such as mentoring options that they might not otherwise consider.

❖ **Mid-Adolescents set their future:** When they reach the ages of 15-17 years this period known as mid-adolescence, Adolescents distance themselves a little more from their parents, and their emotions and intellectual capacities increase. This plays an important role in finding one's relations to oneself, groups, and the opposite sex. During this time, the adolescent battles over his/her own set of values versus the set established by parents and other adult figures. The adolescent also begins to take on more control of his/her education and begins to think more seriously about future goals. It is during this time that the adolescent's independence becomes apparent. She/he starts making a place in society.

Cognitively teenagers move from concrete thinking to formal operations and develop the ability to think abstractly. With this comes a sense of omnipotence and a belief that they can change the world. With the onset of the ability to think abstractly, teenagers begin to see themselves as they think that others see them and may become extremely self conscious. They think that everyone is looking at them only and can get easily embarrassed. Middle adolescence is characterized by growth in emotional autonomy and increasing detachment from family. The bulk of physical growth and development is completed during this stage; however, body image concerns may continue to be a source of worry, especially among boys who are late to mature and girls who have experienced great changes in body composition and size. Conflicts over personal choice become increasingly common. Peer groups become more important than family. Coinciding with the increased importance of peer acceptance, the initiation of health compromising behaviors such as smoking, alcohol consumption, using drugs, and engaging in sexual activities often occurs during middle adolescence. Teens may consider them invincible and often still display impulsive behaviors.

Youth is transitional phase from childhood to adulthood when young people, through a process of intense physiological, psychological, social and economic change, gradually come to be recognized and to recognize themselves-as adults. "Youth is an important stage of life building the human capital that allows," young people to escape poverty and lead better and more fulfilling lives. Young people are growing up in a more global world. Greater mobility and rapid urbanization flow people across the borders are closely associated with

new health risks worldwide. As a result, sexual initiation and sexual experimentation in youth carries far a greater risks than before with very high HIV-prevalence rates.

In many ways the risks facing young people today are greater and consequences potentially more deadly, than for previous generations. This is most obvious in the spread of HIV/AIDS, increasingly prevalent among young people. A central element to HIV prevention is AIDS Education to change youth behavior and encourage adoption of healthy life style (World Bank, 2005).

Risk behavior during youth can deplete productive human capital many years into the future. In some developing countries today, close to half of all young men are smokers. Similarly, HIV develops into AIDS with a lag of up to 10 years, taking its toll on people in their prime working ages. In many developing countries, new HIV infections affect young people disproportionately. The costs of treating AIDS are high and the treatments often ineffective. The best way to avoid the future loss of youth is to modify their health behavior. First, give them the knowledge to help them make informed choices about their behavior and skills to negotiate safe behavior with peers and partners. Second, create an environment for the youth to practice healthful behavior.

Individuals may not have good information about the risks they face today, even if he/she understands the risks over time. More than half of the young in many countries are sexually active, and data from surveys conducted between the late 1990s and 2004 show that the proportion who initiated sexual activity before the age of 15 is increasing. A significant proportion of youth in developing countries especially girls are sexually active. Imperfect knowledge about consequences can lead people to engage in unprotected sex. Even in countries where HIV prevalence is high, a large proportion of young people engage in unprotected sex. These people are at greater risk of HIV infection. Education, often called a "social vaccine" is considered by many to protect young people from engaging in risky behaviors.

More than 100 million STIs other than HIV occur every year around the world among people under 25. Many infections, however, go unnoticed, especially among women and girls, who may show no symptoms or signs so mild that they are unrecognizable. Providing STI education and training providers to treat STIs in adolescents increased the uptake of STI services among sexually experienced students a significantly reduced the incidence of STIs. (Worlds Developmental Report 2007).

Programmes addressing youth are of particular importance in preventing HIV/AIDS. In 2003 the Ministry of Health in Brazil launched an AIDS education program in schools of five municipalities. In 2004 the programme was extended to 205 municipalities responsible for almost half of all HIV/AIDS cases in Brazil. The programme was expected to reach all public schools and this particular initiative has been Brazil's successful strategy of curbing the fast spread of HIV/AIDS.

Fitzgerald and Stanton (1999) reported that a curriculum based programme, 'My future is my Choice' in Nambia for African and American youth. It included basic

information about reproductive health. HIV/AIDS, substance abuse and violence as well as communication and decision making skills over 14 sessions. The intervention was randomly assigned to young people in grades 9 to 11 (15 to 18 years old) in 10 secondary schools. Participants displayed improved knowledge of HIV/AIDS, reproduction and the use of condoms relative to the control group. Interventions to change behavior such as Abstain, Be faithful, Use Condoms (ABC) have been the mainstays of HIV prevention since the 1990s. Providing accurate and specific information is more effective than providing vague or general information. School based HIV/STI programs were more likely to have an impact on behavior than general reproductive health programmes. A school based sex/HIV education programme in Kenya that provided young girls with information about higher prevalence of HIV among older men reduced intergenerational sex and significantly reduced pregnancies among girls.

Inculcating life skills in schools is the surest way to enhance the capabilities of young people. This goes beyond skills needed for further schooling and work. School based reproductive health education programmes can increase knowledge and the adaptation of safe sexual behavior. A school based sex education intervention in Kenya providing young girls with specific information such as the prevalence of HIV infection reduced risk behavior among them.

2.2.2 Experience and Experiment in different ideas:

The adolescent starts experimenting with different ideas. Risk taking becomes an important feature at this stage. Abstract reasoning skills begin to emerge among most teens during middle adolescence; however, these skills may not be highly developed. Adolescents will often regress to concrete thinking skills when faced with overwhelming emotions or stressful situations. Teens start to comprehend the relationship between existing behaviors and the future. With some experience in using more complex thinking processes, the focus of middle adolescence often expands to include more philosophical and futuristic concerns, including the following:

- ❖ Questioning and analyzing more extensively (i.e., an expansion of verbal abilities).
- ❖ Thinking about and beginning to form their own code of ethics (i.e., what do I think is right?).
- ❖ Thinking about different possibilities and beginning to develop their own identity (i.e., who am I?).
- ❖ Thinking about and beginning to systematically consider possible future goals (i.e., what do I want?) and to make their own plans i.e., thinking long term.
- ❖ The use of systematic thinking begins to influence the adolescent's relationships with others.

2.3 KNOWLEDGE OF ADOLESCENTS REGARDING HIV/AIDS:

The studies indicate that the circumstances of adolescents in developing countries with respect to sexual behavior and knowledge vary tremendously both across and within the regions (Blanc and Way, 2001). The creation of a global economy and the growth of town led to new jobs, many of which require education beyond the primary level and presented adolescents and young adults with the leverage to loosen parental control. Globally, a teenage

culture is developing. Films, sound and video cassettes, television and radio have spread the same fashion in music and clothes, and thereby also the appearance of a revolt against parents. Much of this change occurs during adulthood as an adjustment to demands made by the evolving global economy and society. The formation of a global teenage culture of music and fashion has been of major importance is the export of the Western concept of companionate heterosexual relations before and after marriage.

In view of increasing prevalence of STDs and HIV/AIDS among youth, it is imperative that knowledge of the safe sex practices be imparted to them. One of the safer sex practices is the use of condoms. Hence, use of condoms has been considered as a useful means to prevent HIV/AIDS as well as RTIs and STIs. However, studies to assess the knowledge and attitude of youth indicated that only a small number uses condom. However, the level of knowledge is found to be significantly higher in urban areas as compared to rural areas (Gupta 2000). It has been established that adolescents are less likely than people over age 20 to use contraceptive methods. Reasons for this include lack of information misinformation, poor access, hitch, lack of ability to negotiate, etc.

2.3.1 Sources of Information about HIV/AIDS:

A study conducted in two randomly selected co-educational schools of Jamnagar, Gujarat. The two schools were selected by random sampling technique. 12th class students from both biology and non-biology sections were taken as sample subjects for the study. A total of 358 students in the age bracket of 16-18 years were included in the study of which 155 were from biology and 203 were from non-biology stream. A pre-tested close-ended schedule was administered to each of the samples in their respective classrooms. The entire schedule was explained to the sample students and all the queries raised by them were clarified. Care was taken to minimize consultation amongst the school children. Adolescents form a sizeable proportion of the population. The study reveals that Pornography is explicit sexual writing or visual materials, often considered obscene. Most societies have always regarded any distribution of pornography as potentially dangerous and corrupting, particularly to younger people. It is believed that more than inciting them to indulge in criminal and deviant behavior, pornographic material causes insecurity in people's minds by producing distorted standards. People may believe that whatever is shown in pornography is the real thing and try to imitate them in real life. This makes them lose their self-confidence and affects their otherwise normal sexual response (Bhalla, et.al, 2005).

A study conducted among adolescents in the Tamil Nadu reveal that to get information on sex and related issues, many times adolescents refer to sex magazines, pornographic photo albums, adult movies and such other means. This study revealed that the exposure to the pornographic literature and blue films was significantly higher among boys as compared to girls. Nearly two percent of girls had seen blew films and 13 percent had seen or read pornographic literature. The corresponding figures for boys were 45 percent and 43 percent respectively (Kumar P Saleel, 2010).

A further analysis revealed that the exposure to pornographic movies and literature was higher among school going girls as compared to out of school girls. However, the

situation was reverse in the case of boys. The out of school boys were more exposed to such movies and literature as compared to those going to schools. Nearly 57 percent of girls and 71 percent of boys expressed curiosity to know about sexual health issues. It can be observed that a majority of the adolescents discuss about sexual health issues with the friends of same sex. It indicates towards the potential effectiveness of peer education strategies for informing adolescents on sexual and reproductive health issues. A small proportion of boys and girls also satisfy their curiosity reading literature or viewing movies on sexuality. The study reveals that more than half of the girls and nearly 10 percent of boys do not find any means to satisfy their curiosity to know about sexual health issues. Most of the adolescents feel that they are unable to obtain sufficient information. The study shows that only 10 percent of girls and 42 percent of boys believe that they are getting correct and sufficient information on reproductive health issues. Only a small fraction of girls and boys reported getting correct and sufficient information on issues related to sexuality. It was also found that nearly 90 percent of girls and 83 percent of boys feel that more information is required on such issues (Kumar P Saleel, 2010).

One of the first steps towards ensuring adequate reproductive and sexual health care for adolescents is to provide them with information about their bodies, puberty, relationships, sex and sexuality. There is no State mandated sex education in schools in India, and not all adolescents are fortunate enough to get text books or magazines from which they might gain some information about their changing bodies and relationships. A great deal of adolescents' knowledge however comes from informal communications with their peers and select family members. Some studies on girls in India have found that they are generally told nothing of menstruation until their first personal experience of it (George, 1997). In a study of 800 girls from Tamil Nadu a little less than a two third of the girls had any information about menstruation before it occurred, and not all had access to accurate sources of information (Narayan, et.al. 2001).

2.3.2: Shortcomings in the body of Knowledge:-

Adolescents are more vulnerable than adults of unplanned pregnancies, sexually transmitted diseases and HIV/AIDS. Among the adolescents, girls are more vulnerable to STDs including HIV/AIDS. Their knowledge about different diseases is very poor. One of the factors that influence HIV risk behavior among early adolescents is their HIV/AIDS knowledge. In spite of the preventive efforts to reduce the incidence of HIV infection in the last decade, 10 million young people age 13–24 years are infected with HIV worldwide (Monasch, et.al. 2006). Teenagers are susceptible to many health problems, such as drug use and sexually transmitted diseases (Papalia et.al, 1997). Adolescents are a high-risk group because; 1) they are in an age of sexual identity exploration, and they experiment with illicit drugs; 2) they are impulsive, and they are influenced by their peer group; and 3) they don't feel vulnerable because they cannot foresee long-term consequences (Marcia, 1989). Adolescents' attitudes towards risk behaviors are often the denial of any chance of infection and the adoption of the belief that they are invulnerable (Mason, et.al, 1988). Fear of contracting AIDS decreases substantially as knowledge of the disease increases. Alcohol and drug use could be considered risky behavior since they reduce inhibitions (Grunbaum, et.al, 2002). Alcohol and drug use are the most important predictors of sexually transmitted

disease and HIV infection among high school students, they also have a strong effect on the age of sexual debut.

- **Generation Gap:** There is a natural gap between the thinking and perception of younger people and older people. This gap is noticed in almost every society and family. This is called the generation gap. The old people in society have fixed views about all matters and this makes them rigid. They usually stand for the voice of reason, tradition and connection. They often refuse to change with the young and continue to hold on to their obsolete ideas and they become obstinate. They usually find the “new wave” shocking and revolting. They feel that the young are corrupt and usually too liberal. They find youngsters irresponsible, insensitive and easily corruptible. However, they forget that it is the lack of years of experience that makes the youngsters seem so. While in fact the young only represent change and revolt against the set tradition and way of life.

The young mind on other hand is analyzing all that the old people stand for. They question about the existing norms in society and refuse to follow these blindly. They argue that they cannot be expected to follow the established system simply because their elders laid them down. Due to the various developments in science and technology in the world in general, there is a great need for the young people in each society to keep abreast with the changing trends. However, they usually find a conflict between what the media, the newspapers project and the values that they see their parents and elders upholding. The older generation usually represents a life of simplicity and austerity. They are more patient, tolerant, sympathetic, charitable and pious. They depend heavily on religion for their peace mind. Youngsters find religion a waste of time because their minds are restless and they have less patience too. Their young blood makes them rash, hot-tempered, impulsive and these are the qualities that upset the older generation. The young always want to change the way of the world with their new vision and vigor. The different of opinion between the two gives rise of friction. Both hold on to their ideas and this result in the generation (M kurin 2001).

Heffernan (2004) from National AIDS Control Organization (NACO) survey reports that India had 5.1 million people infected with HIV as of the end of 2003. This represents a 10.3 percent increase in estimated infections. In India 85 percent of people that have HIV/AIDS were infected by a partner of the opposite sex. The survey reveals that the virus has started to spread from high-risk groups to the general population and to move from urban to rural areas. Nine out of 10 HIV positive people in India are between 15 and 44, the most economically productive age group. Indian women are more at risk in getting infected by the HIV virus due to discrimination, lack of education, social standing and poverty. Today 1.9 million women are HIV positive. It was estimated that 22 percent of HIV cases in India were housewives with a single partner. According to NACO (2008) the impact of HIV/AIDS on Children and Youth is that 300,000 children between the ages 0-14 are HIV positive and the majority of the newly infected people in India are under 25 years.

The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation's Avahan programme (2008), has devoted most of its resources to focused interventions in the six states with high HIV prevalence as well as along national highways. It aims to reduce HIV transmission among high-risk groups,

especially sex workers, their clients, and injecting drug users (IDUs), and to slow the spread of the epidemic into the general population. Advocacy, public education, and capacity building supplement these interventions.

CHARCA (2005) is a joint UN programme aimed at young women and girls in India for prevention of and education about HIV and other sexually transmitted infections. According to UN experts, women account for about 40 percent of HIV cases in India, and there has been a recent rise in HIV prevalence among women and girls ages 15 to 24. "India has the right laws, policies and money, but implementation is an issue which needs to be addressed." The new campaign, titled "Commitment to Protect the Young and Vulnerable." aims to use rock concerts, plays and skits in the Indian cities of Aizawl, Udaipur and Bellary. "We look at it as an advocacy tool using the popular format of music to draw the attention of policymakers at both the national and state levels," Alankar Malviya -a project coordinator for CHARCA said, adding; "It is clear that by dedicating the International Women's Day (March 8, 2004) to the issue of reducing women's growing susceptibility to the disease, we recognize the enormity of it"

The New Indian Express (March 3rd 2006) reported that the Coordinated HIV/AIDS Response through Capacity Building and Awareness along with the United Nations Development Fund for Women, UNAIDS and Indian Government Agencies began Awareness Campaign to increase HIV/AIDS awareness among young women and girls in India ages 15 to 29. Hussein, from Hindustan Times, (March 2006) reports about HIV Positive Woman Is Running for Legislature in India's Assam State, An HIV positive woman who advocates for increased HIV/AIDS awareness and heads the Assam Network of Positive People submitted an application thus run for an Assembly seat in the Indian State of Assam.

The general spread of education is it formal, non-formal or informal empowers women and men to improve their lives and reduce the risks they face. Women who are educated are better equipped to demand and obtain their rights, and therefore to remain free from HIV infection. In many of the hardest-hit countries, educated women have been at the forefront of community mobilization against HIV/AIDS. Thus, achieving the goals of Education for All, notably the commitments that focus on gender equality in education, is a vital contribution to HIV prevention. Ultimately, empowerment through education contributes to building secure relationships based on gender equality, mutual respect and consent.

- **Poor assessment of Education on HIV/AIDS:** Globally, 10.3 million youth in the age group of 15-24 years are living with human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (HIV/AIDS). India is one of the largest and most populated countries in the world where adolescents constitute about 22% of the total population. As per estimate of 2009, in India, 2.4 million people were living with HIV (Overview of HIV/AIDS in India Report, 2011). Out of total cases of HIV/AIDS in India, 35% were in the age group of 15-24 years and most of them were infected through unprotected sex. The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) statistics (2003-2008) found that only 20% of the adolescent females are aware about the comprehensive knowledge on HIV/AIDS, while the percentage in male counterpart is about 36%. This

underlines the vulnerability of female adolescent to HIV/AIDS (Naswa et al., 2012). The adolescents living in slum areas are more vulnerable for HIV/AIDS due to poor access to education, migration, poverty, etc. (Erulkar, et al, 2006).

A community based cross sectional study was conducted in the urban slum areas of Solapur Municipal Corporation of Western Maharashtra during June 2010 to August 2010. Total 400 adolescent girls in the age group of 13-19 years were included in the study. Out of 127 slums registered under Municipal corporation area, 10 slums were selected by lottery method. Forty respondents from each slum were selected by simple random sampling method. If the respondents were found less in a particular slum area then the remaining were covered in next big slum area. The data was collected with the help of pre-tested and pre-designed schedule by skilled social workers taking the informed consent from the adolescent girls. Before taking the interview, brief view was done about the questions asked for e.g., what is the meaning of unsafe sex etc. and the information was collected. The study of 400 adolescent girls, 102 (25.5%) were in the age group of 13-14 years, 115 (28.75%) and 183 (45.75%) were in the age group 15-16 years and 17 years and above, respectively. The mean age of the respondents was 15.92 years. Out of the 400 adolescent girls, 63 (15.75%) said that HIV/AIDS transmits through unsafe sex, 94 (23.5%) through contaminated blood transfusion, 19 (4.75%) through mother to child during pregnancy and child birth, 48 (12%) through breast feeding, 24 (6%) by sharing contaminated needles/syringes, and 217 (54.25%) were not aware exactly how HIV/AIDS transmits from one person to another. HIV/AIDS transmits through unsafe sex was told by 6.86% girls in the age group of 13-14 years, while the percentage was 13.04% and 22.40% in the age group of 15-16 years and 17 years and above, respectively. Statements such as HIV/AIDS transmits from mother to child during pregnancy, child birth or after birth through breastfeeding were significantly told by the girls in the age group of 17 years and above (Naswa et al., 2012).

A study by Kotecha and others found that only 19.2% and 33% school going girls were not aware about HIV/AIDS transmission. A total of 15.75% girls in the present study said that HIV/AIDS transmits through unsafe sex (Kotecha P.V. *et al.*, 2011). It underlines the vulnerability of adolescent girls for HIV/AIDS due to poor knowledge of safe sex. A total of 23.5% girls in the study said HIV/AIDS transmits through contaminated blood transfusion. Thus, poor knowledge in adolescents about HIV/AIDS transmission was a serious concern as found in the present study. There is a great need to formulate the information, education, and communication (IEC) strategies focusing on individual level, family level, and community level.

The central and state governments have launched IEC (Information, Education and Communication) programmes through mass media and through other means of increasing awareness about AIDS. Many NGOs have also launched similar programmes. As a result of these and publication of reports in popular newspaper and magazines, the awareness about AIDS has spread as a very threatening disease, but very little is known about the depth of awareness in different segments of adolescents. The education sectors of affected countries play an increasingly important role in the fight against HIV/AIDS. Education has a dramatic impact on the prevention and control of HIV infection and development of nation. The

increasing role of education sectors recognize that a good education is one of the most effective way of helping young people to avoid HIV/AIDS. For these adolescents and youth there is a window of hope, a chance of a life from AIDS if they can acquire the knowledge, skills and values to help them protect themselves as they grow up. Providing young people with the “Social Vaccine” of education offers them a real chance of productive life (World Bank, 2004).

2.4: ATTITUDE OF ADOLESCENCE AND HIV/AIDS:

Attitude and behaviours surrounding sexuality carry profound meaning for men and women in every society and affect the quality of life in fundamental ways. The social construction of sexuality refers to the process by which sexual thoughts, behaviour and conditions are interpreted and ascribed cultural meaning. This element incorporates collective and individual beliefs about the nature of body, and what is considered erotic and offensive and what and with whom it is appropriate or inappropriate for men and women to do or to talk about sexuality. In some cultures, ideologies of sexuality stress female resistance, male aggression and mutual antagonism in the sex act; in other they stress reciprocity and mutual pleasure (Standing and Kisekka 1989). A study conducted by Selvan and others revealed that those adolescents who follow traditional sexual norms tend not to involve in actual sexual behaviour. However, the peer group norms were significant variables for intended sexual and actual sexual behaviour (Selvan, et.al. 2001). To understand the attitude of adolescents towards friendship with opposite sex, the respondents in this study were asked about how far they approve the friendship. It was found that 42 percent of girls and around two-thirds of boys approved friendship of girls and boys with opposite sex.

The approval for sexual relation of girls with boys was 13 percent among girls and 17 percent among boys. Nearly one-fifth of the girls and one-fourth of the boys approved sexual relationship of boys before marriage. A small proportion of girls and boys also approved extramarital relationship of men and women (Selvan, et.al, 2001). The approval for friendship of girls and boys with opposite sex was more among school going girls (50 percent) as compared to out of school girls (45 percent), although approval for sexual relations was comparatively higher among out of school girls than those going to school. Friendship with opposite sex as well as sexual relationship was found higher among out of school boys as compared to those attending schools. It is also interesting to note that the sexual relations of boys got greater approval, both by boys and girls. Such differential is indicative of gender-bias prevalent in the society, even on the issues related to sexuality (Selvan, et.al. 2001).

As pointed out by Mane and Maitra (2002), “relatively little is known about the sexual behavior and attitude towards different aspects and forms of sexual activity in India”. It is true that the AIDS pandemic has aroused interest in sexuality and sexual behavior research, because in India, the mode of transmission is mainly heterosexual. Adolescents, however, are not viewed as a priority target group because it is believed that they are not sexually active. The need for studying this group, however, needs to be recognized because adolescence, just like childhood, could provide the key to understanding several aspects of adult behavior. If adolescence is considered as a period of great turmoil, the need for studying

this group becomes even more significant. The concern for understand the sexual behavior of adolescents has grown in recent years. In part because of real and perceived increase in their sexual activity, and in part because of the high vulnerability of adolescents to HIV infection, mainly due to their increased sexual activities.

2.4.1 Behavioral changes during Adolescents:

In the state of transition from traditional to modern societies, adolescents often find themselves faced with conflicting definitions of their rights and responsibilities, and off their sex roles and gender expectations. The stress engendered by this conflict is often amplified by integrating tensions regarding sex behaviors (Gage, 2001). Adolescents may also differ from adults in terms of their understanding of the risk of engaging in certain behaviors. This difference may partly be due to their knowledge and attitude regarding sexuality and the perceived risk of the sexual practices. Hence while studying the sexual behavior of adolescents, the knowledge, attitude and practices off adolescents become important aspects. Keeping this in view, the variables for this study focused on the knowledge, attitude and practices of the adolescents regarding several reproductive and sexual issues.

Adolescence is a complex but natural process. Both the adolescent and the majority of adults surrounding them are unaware of the process itself and all its manifestations. Adolescents often adopt incorrect attitudes and behavioural patterns that can lead to both social problems and ill health. Adolescents' risky behaviours often result from their inadequate knowledge and experience with such behaviours and their lack of understanding of the risks involved. Moreover, their cognitive limitations make it difficult for them to learn from the experiences of others (Prabhakar, et.al, 2009). Several studies conducted on Indian adolescent have found that many adolescents particularly males are sexually active and are likely to indulge in unsafe sexual activities making them vulnerable to STD's including HIV infection. According to estimate by UNAIDS, by the end of 1999, there were already 33.6 million people worldwide with HIV infection altogether more than four million children under the age of 15 years and more than 10 million young people (15-24 years) have been infected with HIV since the epidemic began. Unfortunately, the needs of adolescents have not been addressed by the health system (Prabhakar, et.al, 2009).

2.4.2: Family Dynamics of Unhealthy Coping:

The optimal development of a young child requires a family environment that ensures gratification of all basic physical needs and promotes health and safety. The development of a young child is fostered by a relatively high frequency of adult contact, positive emotional climate in which the child learns to trust others and self and an optimal level of need gratification.

Quality of Parent - adolescent interactions and parenting styles lead to the expected adolescent development namely, autonomy, identity and morality. Authoritarian parenting styles involve relative neglect of the child's needs, strong demands for child compliance and forceful methods for gaining compliance and punitive methods. Permissive parenting styles are characterized by low demands from parents. Hardly any check is done on child-centered indulgence or child's self-direction, hi indulgent and authoritarian kind of parenting style desirable levels of reciprocity

and communication are disrupted by the dominance of parent in the authoritarian style and of child in the indulgent style. Studies revealed that lack of parental involvement and support is associated with negative self-appraisals by adolescents leading to decline in the adolescents' school performance.

Substance abusers (parents) are more prone to engage in conflict and emotionally abusive mood. While abusing alcohol or drug parent may become abusive but when the same person is in a sober mood he is loving and emotionally expressive. Another dynamics in alcoholic families is that when one partner abuses the other overcompensates and manages the addiction telling the children not to bother the father (who is the abuser). One parent takes over the responsibility of the other and becomes functional for a time, then relapses into depression or anxiety and forces the abuser into short-term sober behavior. Children engage in role reversals, becoming parents to each other and the parent. Family may suffer multiple losses due to substance abuse, accidents and crime. But continue to be in denial and not doing anything to change the cause of behavior of adolescents.

2.4.3 The Domination of Masculine Behavior:

In societies where girls are valued less than boys, parents exert excessive protection over their girls, restricting their mobility in public in order to preserve their value as a commodity of marriage specially their virginity and under-invest in their education. When they lack secondary or even a primary education, girls' choice are limited to early marriage and child bearing, and they experience lower earnings throughout their lifetimes than if they had stayed in school (summers, 1994). Girls living without parents might seek their own form of protection in relationships with older men, heightening their risk of infection.

Girls in one or more of the following life situations are judged to be the most vulnerable to HIV infection such as those out-of-school, especially very young adolescents (ages 10-14), girls living apart from their families, particularly those newly migrated to cities and in domestic service, girls acting as heads of households and pressured to earn income and married adolescents under 18 years old (Bruce, 2007). Married adolescents have higher HIV infection rates than unmarried sexually active adolescents. This difference has been attributed to married adolescents' inability to negotiate condom use (Clark et al., 2006). The most socially isolated girls are six times more likely to have been physically forced to have sex than the most socially connected girls (Bruce and Chong, 2006). This reveals the increased incidences of sexual practices prevailing among the adolescents that have direct bearing upon their life situations and risk of unintended pregnancy, induced abortion, STD, RTI, HIV and AIDS.

An article on 'Reaching Socially Marginalized Youth' discusses the realities and challenges of reaching a group of youth characterized as "socially marginalized". These youths often have weakened or severed family ties and lack connection to institutions such as schools, youth clubs, or a formal workplace. They are vulnerable to sexual exploitation and are at disproportionately high risk of unintended pregnancies and STIs, including HIV/AIDS (Stevens, 1999). An article on 'Many youth face grim STD risks provides an overview of recent research on adolescents and STIs, mostly in developing countries. It describes young

people's misperceptions about STIs, including HIV/AIDS, and present study findings illustrating that even when adolescents have accurate knowledge about STIs, they often continue risky sexual behaviors. Lack of access, inexperience, or embarrassment is significant barriers to young people using condoms. Young people – young women in particular – continue to be more vulnerable to STIs than those who are older. In developing countries, up to 60 percent of new HIV infections are among 15 to 24 year olds, with generally twice as many new infections in young women than young men (Best, 2000).

The physical changes that occur at pubescence are responsible for the appearance of the sex drive. The gratification of sex drives is still complicated by many social taboos, as well as by a lack of accurate knowledge about sexuality. Despite their involvement in sexual activity, some adolescents are not interested in or knowledgeable about, birth-control methods or the symptoms of sexually transmitted diseases. Consequently, the rate of illegitimate births and the incidence of venereal disease are increasing.

Adolescents comprise 20 percent of the global population, 85 percent of whom live in the developing countries. Furthermore the adolescent population in developing countries is expanding, with the number of urban youth growing to a projected 600 percent between 1970 and 2025. Twenty one percent (210 million) of India's population is in the age group of 10-19 years. Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to adulthood spanning age 10 to 19 years. Currently, the world's adolescent population is 1.2 billion. This unprecedented number of adolescents will ensure continued population growth for decades to come, even as family sizes get smaller. An increased world population brings its adolescents increased poverty, decreased access to health-care services, decreased access to education and decreased economic opportunity. Adolescence is a period of deep emotional changes. Adolescence is also the period of experimentation, which express the youth to health risks through drugs, alcohol, tobacco use, irresponsible sexual behavior, etc. (Prabhakar, et.al, 2009).

According to UNICEF (2000) over 50 percent of young people (aged 15-24) in more than a dozen countries have never heard of AIDS or have serious misconceptions about how HIV is transmitted. Providing women and young people with candid information about AIDS and life skills is a prerequisite in any AIDS response.

African American youth are disproportionately represented among adolescent cases of HIV infection. The number of adolescents infected is doubling every 14 months. The primary risk factor for contracting HIV among adolescents is unprotected sexual intercourse. With 60 percent of 12th graders from national sample reporting having had sexual intercourse a fairly substantial proportion of adolescents are at potential risk for contracting HIV. Because school connectedness is linked to later onset of sexual intercourse, most likely the 60 percent estimate among 12th graders represents a considerable underestimation of the actual rate of sexual intercourse among 17-year old youth who have dropped out of school. Although each emerging cohort adolescents have been given awareness of the need to have safe sexual practice, less than 50 percent of adolescents only use condoms consistently (Jemmott & Fong, 1998).

Greater wealth and changing lifestyles have increased the exposure of youth to new technologies and global culture. This is creating tension between traditional and modern values. It has led to new health risks, such as drug abuse, HIV/AIDS, unwanted pregnancies and abortions. Youth make up a growing share of HIV/AIDS infections from 10 percent in 1994 to about 40 percent today. Young women are especially vulnerable to sex-related health risks because of their limited decision-making power and lack of comprehensive sex education (World Development Report, 2007).

Many young people are themselves living with HIV/AIDS or are coping with the deaths of parents, friends and relatives. They have a key role in raising awareness about HIV/AIDS and supporting others. Many members of the AIDS challenge youth club in Uganda have had direct and distressing experience of AIDS, having lost parents or close relatives. Members are aged 13-35 years old, and the group meets regularly to share experience and ideas, and learn about AIDS and support others. During training courses, counseling sessions and club meetings members have build up their confidence and self esteem. They are open and honest in their family situations, and able to support others in affected families. They talk very freely about relationships, friendships, sex and condom use. Young people said that they had difficulties in talking about sex with their parents, and recognized their own responsibility to start communication by discussing neutral subjects such as work or school. Above all young people wanted to live with hope, not anxiety and fear (AIDS Action, 1994).

- Use of physical force to compel a person to engage in a sexual act against his or her will, whether or not the act is completed.
- An attempted or completed sex act involving a person who is unable to understand the nature or condition of the act, to decline participation, or to communicate unwillingness to engage in the sexual act (for example, because of illness, disability or the influence of alcohol or other drugs or due to intimidation or pressure). The sex act or the Sexual act has been defined as contact between the penis and the vulva or the penis and the anus involving penetration, however slight; contact between the mouth and the penis, vulva or the anus.
- Abusive sexual contact that includes intentional touching directly, or through the clothing, of the genitalia, anus, groin, breast, inner thigh, or buttocks of any person against his or her will, or of any person who is unable to understand the nature or the condition of the act, to decline participation, or to communicate unwillingness to be touched (e.g. because of illness, disability, or the influence of alcohol or other drugs, or due to intimidation or pressure).

2.4.4 Psycho-Social Problems of Female living with HIV/AIDS

This includes trauma to the victim caused by acts, threats of acts, or coercive tactics, such as those given in the list below: Humiliating the victim; controlling what the victim can and cannot do; withholding information from the victim; getting annoyed if the victim disagrees; deliberately doing something to make the victim feel diminished (e.g., less smart, less attractive); deliberately doing something that makes the victim feel embarrassed; using the victim's money; taking advantage of the victim; disregarding what the victim wants; isolating the victim from friends and family; prohibiting access to transportation or telephone;

Getting the victim to engage in illegal sexual activity. However, it has been felt that this list is not exhaustive and can be extended to include many other types of behavior that could be considered as emotionally abusive by the victim.

It has been found that severe psychological stress and living under terror and the mental torture of violence can lead to self destructive behavior and fatal consequences such as suicides. Studies in India, Bangladesh, Fiji, the USA, Papua New Guinea and Peru show a high correlation between domestic violence and suicide rates. Women who are victims of domestic violence are 12 times more likely to attempt suicide than those who do not experience such violence.

Nearly two in five (37 percent) married women have experienced some form of physical or sexual violence by their husband. One in four married women experienced physical or sexual Violence by their husband in the 12 months preceding the survey. Studies from WHO indicate that between 16% and 52% of women world-wide are physically assaulted by an intimate partner at least once in their live. Statistics published in 1997 by the World Health Organization (WHO) reveals that, according to 40 studies conducted in 24 countries on four continents, between 20% and 50% of the women interviewed reported that they suffered physical abuse from their male partners. Also, according to *'Where Women Stand - An international report on the status of women in 140 countries, 1997-1998'*, the number of women reporting physical abuse by a male partner during the period 1986-1993 were between 21% to 60%. It has become generally recognized that acute and chronic medical conditions in the Pediatric population have the potential to bring about a range of psychosocial challenges not only to patients, but also to family members and health care workers. Of these conditions, HIV/AIDS presents perhaps the most complex psychosocial issues of any medical condition. The overlapping of social, individual, family, financial, cultural, and illness factors poses a challenge to communities and healthcare teams that strive to provide comprehensive services to this population (JAIDS-2014).

The existence and rapid spread of HIV and AIDS poses a serious challenge to every nation across the globe. HIV and AIDS have the potential to undermine the massive improvements that have been made in global health over the years. Apart from being a serious health problem, the multi layered effects of the epidemic on the socio-economic fabric of whole nations, makes HIV and AIDS a potential development threat worldwide. The seriousness of the situation and the need to take action has been captured aptly, there is an utmost need to address the long-term psycho-social needs of Pediatric HIV/AIDS patients in general, women in particular and has been recognized in recent years as it is a critical and crucial, although there is still a little empirical literature regarding the long-term effects of the disease available. There is a need for explicit research to understand psycho-social problems of specific diseases of HIV /AIDS with chronic illnesses in general along with a social stigma in particular and its impact on their families.

The Human Immunodeficiency Virus has a large psychological, physical and social impact on infected individuals and their families. Stigmatization worsens this impact; it hinders the prevention and treatment of HIV and hampers social support and HIV disclosure.

The families most affected by HIV are characterized by low socioeconomic status, which includes such groups as tribal community, drug users, migrants and asylum seekers. Primary and secondary HIV prevention needs to be promoted, which means educating people about HIV, providing materials for its prevention, providing access to treatment and providing programmes that reduce both the short and long term physical, psychological and social harm it causes in adults and children. Specific prevention efforts should be directed at the group of people below 30 years of age (Hingar, P. L. Sharma and Vismita Paliwal, 2013).

According to Meenu Sharma, Kalpaz, (2012) AIDS is undoubtedly the most devastating pandemic mankind has ever faced. As a cure remains elusive, the disease continues to propel the evanescence of life. Today, the global community seems to be struggling as the disease rips apart the social and economic fabric of the society by killing people in prime of their youth, rendering millions of children orphans and shattering homes and hopes alike. With remote prospects for a cure/vaccine, the challenge to contain the spread of HIV has become imperative. Although no culture or community is known to be immune to AIDS yet, certain populations are more vulnerable to the disease because of their high-risk behaviours. Also, it is true that certain vulnerable populations have remained either untouched or non-responsive to the ongoing prevention efforts. The book delves into the lives of some such communities with a modest attempt to create AIDS awareness amongst them. It focuses on documenting high-risk behaviour as well as in delineating factors fuelling them. A concerted effort has been made to understand various issues that can effect desirable behavioural changes in context to HIV/AIDS. The endeavor also investigates to demonstrate how the community participation can be effectively used in raising HIV/AIDS awareness as well as in achieving sustainability of the programme. What follows henceforth is a significant transition leading from a state of unawareness to awareness.

A work by health and development experts and professionals, this well-researched compilation traces the evolving and highly dynamic nature of HIV/AIDS and its unprecedented health and development threat in Asia. Three decades of HIV/AIDS in Asia studies how the region has responded to this epidemic in the last three decades. It contains country-specific chapters on the HIV/AIDS problem -low-prevalence countries such as Bangladesh and Sri Lanka as well as countries with advanced epidemics such as Cambodia, China, India, Pakistan, Thailand and Vietnam and the evolving response to it. There is recognition of the fact that Asia remains the hardest hit after Africa. The lesson learnt from the Asian countries show that HIV can be prevented and clinically managed with sustained political commitment, adequate human and financial resources, and inter-sectoral action. With the modus operandi of real-life stories and case studies, this work is highly relevant in assessing the ground reality and the measures required for effective prevention, treatment, and care across the continuum (Narain 2012).

The most important way to change risky behaviour is health education. Several studies have shown the positive impact of education and health literacy on cautious sex behaviour. Education itself does not work, only it leads to higher health literacy and general cognitive ability. It creates choices and opportunities for people, reduces the twin burdens of poverty and diseases and gives a stronger voice in society. In a study it was emphasized that there is

currently no publicly available vaccine for HIV or cure for HIV or AIDS. The only known methods of prevention are based on avoiding exposure to the virus or failing that an antiretroviral treatment directly after a highly significant exposure called Post Exposure Prophylaxis PEP (Singh and Kumar 2011)

It was emphasized that it can educate the policy makers, consultants, teachers, researchers, NGOs, managers and administrators for the total welfare of humanity. It can serve to add knowledge among female gynecologists, pediatricians, behavioural scientists, social workers health educators, home scientists managers and other faculty members for prevention of diseases and promotion of health. The HIV/AIDS pandemic is entering a new more dangerous phase. As the global threat increase, there are many sign of growing complacency persistence denial and resurgent discrimination. A creative revitalization of effort against AIDS is needed. It was to bring together current knowledge of HIV/AIDS it explores the complexities of the issue challenges thrown up by the contemporary situation in India. This is the outcome of the conclusion of a study of about 300 social work students from different universities; the basic objective is to evaluate the knowledge and attitude towards HIV/AIDS. Besides, it also offers examples of government action that has been taken to combat this disease. The generalization made on the basis of response of the present study will prove helpful to the researchers, social work students, nursing students, policy makers who are interested in concerned with further studies about the status of HIV/AIDS (Parveen 2010).

It is an outcome of several qualitative and quantitative studies conducted to understand patterns of migration and HIV risk in India. It is an edited version of the research report funded and presented to Department of International Development India for the purpose of assessing and exploring the subject for the purpose of policy formulation. The research was conducted by Development Research Services Pvt. Ltd and authors conducted study supported by a team of experts and research specialists. The book provides an insight on the issue of migration, mobility and HIV risk in India. With its unique blend of qualitative and quantitative research methodology and framework, this book will be of immense value to diverse audience which includes public health professionals, social workers, NGOs, researchers, policy makers and educators involved in prevention and rehabilitation of drug addicts (Gulalia, Rao and Bhatt, etal.2010).

This research endeavor has been undertaken among women living with HIV Positive in Chennai City of Tamil Nadu, with the objectives of investigating the socio-economic background, marital status and circumstances leading to HIV infection, sexual behaviour after infection, impact of HIV/AIDS in social relationships and their attitude towards pregnancy and child birth after infection. Since the prevalence of HIV is an estimated figure based on sentinel surveillance data on the selected cities according to UNAIDS/WHO criteria, the universe is not taken into consideration for this study. Therefore, purposive sampling technique is adopted to contact the respondents by resorting to snowballing procedure. Accordingly, 200 women living with HIV positive in Chennai city were interviewed with the structured interview schedule to collect required information on the line of objectives formulated for the study. Apart from interview with the respondents, discussion

was also held with Government officials and N.G.Os working in AIDS intervention programmes. Available data had been subjected to process statistically leading to analysis and interpretation. Based upon the analysis and findings, a specific action plan has been evolved to provide care and support for the women infected with HIV and to create AIDS free society (Sakthi 2010).

The assessment is the result of a collaborative effort of many organizations, agencies and individuals working to improve the situation of children and women affected by HIV and are vulnerable to HIV infection in Bangladesh. The successful completion of the assessment was possible with support from the staff of the NGOs other organizations/agencies that facilitated the work of researchers. They participated directly or indirectly in the preparation, implementation of the study and finalization of the report. People living with HIV generously shared their experience with the researchers which added pragmatic value to this assessment" (UNICEF 2008).

The AIDS stigma exists around the world in a variety of ways, including ostracism, rejection discrimination and avoidance of HIV infected people, compulsory HIV testing without prior consent or protection of confidentiality, violence against HIV infected individuals or people who are perceived to be infected with HIV and the quarantine of HIV infected individuals. Stigma-related violence or the fear of violence prevents many people from seeking HIV testing, returning for their results, for securing treatment, possibly turning what could be a manageable chronic illness into a death sentence and perpetuating the spread of HIV/AIDS Research and Control Centre (ARCON) , Mumbai, pointed out the major findings include that majority of the patients are migrants of rural areas, from low-income group, less educated, depressed and have lost their hopes for future. It was observed that most patients have the fear of being abandoned from their family if they reveal their HIV status (Ramasubban, Rishyasringa and Rawat,2005).

The economic problems are the major issue, because managing money for the long-term treatment is difficult for those who can hardly afford for their sustenance. In case of the females, majority has been infected husbands are living alone. Women were at a disadvantage with their in-laws and there is definitely the danger of abuse. So it is essential and crucial to focus areas related to assess the psycho-social problems of women living with HIV/AIDS and to understand the impact of psycho-social problems of the victims on their families as inadequate considerations have been noticed that which the essential part of successful was and implementations of the programme. Only a very few studies are convey the social, economical and emotional feelings of the women living with HIV & AIDS to the society. It is essential to understand comprehensively with a set focus in the society and among the family members of the victims about the infected women and their mental condition.

2.5 EXISTING SEXUAL EXPERIENCES AND PRACTICES AMONG ADOLESCENTS:

Sex is usually not a matter of overt discussion in India, but the threat of AIDS as a killer disease has made it legitimate topic of allusion in Indian mass media. Much of the

underlying assumptions behind the allusions are based on myths and stereotypes which may be far removed from real fact (Nag Moni, 1994). A few recent studies indicate, however, that the practice is not uncommon in both educated and uneducated and in both urban and rural populations. In fact, sexual expression is an important element of being an adult and young people do not perceive problems that may come in future, especially when they concern them as sexual beings. Young boys and girls experience sexuality in diverse ways. Few studies on youth sexuality in India that are available have been reviewed by Nag (1996) and Jejeebhoy (1996). They arrived at a common consensus that sexual activity in terms of sexual intercourse among youth is on increase especially in urban areas.

In the study area, 17 percent of girls reported having penetrative sex and 22 percent had experienced touching of private parts. Such types of sexual experiences were more reported among out of school girls than those attending schools. Penetrative sex was experienced by 18 percent of the out of school girls, whereas it was 15 percent among school going girls. Similarly, the proportion of girls reporting experience of touching body parts was also higher among out of school girls. The study also indicates that a slightly higher proportion of boys are involved in sexual activities as compared to girls. Among boys, one-fifth reported having penetrative sex and around 30 percent reported experiencing touching of private parts. The analysis by schooling status indicates a similar trend as observed in the case of girls. The proportion of boys reporting sexual experiences was higher among out of school boys (22 percent) as compared to those going to schools (18 percent).

The mean age at first penetrative sex was found to be 16.8 years among girls and 17.4 years among boys. Nearly 14 percent of girls and 6 percent of boys had first penetrative sex before attaining 15 years of age. A larger proportion of girls had first sex at 16-17 years of age, whereas, a larger proportion of boys had first sex when they were 17-18 years. This indicates that sexual activities among girls were initiated earlier as compared to boys. Nearly 15 percent of the girls reported that they were forcefully involved in sexual activity. The forceful involvement in sex was reported higher among the girls in younger age-group (13-15 years) than the elder ones (16-19 years). It was also higher among those not attending schools.

The findings indicate that of those girls who were involved in sexual activities, a large proportion was involved in such activity incidentally or unintentionally. Secondly, a significant proportion of forceful sex, and that too among the girls in younger ages, should be a cause of concern. These findings suggest that there is a serious lack of skills among girls to negotiate on sexual issues and to say 'no' if they don't wish to get involved in sexual activity.

Another important aspect came out during the study was regarding "light sex". It was informed that some of the adolescents did not consider themselves at risk of pregnancy or STDs because they were engaged in "light sex", which they distinguished from sexual intercourse. Further investigations revealed that "light sex" might be involved in rubbing the penis against the vagina and some penetration, and is therefore, a risk practice.

Studies indicate that motivations for engaging in certain types of sexual behaviour such as offering sex for money or having intercourse as a result of force or coercion appear to be

more common among teenagers than among adults (Gage, 2001). Power disparities based on economics, age, and gender make adolescent girls more vulnerable than adult women to exploitative and coercive sexual practices, especially if pressure on them to earn income are strong because of their own needs or because of demand from their family members (Podhisita et.al, 1994). Adolescent girls may have little leverage with which to say “no” to unwanted sex or to oppose male partners who argue that no risk is involved in having sexual relations.

2.5.1 Sexual Activities:

Though sex is understood and expressed in a physical manner, it is more than just a physical activity. Sex involves feelings, thoughts, beliefs and values. These sexual feelings and expressions engage people in different ways. For the example holding hands, fantasizing, gazing affectionately and kissing.

- **Kissing** is the pleasurable touching of one’s lips against another’s or other parts of the body. Deep kissing is pressing the mouths together with the lips parted, which allows for one’s tongue to play in the other’s mouth.
- **Masturbation** is the manual stimulation of one’s genitals. It may involve rubbing, stroking and caressing one’s own genitals. This can occur individually or with other person(s). It is a normal and natural activity, done by boys and girls, men and women. As long as people take care to not hurt themselves and do not let it interfere with the other things they have to do like games, studies etc., there is no harm in masturbating. There are a number of myths associated with masturbation, although it is one of the safest forms of sex in relation to HIV transmission. It is a personal and pleasurable act. The act is not dirty and it does not matter how often you masturbate.
- **Fantasy:** Having day dreams/fantasies about sexual behaviour is normal among adolescents. For some adolescents heroes and heroines from cinema become the role models and they try to emulate them, often leading to disappointment.
- **Experiencing pleasure:** When certain parts of the body are touched (like holding hands, hugging, kissing etc.) in loving and caring ways, feeling of pleasure is experienced by adolescents/youth.
- **Obscene phone calls:** This is a punishable offence in India and complaint can be lodged with the police. In this the anonymous callers indulge in obscene talks which results in a feeling of helplessness and harassment on part of the receiver.
- **Use of SMS through Mobile:** Sending vulgar messages through mobile phone via SMS is also one of the common sexual behaviours indulged by adolescents.
- **Eroticism:** Feeling sexual excitement/enjoyment from certain actions/images etc.(For example, pornography)
- **Sexual harassment:** It includes a variety of behaviours. For example, making fun/passing remarks about some one’s appearance/body parts; unwanted touching; demands by teacher or other people in authority in exchange for marks, promotion, salary raise; eve teasing and so on. These are behaviours that are manipulative and people have a right to lodge a complaint against sexual harassment. This is a punishable offence in India.

Rape: This is a criminal offence in India and the rapist may be sentenced up to 7 years in jail. The punishment is more severe if the victim is a minor. Rape means

coercing/forcing/refusing to accept no in order to have genital contact with the other person. The rapist always uses strength/power/threat with the victim and induces fear, humiliation, guilt and low self-esteem in the victim. Sometimes the scars/psychological damage take many years to heal. People should lodge a complaint in case of rape. You will learn more about it in Block 3, unit 2 of theory paper.

2.6 LACK OF UNDERSTANDING ON HIV/AIDS

• Misconception & HIV/AIDS:-

Misconceptions about HIV/AIDS are widespread. UNICEF statistics (2003-2008) show that only 36% of adolescent males in India have comprehensive knowledge of HIV, while their female counterparts lag behind with just 20% of them having complete and accurate HIV information. A national study by NACO (National Behavioral Surveillance Survey, 2001) among young people (15-24 years) found that the level of awareness about HIV was higher in urban adolescents compared to their rural counterparts, more in males than females and that education increased the levels of awareness. Eighty-three percent respondents knew of at least two correct modes of transmission of HIV/AIDS. Nearly half of them report using condom in the last casual sex and consistent condom use is much lower. In the UNICEF study (2003-2008), 37% males used condom at last higher-risk sex, while only 22% females had used condoms.

• Lack of Awareness:-

Lack of HIV/AIDS knowledge and incorrect HIV/AIDS information are associated with HIV infection (Paniagua., et.al, 1997). Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are increasing the likelihood of HIV transmission as well as having other reproductive health consequences such as chronic lower abdominal pain, infertility or life threatening ectopic pregnancies (UNFPA, 2003). World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that at least one third of the 333 million new cases of curable sexually transmitted infections (STIs) each year occur among people under age 25 years (WHO, 1998). It has been estimated that at the end of 2001, approximately 40 million people worldwide were living with HIV/AIDS. Of which, a total of 6.4 million people belonged to the Asian region. Young people bear a special burden in the HIV/AIDS pandemic. Adolescents are more vulnerable than adults of unplanned pregnancies, sexually transmitted diseases and HIV/AIDS (Gubhaju, 2002). Among the adolescents, girls are more vulnerable to STDs including HIV/AIDS, especially through heterosexual intercourse with others than their male counterparts. This increased vulnerability is attributable to the fact beyond their control such as sexual violence and exploitation, early sexual initiation and inability to negotiate for safe sex. These further strengthened by strong discrimination, lack of education, lack of power, lack of access to contraception and reproductive health issues. So, it is nearly impossible for the adolescents to protect themselves from sexually transmitted diseases, HIV and unwanted pregnancies. On the other hand, the young people are not aware about the sexually transmitted diseases. Their knowledge about different diseases is very poor. There has been a host of studies which examined the knowledge on STDs among various age and social groups. Very limited studies have investigated young peoples' level of knowledge about STDs and AIDS. Most of the studies explored just naming of the diseases. The ability of the peoples' either knowledge or mode of transmission and its prevention is very limited (Minichiello, et.al, 1996). Not only

this, their knowledge is a mixture of facts, myths and rumors and is not always correct. An unfortunate misconception is prevailing among the young people. This sort of perception exists in different parts of the world. Keeping in view the earlier mentioned issues among the adolescents, it is necessary that they need to be helped towards improving their knowledge, attitude and behavior. Therefore before designing an intervention it is necessary to study and understand the adolescents better and this study emphasizes to fill up the gap prevailing in the important area to understand from the adolescents' perspectives their knowledge attitude practices towards HIV/AIDS.

In the studies conducted on adolescents, it has been found that most adolescents tend to be largely unaware of their reproductive system. A study conducted in 21 districts of the state revealed that only 23 percent of the girls were aware of the issues related to health, nutrition and family life (UNICEF, 1991). This study also indicates that one of the reasons for lack of awareness was poor exposure to mass media or other means of information. The data from NFHS-I has further supported this observation. It has revealed that 70 percent of teenage married women did not have regular access to any media. However the situation showed some improvement in NFHS-II. A little less than half of the women had access to radio or television at least once a week. The access to television particularly shows improvement between NFHS-I and NFHS-II.

- **Poor quality research feedback:**

The task being gigantic and the work that needs to be done for the patients infected with HIV or suffering from AIDS for many years being unprecedented in terms of scale and efforts government alone cannot be expected to take up the total control programme. Voluntary organizations too have to be involved in "behavior change" programme. The world Health Organization also has emphasized its need. But it appears that at present, the voluntary organizations are unwilling and consider themselves to these social realities. Focusing on the social factors influencing the vulnerability of people to HIV infection, the voluntary organizations can provide information services and other social support systems to people in danger or catching the disease. Before catching the information, knowledge in the spreads of HIV infection can be imparted by community-based social workers. Knowledge imparted by voluntary organizations to the prostitute for safe sex will create an environment in which these women can make choices and act on them. The capacity to motivate and sustain the involvement of the vulnerable people will determine the success of the voluntary organization. After being infected with virus the need for psychological and social support is as crucial as medical support and non-governmental organizations from a certain disease total dependence on the medical system will be unwise and will surely result in a failure. There is a simultaneous need to prepare communities to be able to cope with caring for the diseased people and to find resources for this within the community itself. The voluntary organizations can surely make genuine effort towards this support system. Besides helping the patients, the voluntary organizations can also help the children, families and other dependents of the sufferers who become victims of isolation and discriminations.

Action is an international anti-poverty agency working in over 40 countries, taking sides with poor people to end poverty and injustice together. Action Aid India Society has

been implementing the Link Workers Scheme (LWS) in 1595 villages of 295 Grampanchayats of six districts in Odisha viz; Angul, Balasore, Bhadrak, Balangir, Ganjam and Khurda in close coordination with Odisha State AIDS Control Society (OSACS), supported by National AIDS Control Organization and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), India since October 2008.

As on October 2010, the project has covered 1,722,230 populations, 5,318 Female Sex Workers, 2,746 MSMs, 182 injecting Drug Users, 2,14,245 vulnerable population, 3,336 PLHIVs, 1,131 Orphan and Vulnerable Children with Sexually Transmitted Infection (STUs), Reproductive Tract Infections (RTI), HIV & AIDS Preventive, Curative and Treatment services through different innovative programmes like Mid Media programmes, Community Programmes, One-to-One and one-to Group Counseling, Peer group Meetings and special events.

2.7 EXISTING POLICIES & PROGRAMMES:

State governments generally follow Government of India policies, and implement programmes as per norms/guidelines laid down. Some state governments have, however, undertaken initiatives to formulate their own state specific policies to address some state issues. A review of policies of central and state governments reveals that while some of the policies deal with adolescent health and development related issues explicitly, others though not addressing the issue directly, implicitly relate to this important population group (Gupta 2002). The important policies are relevant to adolescent health and developments are:

- ✓ National Policy for Children, 1974
- ✓ National Health Policy, 1983 (now the Draft National Health Policy, 2000)
- ✓ National Population Policy, 2000
- ✓ National Policy for Women
- ✓ National Nutrition Policy, 1993
- ✓ National Policy in Education, 1986 (Modified 1992)
- ✓ National Youth Policy, 1986 and Draft New National Youth Policy, 2000
- ✓ National Policy for Child Labour, 1987)

2.7.1 Programmes undertaken by the govt. in controlling the disease:-

At the national level, the National AIDS Control Committee, under the chairmanship of Minister of Health and Family Welfare has been constituted. AIDS education in school has been taken up to sensitize the students from class- IX onwards. The electronic media, print media and other field based organizations of the Government have been involved in awareness generation on HIV AIDS till March 1998. 3500 counselors had been trained in various states at the grass root level under the National training program of NACO. National AIDS telephone help line in cooperation with Department of Telecommunications has been set up with a toll free four digit number 1097 for computerized information and counseling on telephone for HIV/AIDS and STDs. The first project under this help line has been functioning in Delhi since October 1997. Telephone counseling facilities have also been set up in Chennai, Hyderabad, Calcutta and Guwahati and proposed to be expanded to other cities.

For ensuring safe blood supply, a network of HIV testing facilities has been established with 154 zonal Blood Testing Centers all over the country. These centers provide linkages to blood banks located in government, voluntary and private sectors. National Blood Transfusion Council and State Blood Transfusion Council have been set up for promotion of voluntary blood donation camp for the proper management of HIV AIDS cases. Training of medical doctors working in Government and non-government sectors is being undertaken through government institutions. IMA voluntary Health Association of India (VHAI) etc. States are being given 100 percent financial support in implementation of the National AIDS control Programme including clinical management. This understanding of how the virus works has led to a change in the aim of treatment for HIV. Rather than waiting for HIV to damage the immune system by destroying CD4 cells, the purpose of anti-HIV therapy now is to reduce HIV viral load so that the immune system can be preserved.

2.7.2 Programmes Undertaken by the Government of Odisha- Odisha State AIDS Control Society (OSACS) was formed to implement HIV/AIDS prevention and control programmes in Odisha at state level. It functions under National AIDS Control Organization (NACO), ministry of health and family welfare Govt. of India. Since July 2004, OSACS has been working steadily towards curbing this dreaded disease and helping those affected by the virus much has been achieved but the battle is still on as there were 22,720 people infected with HIV till October 2011 in Odisha. Out of this 1,504 people were AIDS affected. HIV cases among male is 13,246 and female is 8,070. According to the recorded HIV positive cases in Odisha, 76% cases are seen between the age group of 29 and 49.

- **Services and Support for PLHIV Targeted Interventions-** Four major groups- Female Sex Worker (FSW), Intravenous Drug User (IDU), Men Having Sex with Men (MSM) and migrant labourers- are the most vulnerable to the disease. Keeping this in view, OSACS are running 67 targeted interventions projects covering more than 1 Lakh target groups with NGOs. Includes 9 projects especially for injecting drug users, helping around 2,200 IDUS.
- **Community Care Center-** To provide long-term support in psychological, social and health care, community care centers have been opened. Currently in Odisha, 5 such centers are operating at the ART or link centers with the help of NGO partners.
- **PPTCT Cell-** PPTCT Cell works to strengthen PPTCT service delivery in the state. Training of HCPs, institutional delivery, pre-ART registration, Administration of NVP to MB pare, counseling, breast feeding practices, EID, Line listing and follow of care to CLHIV are the important activities undertaken by the PPTCT Cell.
- **Drop in Center-** In order to strengthen PLHA networks conduct various advocacy workshop for the rights of positive people, OSACS provides financial support to 10 drop in centers managed by different PLHA networks at the district level.
- **Red Ribbon Club (RRC)-** Youth is identified as a vulnerable group with 31% of AIDS victims being those within the 19 to 29 years. For creating awareness on HIV /AIDS among youth, OSACS established 700 RRCS in degree colleges and Universities across Odisha in collaboration with Indian Red Cross Society, Odisha State Branch and NSS, Sambalpur University.
- **Mainstreaming HIV/AIDS-** HIV/AIDS is no longer only a health issue. The causes and impact are multi sectorial, keeping on this in view OSACS has focused on integration

and convergence as an effective strategy to work with the line Govt. departments, NGOs, International Organizations, Corporate and civil Society in Odisha.

- **Madhubabu Pension Yojana**- Odisha is the first state in the country to provide social security to PLHA giving a RS 200 per month pension to people living with HIV/AIDS. Confidentially regarding identity is strictly maintained and no physical verification is required in this case. Till Jan 2011, 13,666 people received pension under this yojana.
- **Mo KudiaYojana**- A low-cost free housing scheme has been launched for the HIV infected family. Till Sept 2011 around 154 HIV infected families received benefits under this Yojana.
- **Targeted intervention** -To halt the HIV/AIDS: there are four major groups –female sex workers (FSW), intravenous drug user (IDU), men having sex with men (MSM) and migrant labourers are mostly most vulnerable to HIV keeping view of this OSACS with the support of civil society is running 61 targeted intervention in 24 district of Odisha.
- **Blood bank & Blood Component Separation Unit**- To halt the HIV /AIDS provision of safe blood is equally important to the control HIV/AIDS. At present, 89 blood banks with five having blood components separate unit and nine blood storage centers established in Odisha.
- **Red Ribbon Club (RRC)** - youth can make a difference: youth are identified as a vulnerable group to HIV /AIDS under the National AIDS Control Programme, phase- III. For creating awareness on HIV/AIDS among youth (students), OSACS established 600 Red Ribbon Clubs in degree colleges and universities of Odisha in collaboration with Indian Red Cross Society, Odisha branch.
- **Red Ribbon Express (RRE)**- World's Largest Social mobilization campaign against HIV/AIDS a unique train called Red Ribbon Express (RRE), Visited Odisha's 9 railway stations from May 02-22, starting from Rayagada, Korapur, Berhampur, Mancheswar (Bhubaneswar), Cuttack, Jajpur, Keonjhar Road, Jaleswar, Balangir and Rourkela Railway station. The RRE halted for a period for a period of two days in each station. A crowd of more than 30000 gathered at Berhampur railway station, which had the second highest population in a particular halt station so far. During this period a total of 99,987 persons visited the exhibition and 4,049 participated in the training programme. 2,795 persons were counseled out of which 1,981 persons tested and 371 persons were treated for STD. In IEC van campaign 352 cultural programme conducted covering up 1,760 villages which has been witnessed by 249 lakh people of the state (Times of India 1/1/2011).

Fig 2.5-Involvement of adolescents in awareness programmes

2.5(a) Be the member of awareness

2.5 (b) Together towards new eras

2.5 (c) take Oath Today Onwards.....

2.5 (d) Lets learn for Living of Life

2.5(e) towards new li

2.5(f) Towards New Life

2.5(h) A Procession for World AIDS day

2.5(i) "Red ribbon" performed by the students

2.7.3 Services and Facilities for the HIV/AIDS People:

- ❖ **Awareness Raising:** It is accepted that HIV infection is entirely preventable through awareness rising. Therefore, awareness rising about its occurrence and spread is very significant in protecting the people from the epidemic. It is for this reason that the National AIDS Control Programme lays maximum emphasis on the widespread reach of information, education and communication on HIV/AIDS prevention. Changing knowledge, attitudes, and practices along with behaviour of the high risk group and 95 percent of the young people. In fact, the awareness campaign of NACP has received a big boost with the formation of National Council on AIDS that has mainstreamed HIV prevention activities in various government institutions and programmes. The programme focuses on high risk groups (commercial sex workers, injecting drug users, men who have sex with men), migrants and truckers, and a large number of young women and men in the general community, with information on various aspects of vulnerability of HIV infection.
- ❖ **Management of STI/RTI:** Sexually transmitted diseases are one of the determinants of HIV transmission. Increased demand for the services through capacity building among the medical practitioners of primary healthcare centre community healthcare centre and the private regional medical practitioners providing STD services. The Programme also supports not-for-profit private practitioners and NGOs in the management of STDs among the high risk groups.
- ❖ **Condom promotion:** NACO advocates and promotes condom use as a safe sex practice for prevention of STI/RTI and HIV, in addition to protection from unwanted pregnancy. The availability of free supply, subsidized and commercial brands of condoms was also increased during NACP I & II. Increase the number of free condoms distributed through STI and STD clinics, reaching those who are at the

highest risk of acquiring or transmitting HIV and non-traditional outlets for socially marketed condoms, e.g. pan shops, lodges etc. in strategically located hotspots of solicitation.

- ❖ **Access to safe blood:** The specific objective of the blood safety programme is to ensure reduction in the transfusion association with HIV transmission to 0.5 percent, while integrated making available safe and quality blood within one hour of requirement in a health facility.
- ❖ **Integrated Counseling and Testing Centre (ICTC):** Establishment of ICTC for conducting HIV diagnostic tests, providing basic information on the modes of HIV transmission, and promoting behavioural change to reduce vulnerability and Link people with other HIV prevention, care and treatment services.
- ❖ **Post exposure prophylaxis (PEP):** refers to comprehensive medical management to minimize the risk of infection among Health Care Personnel (HCP) following potential exposure to blood-borne pathogens (HIV, HBV, and HCV). This includes counseling, risk assessment, relevant laboratory investigation based on informed consent of the source and exposed person, first aid and depending on the risk assessment, the provision of short terms (for weeks) of antiretroviral drugs, with follow up and support.
- ❖ **Prevention of Parent to Child Transmission:** The PPTCT programme aims to prevent the perinatal transmission of HIV from an HIV infected pregnant mother to her newborn baby. The programme entails counseling and testing of pregnant women in the ICTS. Pregnant women who are found to be HIV positive and given a single dose of nevirapine at the time of labor; there newborn babies also get a single dose of nevirapine immediately after birth so as to prevent transmission of HIV from mother to child.
- ❖ **Anti-retroviral therapy (ART):** ART is now available free to all those who need it. PLHA with less than 200 CD4 (while blood cells/mm³) require treatment irrespective of the clinical stage. For PLHA with 200-350 CD4, ART is offered to symptomatic patients.
- ❖ **Care and Support:** Under NACP-II, focus was given on low-cost care, support and treatment of common positive people. Apart from further improving the availability, accessibility and affordability of ART treatment to the poor, NACP-III plans to strengthen family and community care through psychosocial support to the individuals, more particularly to the marginalized women and children affected by the epidemic, improve compliance of the prescribed ART regimen, and address stigma and discrimination associated with the epidemic. The active this objective, 350 Community Care Centre are planned to be set up during the programme period (2007-2012) in partnership with PLHA in high prevalence and moderate prevalence districts. These centers will be established based on the epidemiological profile and PLHA load of the districts, and linked to the nearest ART centre. The centers will provide counseling for drop adherence, nutritional needs, treatment support, referral and outreach for follow up, social support and legal services. State AIDS Prevention and Control Societies will ensure access of high risk groups to community care centers through linkages between this and the centers.

Services and Facilities for HIV Positive Children: National Aids Control Organization (NACO) with the support of Indian Academy of Pediatrics, Clinton Foundation, UNICEF and WHO have formulated the policy and guidelines which form the basis of the “National Pediatric initiative” for children living with HIV. NACO under this initiative has set a target for providing Anti Retroviral Therapy (ART) to children. Approximately 50,000 children below 15 years are infected by HIV every year. So far, care and support response to these children was at a very minimal level. NACP-II plans to improve this through early diagnosis and treatment of HIV exposed children; comprehensive guidelines on pediatric HIV care for each level of health system; special training to counselors for counseling HIV positive children; linkages with social sector programmes for accessing social support for infected children; outreach and transportation subsidy to facilitate ART and follow up, nutritional, educational, recreational and skill development support, and by establishing and enforcing minimum standard of care and protection in institutional, foster care and community-based care systems.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

“Research Methodology” is a way of systematically solving the research problem. It explains the steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying the research problem along with the logic behind it. It also may be understood as all these methods or techniques that are used for conduction of a research. It occupies a great importance and value in research work. It would be difficult to comprehend the nature and content of research without appropriate research methodology. This chapter deals with the methodology adopted for the study entitled “Knowledge, Attitude and Practices towards HIV/AIDS among Female Adolescents”. Present study involves the following steps:

- 3.1 Statement of the Problem
- 3.2 Significance of the Study
- 3.3 Scope of the Study
- 3.4 Operational Definitions
- 3.5 Research Design
- 3.6 Methods of Data Collection
- 3.7 Analysis of Data

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

A problem statement is the description of an issue currently existing which needs to be addressed. It provides the context for the research study and generates the questions which the research aims to answer. The statement of the problem is the focal point of any research. A good problem statement is just one sentence (with several paragraphs of elaboration). Over 1,400 people have lost their lives due to AIDS in Ganjam district in the last 14 years as per the latest figures released by Odisha State AIDS Control Society (OSACS-2013), the State-level nodal agency for fighting the dreaded disease. By the end of October, 12,307 persons in the district were identified as HIV positive while 1,404 persons succumbed to AIDS between 2000 and 2014. As per the reports of ‘ARUNA’, (a social service non-governmental voluntary organization) working for prevention of AIDS, majority of PLWHA (People Living with HIV/AIDS) are from rural Ganjam district. Large scale migration, ignorance, low female literacy, inadequate prevention activities, stigma and discrimination are the reasons behind the spread of AIDS in the state. Adolescents in India are highly vulnerable to human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs) (Hemalata et.al.2011).

Given the prevailing social, economic and cultural inequities in India, a large number of adolescents are forced to work and live in inhospitable, unsafe and exploitative conditions. They can be found trapped in various situations that emphasize the need to individualize the therapy according to the background from which an adolescent comes. Some of the most vulnerable situations that cause the Indian adolescents to be infected by HIV/AIDS are Adolescents those living in streets, working as sex workers, trafficked adolescents, runaway adolescents, abandoned adolescents, sexually abused adolescents, sexually active adolescents, adolescents using substance and orphan adolescents are found commonly vulnerable to get infected from HIV/AIDS. Street has the dubious distinction of highest number of adolescents living on streets. Most of these adolescents are found in the big cities of the country. They

earn their living through rag picking, working in hotels, involvement in prostitution and so on. This group is the most vulnerable because they do not have alternative options. The most vulnerable are the girls. Puberty brings new stress into adolescent street girls' lives. These girls do not have mothers or female relatives to explain to them about protecting themselves from the vulnerability of HIV/AIDS. Even though their parents continue to live with them, they may not have adequate knowledge or ability to protect the adolescent girls from the dangers of coerced sex. Most of them are sexually abused even before they reach the age of ten years. The tenderness of the age of street girl does not appear to their risk of sexual abuse. Very often girl children of all age groups are sexually abused or raped. Street girls also indulge in drug abuse. Most of them pick up the habit unknowingly. Many of them land in brothel houses against their will. They have no marriage or family life. Under such circumstances a girl child is exposed to risk factors causing HIV infection.

The adolescent is exposed to new social situations, patterns of behavior and societal expectations which bring a sense of insecurity. It has been found that there is increase in the incidence of depression. The adolescents show the tendency of impulsive urges to take immediate action which often leads to risk taking behavior. Unprotected vaginal intercourse with an HIV infected partner causes most HIV infection among women. Females are more susceptible to HIV infection than men when exposed to the virus during vaginal intercourse. Since women have a greater area of exposed tissue such as the cervix and the vagina, any small tear may occur in the vaginal tissue during sex makes an easy pathway for infection. This is increasingly risky when it comes to adolescent females who encounter early sexual debut in their life. Hence female adolescents are prone to vulnerability and at increased risk of contracting HIV infection very early in their life that can cause severe impact on them and the society around.

Present study is an attempt to understand female adolescents' knowledge, attitude and practices regarding HIV/AIDS. By this study the researcher desires to understand female adolescents' level of knowledge, their attitude and practices towards HIV/AIDS, and also help them to improve on healthy sexual behaviour so that their vulnerability to the risk of HIV/AIDS is reduced.

3.2 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The health of adolescents has become a subject of increasing importance throughout the world. This is especially true with regard to their sexual health. Adolescent females experiencing early sexual debut are always been at greater risk of contracting HIV/AIDS. Adolescents become sexually active without knowing the facts and risks involved in it for its short term and long term health effects. This study helps in analyzing the knowledge base of female adolescents, their attitude towards the infection and also the current practices contributing to vulnerability to HIV/AIDS and helps in reducing such vulnerability among the female adolescents.

HIV/AIDS have assumed epidemic form in India. An estimated 4 million persons are reported to be affected with HIV infection. The magnitude of the problem is expected to increase further. Around 50% of the reported cases are among the sexually active young

people aged below 25 years. Adolescents are more vulnerable to HIV by certain taboos, ideologies and social norms. This is particularly the case where young people are denied knowledge and skills on sexual and reproductive matters, barred from reproductive health services including HIV prevention. Adolescents are left along to deal with the biological and social transformation often with no caring adult to talk. This present study signifies in terms of identifying the need based programmes that are required for adolescents to have up-to-date knowledge.

This study intends to study the adolescent's knowledge pertaining to HIV/AIDS, their attitude and practices towards HIV / AIDS. As adolescents, those who are studying in various institutions it is necessary that equal attention needs to be given to them and we should help them to develop self help skills so as to prevent risky sexual behaviour. This study also finds appropriate measures for developing adolescent oriented prevention programmes, and effectively addressing the prevention and care of adolescents. This study would result in mitigation of the vigorous spread of HIV/AIDS, by generating awareness and developing adolescent-friendly programmes that are more effective, adolescent centered, result based and sustainable.

It will also strive to create an empirical basis for national level planning on sex education in schools so as to inculcate better knowledge, attitude and practices on HIV/ AIDS. As this study involves in studying the different contexts in which sexual activity among adolescents takes place, it is more helpful in deciding and designing appropriate programmes suitable for adolescents towards promoting healthy sexual practices in a friendly manner. This can be more effective in contributing to the prevention of the vigorous spread of STD/HIV/AIDS among adolescents. This study also adds its significance to policy making, social planning, project formulation that are subjected to empirical basis, which pave the way to conduct projects for the adolescents betterment both at state and national level.

3.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The present study was conducted in both the rural and urban areas of Odisha. Adolescent girls enrolled for education in the girls' high schools and +2 Junior colleges are studied. Data pertaining to adolescents' knowledge, attitude and practices towards HIV/AIDS are collected. The age group of the respondents is between 14 to 17 years. The study includes only female adolescent girls. The study will aid in understanding their knowledge, attitude and practices towards HIV/AIDS and also gives scope for generating awareness among them. This study provides the scope for suggesting measures to overcome the serious issues that affect adolescents in terms of contracting HIV/AIDS. The study also extends its scope for enabling adolescents to be protected against the transmission of HIV/AIDS by improving upon their knowledge.

3.4 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS:

- **Adolescence:** India is the second most populous country in the world with a total population over 1220 million and adolescents from a large section of the population at the rate of 22.5%, that is about 275 million as per the senses data. Adolescence has been defined by WHO (World Health Organization) as the period of life spanning between 10-

19 years and the youth as between 15-24 years (N. Swaminathan 2013). The ICDS, India defines adolescence as 11 – 18 years (ICDS 1975). The NCERT categorizes adolescence into three different categories and has defined them as early adolescence: 13 – 14 years, middle adolescence: 15 – 17 years and late adolescence: 16 – 19 years. In Indian culture there is no definite age range of the adolescent period acceptable throughout the nation. Stott (1974) has started that adolescent period of development as all other human development periods is a time transition, of moving along a continuum from one signal point to the next, according to Stott the onset of puberty which usually occurs between the ages of 10 and 13 which is early adolescence, the middle adolescence occurs between the ages of 12 and 15 years and the latter adolescence occurs between the ages of 16 and 20 years. But the ages of adolescence varies according to culture. The three views expressed by the authors are from the development point view.

This classification varies from the popular views to some extent. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, the adolescent's age ranges from 14 to 25 years for males and 12 to 21 years for females. It seems that that seems that there is no universally accepted age range for adolescence. Till boys and girls move into adulthood they are adolescents only. Therefore, the present studies from 14 to 25 years are included to study their knowledge, attitudes and fractions adopted. This is because, at the age of 14 the boys and girls enter the 10th standard or S.S.L.C and this is supposed to be the school final and the students leave the high school and enter higher secondary school at the age of 15. After having spent two years in the higher secondary school the students enter the college at the age of 17 in the first year of the 10+2 course.

- **HIV/AIDS:** HIV (Human Immune deficiency Virus): Human Immune deficiency virus is that causes AIDS. The virus is passed from one person to another through blood-to-blood and sexual contact. In addition, infected pregnant women can pass HIV to their baby during pregnancy or delivery, as well as through breast feeding. People with HIV have what is called HIV infection. Some of the body fluids of human beings have been proved to spread the virus are blood, semen, vaginal fluid, breast milk and other body fluids containing blood. AIDS (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome): Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) is the name of the fatal clinical condition that results from long term infection with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). AIDS is the name for the collection of symptoms that result from the immune deficiency caused by HIV. HIV progressively weakens the body's immune defense system, until it is no longer able to fight of infections, among of which waved have been otherwise harmless. AIDS is not a disease rather; it is a syndrome (a group of illness). There is no curable for AIDS and at present neither there any vaccines that can prevent HIV infections. An HIV+ or Sero+ person is permanently infectious to others. HIV is transmitted through semen, Vaginal Fluid, Blood and Breast Milk.
- **Knowledge:** Adolescent's knowledge about HIV/AIDS is important especially when it is considered a major challenge posing threat to their development. Lack of knowledge about HIV/AIDS regarding the basic knowledge about the curability nature of AIDS, causes, channels of transmissions, vulnerable population, risk behavior, treatment, the preventive measures and sources of information may lead to risky sexual behaviour resulting into HIV or the opportunistic infection. Adolescent girls complete knowledge of on HIV/AIDS

i.e. the full form of HIV/AIDS; its nature, characteristics, transmission, causes, role of the virus, types and who are the vulnerable populations, infected people face the problems regarding AIDS, the location of the ICTC and the organizations working on this incurable disease sources of information regarding HIV/AIDS. Under this heading there were only two questions about the information regarding HIV/AIDS.

- **Attitude:** Adolescents form a sizeable proportion of the population. The National Family health Survey (NFHS – 2), 1998-99, found approximately 22 percent India's population comprise of the 15-19 age group. Adolescence is the most volatile period of life, with the children attempting to shed parental restriction while seeking new identity or making new contacts. Peers and friends from opposite sex become more important who seem to exert more influence than the previous role models (parents and teachers). Experimentation with new friends, new behaviour with drugs, and even sex, pose additional challenges for adolescents and parents alike. Girls suffer more acute and dramatic physical, mental and emotional change with little support forthcoming from parents, families or teachers. Because of their greater vulnerability, they may fall prey to exploitation during this period, which may culminate into an unwanted pregnancy or a sexually acquired disease including HIV.

Attitude and behavior surrounding sexuality carry profound meaning for men and women in every society and affect the quality of life in fundamental ways. In some cultures ideologies of sexuality stress female resistance, male aggression and mutual antagonism in the sex act (Kiska and standing 1989).

The study attempted to elicit the adolescents attitude and practices regarding various aspects of sex and sexuality, such as attitude towards relationship with opposite sex, perception about conception and virginity, exposure to pornography literature, sexual experiences, condom use, awareness about mode of transmission as well as preventative measures of HIV/AIDS and safe sex. During adolescence, the individuals face a wide range and variety of emotions. These include both Positive emotions like love, happiness, joy as well as negative emotions like, sadness, depression, unhappiness, anxiety. In addition, feelings of anger, rebellion and protest also emerge. Interestingly, emotions of loyalty patriotism and sacrifice for the nation also develop during adolescence (IGNOU, 2011).

To understand the attitude of adolescents towards people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHAs) The respondents in this study were asked about how far they approved the positive attitude, negative attitude and misconception about the HIV/AIDS disease and positive people. Attitude and behaviour surrounding sexuality carry profound meaning for men and women in every society and affect the quality of life in fundamental ways. Adolescent have incorrect attitudes and behavioural patterns that can lead to both social problems and ill health. Adolescents may also differ from adult in terms of their understanding of the risk of engaging in certain behaviours. This difference may partly be due to the knowledge and attitude regarding sexuality and the perceived risk of the several practices. Hence while studying the sexual behaviours of adolescents the knowledge, attitude and practices of adolescents become important aspects.

Attitude of the adolescents towards the infections those were the general feeling about the infected persons and what way they should be treated and how they will be accepted by the society their family and self-behavior of the hated disease.

- **Practices:** Human sexual activities or human sexual behavior refers to the manner in which humans experience and express their sexuality. People engage in a variety of sexual acts from time to time, and for a wide variety of reasons. Sexual activity normally results in sexual arousal and physiological changes in the aroused person, some of which are pronounced while others are more subtle. Sexual activity also includes conduct and activities which are intended to arouse the sexual interest of oneself and/or another.

Adolescence can be seen as a time when many sexual attitudes and reactions that were rehearsed in childhood begin to reveal their true meaning. Most important of all, it is a period in which experimental and exploratory sex play turns into purposeful adult sexual behavior. In this context the study attempted to know the different sexual activities the respondents indulged in. Misconceptions and misbeliefs on sexual issues are not uncommon among adolescents. Sometimes lack of adequate information and opportunities prompt these young people to turn to literature (often pornographic), experimentation with prostitutes, friends or relatives of opposite sex and at times the same sex, and observation of sexual activities and masturbation. Many studies reflect that female fantasies are largely romantic and emotional in nature. There is often a tendency to assume that the members of the opposite sex think and feel the same as oneself. This assumption, which is far removed from reality, results in a lot of confusion, misunderstandings and tensions, especially, during the process of dating.

Sex and relationships is still a taboo subject between parents and teenage daughters, despite access to formal education and wider exposure to the realities of life through media. Hence there have been efforts to provide proper education on matters related to human sexuality and reproductive health through the educational system. In this background it is important to assess the level of understanding of HIV/AIDS and to ascertain the attitude towards persons living with HIV/AIDS.

3.5 RESEARCH DESIGN:

The formidable problem that follows the task of defining the research problem is the preparation of the design of the research work, popularly known as the "Research Design". A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure. For this study the researcher has adopted exploratory study and the design adopted to carry out this research is the descriptive design. By using this design, the researcher attempts to describe female adolescents' knowledge and understanding about HIV/AIDS, their sources of information about HIV/AIDS, the myths associated with HIV/AIDS, their attitude towards HIV/AIDS, their current practices regarding HIV/AIDS are described as reported by the respondents in a clear cut manner. The study obtained the various details of the respondent namely personal profile, demographic profile of the family members especially both parents i.e. educational, occupational, status and family income along with the details of their belonging as well as their living styles. A clear picture can be derived from the migration

status of the respondents as you know migration is a positive phenomenon and if regulated and managed properly can reap in benefits for both the sending and receiving regions. Inter-state labour migration is an important future of the Indian economy, for which 90% labours of Ganjam district alone migrate to other states. Knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS where including respondents basic knowledge which contains the HIV/AIDS' nature, causes, treatment, location of ICTC, channels of transmission, the sources of information, the risk groups and the preventive measures.

The attitude of female adolescents towards HIV/AIDS is also another important component of the study. The study attempts the various aspects of sex and sexuality, such as negative and positive attitude towards the disease and its victims. There are also some myth and misconception associated with the dreaded disease and people who infected with HIV/AIDS. Adolescents are many times guided by their peer members and as a result of their myths stem out of them in many ways. Last but not least component is the adolescents practice adoption towards HIV/AIDS, sometimes because of the lack of inadequate information and opportunities promote these young adolescents to turn to pornographic, experimentation with opposite sex or with same sex or abbreviations of sexual activities and masturbation, though the sex and sexual relation before marriage is still taboo in our society.

3.6 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION -

A) Universe of the study: The proposed investigation was carried out in the state of Odisha situated in the eastern part of India. It is basically an agricultural state and inspite of rise in levels of urbanization and industrialization, traditional and cultural values still exist. The Odiya people are deeply religious and follow different rituals for every occasion. Every event of life is considered as God's gift (be it good or bad) and is accepted faithfully. Because of this thinking it is still dated one of the most neglected and backward states of the country. Being rural based, it is characterized by poor literacy rate and high infant mortality. Persistence in traditional methods of living leads to loss of socio-cultural interactions with outsiders and less innovation in the sphere of technological and socio-economic pursuits. However, this low-prevalent state Odisha has been witnessing an alarming situation due to the unsafe sex practice of migrated labourers who unmindful of the fact that sexual route is the major cause of HIV/AIDS, prefer to sexual escapades in the slum areas of Surat known for its red light areas rendering few minutes pleasure. Particularly, the unemployed youths of Ganjam, the home district of Odisha, migrate in lakhs (6 lakh as per rough estimation) to Surat (Gujarat) and Mumbai. The maximum migration is reported from Hinjilicut, Purushottampur, Bhanjanagar, Aska, Digapahandi, and Beguniapada blocks of Ganjam district.

People migrate with the hope of employment. Of course the city life is also an attraction to them. Most literate or semiliterate the youth from rural Ganjam migrate with eyeful of dreams. However many of them return with only to count the days of their life after being infected in the deadly virus. The study was conducted in Ganjam district of Odisha state. Ganjam is one of the most populous, underdeveloped district in Odisha, with a population of; total- 35,20,151; male-17,77,324 and female- 17,42,827, per the 2011 census, and a sex ratio of 978 females to 1000 males. It consists of 22 blocks and 3 sub-divisions; with a

geographical area of 8071 sq km. Ganjam has the highest HIV prevalence in Odisha. In 2006, a study of 9200, women found that 0.55 percent of the population was positive. Among STI patients, 1750 were tested and 2.34, percent positive cases were detected.

Ganjam: Ganjam alone contributes 38 percent of the state's PLHIV and 37 percent of AIDS deaths. Latest figures from Odisha State AIDS Society estimate HIV infections among 7637 people, of whom 281 are from ANC centers, and 531 are children, while AIDS related deaths are reported to be 461 until now. There is a huge proportion of males who migrate to Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Uttar Pradesh for work in shipyards, mills and diamond cutting industries, leaving behind their spouses/wives in Ganjam. Ten community health centers and 15 primary health centers are distributed across the district in different blocks. There are five ART centers in the state of Odisha, including one at the M.K.C.G. Medical College in Berhampur, the district's major city, and another four link centers in the district recently introduced by the state AIDS society. Ganjam district has 26 functional individual counseling and testing centers (ICTCs) (Das 2012). Which was conservative, backward and more prevalence of HIV/AIDS district of the state had special significance in this study.

3.1 Map of Ganjam District

Aska: Aska is situated in the river bank of Rushikulya and the heart of the Ganjam district of Odisha state. It is the 3rd largest town which is connected to Berhampur, Chhatrapur, Khalikote, Nayagarh, Bhanjanagar and Soroda blocks. It is a under developed town there is no train root but Berhampur is the nearby railways station which is Major transit point for out migrants in Odisha This station is known for its labour traffic and collection of high revenue to East Cost Railways. And also it is import points for migrants who all are landless and marginal farmers as well as workers the notorious ‘Dadan’ which is the association of unemployed poor young mass. Aska is also surrounded by high hills and lusty bushes of Rusihikulya river banks with plains of natural green. It is 135 feet or (41 k. mtrs) highest from the sea level with a geographical area of 8293.10 Sq Km and 45 Km from Bay of Bengal with its Population around 20,739 per the 2011 census, seven villages are including in this NAC.

3.2 Map of Aska Block

3.3 Map of Bhanjanagar Block

Bhanjanagar: The Bhanjanagar is known as Ghumusar Thasil as per earliest while state of Ghumusar. The Tahasil is situated north part of the district. The Tahasil has main two irrigation project, Rosolkonda reservoir and Daha irrigation project. The area of the Tahasil is 28362 sq km, having population of 142601. There are 27,392 households in the block, of which 85560 are males and 57,042 are female census 2011.

B) Sampling Procedure: There are a total of 22 blocks in Ganjam district among them 12 blocks have reported HIV/AIDS cases. Aska reported the most prevalence of HIV/AIDS. The researcher decided to study 2 blocks under the age group 13-17years are available. They are Aska and Bhanjanagar. As per the latest reports, out of the 14 districts of the country most affected with the AIDS/HIV the Ganjam district is being placed eighth and has been graded

`A` status as more than one percent people of the total population are infected with HIV. Bhanjanagar is the neighbor block of Aska, it is also reported one of the prevalence block of Ganjam district is having 152 positive cases and hot spots are available. While the main Anti Retroviral Treatment (ART) centre is functioning at MKCG Medical College and Hospital here are four link centers at Aska, Bhanjanagar, Khallikote and Polasara. "The move will help in the regular check-up and treatment of these children at the ART centers" the (Distract Collector, Ganjam, 2011).

C)

The phase III of national AIDS control programme was about to end, but Ganjam is prevalence one, Head of OSACS said adding that the number of HIV patients has increased from 100 in 2000 to 14,000 in 212 in the district. According to official reports, 3,427 AIDS patients were identified in Ganjam till November 2012. While Aska has highest number of AIDS patients of 456, Chikiti has the lowest 40. Similarly, 60 cases were identified in Chhatrapur, 63 in Ganjam, 204 in Khallikote, 120 in Beguniapada, 341 in Polsara, 138 in Purushottampur, 161 in Kavisuryanagar, 139 in Hinjilicut, 349 in Rangeilunda, 53 in Kukudakhandi, 88 in Digapahandi, 124 in Sanakhemundi, 152 in Bhanjanagara, 206 in Belaguntha, 177 in Buguda, 44 in Jagannathprasad, 68 in Dharakote, 120 in Dorada and 173 in Sheragada (Orrisa Post 1/12/ 2013).

Considering the fact that these geographical areas are occupied by people with lower level of literacy and also living below poverty, the risk associated with HIV/AIDS infection to significantly higher these two blocks have been chosen for this present study. Aska is the highest no. and Bhanjanagar is the 2nd highest blocks in the district as the prevalence status. The universe of the study comprises all female adolescents between the age group of 13 -17 years. They are students admitted for education in IX, X, XI and XII in Govt. schools and +2 junior Colleges of Ganjam Dist. of Odisha state. There is a mix of students from tribal, rural, coastal villages, town or city; with a mixed culture components comprising this universe the names of Institutions and particulars of these universe and samples are clearly given in Table: 3.2

Table: 3.2- Distribution of Universe and Sample

Dist	Blocks	Schools/ Colleges	Universe	Percentage	Sample
Ganjam	Aska	Govt. Girl's High School	250	40%	100
		Niranjan Women's College	250	40%	100
	Bhanjanagar	Govt. Girl's High School	250	40%	100
		Sabitri Devi Women's College	250	40%	100
			1000		400

The total number of units in the universe of this study comprises 1000 female adolescents. The population is further stratified in to different strata constituting the schools to which this adolescent belongs. A sample of 25% is drawn from different strata chosen from the universe. The size of the sample selected for this study is 400. Hence proportion wise considering the sampling technique applied is proportionate in nature. The list of students from each institute, that projects the universe, was collected and then every 5th student constitutes the chosen sample and was interviewed. This selection of every 5th person

from the sample is systematic sampling under the random sampling design. To sum up, this study adopts the proportionate stratified random sampling design.

Respondents are true representations of the female adolescent population. Therefore, the results of this study can be generalized to a larger population of female adolescents. The study thus was conducted in 2 govt. Girls high schools and 2 junior colleges 2 women’s colleges located in the 2 prevalence blocks of Ganjam District. Further, the investigation found that these places as most suitable and convenient for conducting the investigation which is presumed to bring accuracy in the data to be collected. The names of Institutions and particulars of these universe and samples are clearly given in Figure.3.1.

Fig. 3.4: Sampling Procedure

C) Tools and Techniques Used – Present study adopted multi method approaches to collect primary data from the respondents under study. Being an exploratory and fact finding study following tools were used for the purpose. Interview schedule, Primary data were collected with the help of detailed self structured interview schedule comprising both open ended and close ended questions that cover areas such as personal demographic profile, family demographic profile, knowledge about HIV/AIDS which containing abbreviation treatment and sources of information about HIV/AIDS etc and many more like: myths about HIV/AIDS, attitude towards HIV/AIDS and current practices towards HIV/AIDS. It contains 51 items of both quantitative and qualitative nature of questions. (The scheduled questionnaire is presented as annexure – 1).

The interview schedule to collect data was tested with 15 respondents, in order to find out difficulties with regard to few questions in their understanding. Based on the outcome derived

from the pre-test, the interview schedule was modified accordingly for data collection. Of course the instructions were given before fill up the schedule i.e. the data collection was initiated from the first week of September 2013 and was completed in November 2013. The researcher personally met every respondent and collected data from them with their consent. All respondents consented to participate in the study and confidentiality has been maintained with data collected as it is only for research purposes.

e.g (This survey is being conducted purely for the purpose of research and I need your support and co-operation. There are questions about yourself, your family and about your knowledge, attitude and practices regarding HIV/AIDS. You need to put tick mark or yes / no and in some cases give subjective answers. Please be free, honest and true to yourself in answering these questions. There is no right or wrong answers. Your answers will be kept strictly confidential and only be used for research and only be used for research purpose. Your support and cooperation is highly solicited).

Table: 3.3 - Tools and Techniques used

Group	Aspects studies	Items of Questionnaire
Female adolescents and women in the age group of 13-17 years. Total No. of sample 400. 200 from college students and 200	1. Personal profile of the Respondents	3
	2. Family Demographic profile of the Respondents	6
	3. Migration status of the Respondents	3
	4. Knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS	
	i. Basic knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS	8
	ii Knowledge regarding channels of Transmission of HIV/AIDS	2
	iii Knowledge regarding causes of HIV/AIDS	6
	iv Knowledge regarding problems and preventions	2
	v. Knowledge regarding treatment of HIV/AIDS population	1
	vi. Knowledge regarding sources of information on HIV/AIDS	3
	5. Attitude of female adolescents towards HIV/AIDS	1
	i. Attitude towards HIV/AIDS as a Disease	
	ii. Positive attitude of female adolescents towards HIV/AIDS	
	iii. Negative attitude towards HIV/AIDS	
iv. Myths and misconceptions associated with HIV/AIDS	1	
6. Practice adopted towards HIV/AIDS by the female adolescents respondents	4	
i. Exposure and experience of sex	4	
ii. Interest in pornography	7	
iii. Proposal for seduction by the female adolescents		
iv. Acceptance of seduction by the female adolescents		
		51

Aspects of the Interview Schedule:

- 1 **Socio- demographic profile:** It consisted of 12 questions of which the adolescents age, belonging in the community, present study, domicile, families annual income, siblings, types of family, parental occupation, education and their status.
- 2 **Knowledge Regarding HIV/AIDS:** Under this heading the questions consisted of adolescents' complete knowledge of on HIV/AIDS i.e. the full form of HIV/AIDS; its nature, characteristics, transmission, causes, role of the virus, types and who are the vulnerable populations, infected people face the problems regarding AIDS, the location of the ICTC and the organizations working on this incurable disease sources of information regarding HIV/AIDS. Under this heading there were only two questions about the information regarding HIV/AIDS.
- 3 **Attitude towards HIV/AIDS:** **There** were questions about attitude of the adolescents towards the infections those were the general feeling about the infected persons and available treatment methods and issues of acceptance by the family and socie; attitude towards the disease.
- 4 **Practices Adopted:** In this connection the questions explored the sexual practices adopted by the adolescents in the age of curiosity. How they situation they handle sexual adventure and individual temptations. Practice adapted to present HIV/ AIDS infection was also explained.

3.7 ANALYSIS OF DATA:

All relevant collected data were tested and processed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Simple tables were made so as to make comparison between variables possible. Statistical tests such as t-test was applied so as to test the research hypothesis and thereby arrived at better conclusion. The analyzed data was presented in a scientific manner that gives better easy understanding to all concerned with this research.

Variables used in the present study are as follows-

Independent variables: Age of the respondents, Community, Class, Annual Income of the Family, domicile, Type of Family and Number of Siblings, migration status of the Parents and the causes of migration, parents educational and occupational status etc.

Dependent variables: Knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS i.e. Basic knowledge, Causes, Treatment, Vulnerable population the organization related to HIV/AIDS, Preventive strategies. Attitudes like the negative and positive attitudes towards disease and its victims towards the HIV/AIDS and the practices which they have adopted.

Limitations of the Study:

- While formulating the interview scheduled the researcher was bit puzzled whether she would be able to extract exact information from the respondents; since majority of them belong to rural areas where sex is considered to be a taboo.
- Since the parents of the respondents were not well educated enough they were not able to disseminate adequate information with regard to human sexuality to their children.
- As it was seen in the past when both the parents were working, it was the grand-parents who became the moral teachers to their grand children. Due to various

reasons the concept of joint family is losing its relevance and the norm of nuclear family is prevalent in the rural areas. Family value system and the concept of morality are degenerating.

- The respondents were shy and as it was observed from their body language they were bit hesitant to fill up the interview scheduled.
- While interacting with the teachers the researcher found that they too did not have adequate knowledge with regard to HIV/AIDS. Some teachers were scared that their school might be stigmatized if some students were found to have HIV infection, since the area is subject to high prevalence of HIV/AIDS.
- Though the Government is spending a huge amount of funds on HIV/AIDS awareness. Most of respondents do not know the real causes of HIV transmissions, prevention and treatment.
- The area where the research was conducted, the scholar found that the area being graded as “A” HIV/AIDS status; unfortunately the Government has not provided ICTC, ART centre or any counseling facilities with regard to HIV/AIDS.
- The respondents do not avail proper guidance neither from their parents nor from their teachers as a result they adopted trial and error method and go for various kinds of experimentation and land up with risky sexual behaviour; and which costs a lot to them in their latter life.
- The college campus which is situated beside the river bank is surrounded by lush bushes which indirectly encouraged for promiscuity behaviour to the students.
- Though the Government is providing certain special schemes to HIV infected persons like, Madhubau Pension Yojana due to fear of being identified as HIV+ and being discriminated by the members of the community.
- The children of HIV infected parents are not able to continue their studies in the schools because of the discrimination and touch me not attitude.

Due to HIV/AIDS related stigma and discrimination maximum numbers of people developed a feeling of guiltiness. The persons infected with HIV/AIDS eventually lost their prior social status and sometimes faced lots of isolation particularly in social functions

Chapter 4: Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the analysis, results and discussion of data collected from adolescent girls of selected form high schools and junior colleges. The purpose of analysis is to translate data to meaningful and interpretable form so that the research problem can be studied and tested to obtain good results. The analysis and interpretation of data in this study was based on the data collected through the demographic profile of responds and their knowledge, attitude and practice scales regarding HIV/AIDS. The findings of the study were done based on the objectives and hypotheses of the study. The results of the present research derived through the use of interview schedules. All the data were coded and transformed to a master data sheet for computer programming. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for descriptive statistics and for testing relationship between variables using tests of significance correlations test and the findings of the study is both descriptive and analytical. The results are analyzed using statistical (SPSS) done on total 308 variables, (independent variables 63 and dependent variable 245) of different dimensions. The results of the present study are explained and analyzed under the following headings:

1. Personal profile of the Respondents
 2. Family Demographic profile of the Respondents
 3. Migration status of the Respondents
 4. Knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS
 5. Attitude of female adolescents towards HIV/AIDS
 6. Practice adopted towards HIV/AIDS by the female adolescents respondents
- Summary of the Results

4.1 PERSONAL PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS:

Personal profile of a person shows the personal details of the respondents that herself is experienced in a way that are known from the general information of the respondents of the study. In the adolescent period 13 years to 17 years is a crucial age during which the adolescent need guidance and information on matters like HIV/AIDS. At this age they are also quite receptive to receive such information. Belongingness to social structure in the society is as old as man himself. Caste system has a direct influence on the self – esteem of the adolescents, social discrimination, ill treatment and equalities of opportunities play a greater role on individuals.

9th, 10th, 11th and 12th class is an educational system is an important stage. It is a very crucial and experiment period of adolescents life, they transit from puberty to adolescents and the different environment, the physical and psychological changes that occur during this age create great need for adjustment among adolescents. Hence this period of transition requires guidance and help in handling some issues, which include sexual health and HIV/AIDS education.

In this section demographic profile of 400 experiment group is described in terms of their age, community and class of study as shown in table number. 4.1 and figure no. 4.

Table No - 4.4: Personal profiles of the Respondents

Sl. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	t-test
1	Age			
	13 Years	48	12.0	8.98*
	14 Years	82	20.5	
	15 Years	96	24.0	
	16 Years	97	24.3	
17 Years	77	19.3		
2	Community			
	General	137	34.3	3.23*
	SC	39	09.8	
	ST	57	14.3	
OBC	167	41.8		
3	Class of Study			
	9th Class	126	31.5	6.81*
	10th Class	63	15.8	
	11th Class	121	30.3	
12th Class	90	22.5		

Note * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 4.2: (a) Graph showing the Age of respondents

Fig. 4.2(b) Distribution of respondents by their Community

Fig. 4.2: (c) Distribution of respondents by their Class of study

Nearly one fourth of the respondents (24.3%) belong to the age of 16 years. Whereas 24% of the respondents belong to 15 years of the age group. 20.5% of the respondents are in the age of 14 years, 19.3% of the respondents are in the age 17years and only 12% of the respondents are in the age only 13years. This reveals that all the respondents are in the adolescent phase of human growth and development. The respondents included in this study are distributed in between four different communities they are general caste, other backward caste (OBC), Schedule Caste (SC) and Schedule Tribe (ST). From the total respondents less than half of the respondents belong to Other Backward Caste (OBC); while 34.3% belong to the general community; 14.3% of the respondents belong to Schedule Tribe (ST) and only 9.8% of the respondents belong to the Schedule Caste (SC). This reveals the inclusion of all communities in this study area.

Understanding the class of study of the respondents is essential in any research particularly to find out their educational status. In this research the respondents are distributed among four different classes, they are standard 9th, 10th, 11th and 12th. More than

one fourth of the respondents (31.5%) are in their 9th class of study, while 30.3% of the respondents are in their 11th class of study and 22.5% of the respondents are in the 12th class of study and only 15.8% of the respondents are in the 10 class of study. This reveals that all the adolescents included in the study are enrolled in the mainstream education and this study ignores the dropout adolescents.

4.2. FAMILY DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS:

The demographic profile of the family reflects the general background of the sample in which she is living. Demographic variables also indicate the physical environment of the sample, which may has an influence on the knowledge, attitude and practices of the sample. The findings on family details were presented in table no 4.2 at that time questions were asked to get the valid information about their family income which related to parents occupational and educational status. The area where she lives is an environmental influence especially on one's behavior. The area of residence was classified as urban and rural. Type of families determines the autonomy and freedom of the members towards shaping the future of their children. Depending on the type of the family the samples, responses were grouped under two main types as joint or nuclear family, and also the family details are important to know the background of the respondents which show the number of siblings of the family.

Table No –4. 5: Family Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Sl. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	t-test
1.	<u>Family Income</u>			
	Less than 10000	131	32.8	4.63*
	10001 to 20000	81	20.3	
	20001 to 30000	62	15.5	
	30001 to 40000	38	9.5	
	40001 to 50000	48	12.0	
	50001 and above	40	10.0	
2	<u>Parent's Occupational Status</u>			
	Daily labours	106	26.5	2.67*
	Maid Servant	14	3.5	
	Small Business	196	49.0	
	Work in Govt.	84	21.0	
3	<u>Parent's Educational Status</u>			
	Illiterate	59	08.5	3.45*
	Primary	67	16.8	
	Secondary	83	20.8	
	HSC	165	41.3	
	Graduate	28	07.0	
	Above	23	05.8	
4	<u>Domicile</u>			
	Rural	258	64.5	3.44*

Sl. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	t-test
	Urban	142	35.5	
5	<u>Type of Family</u>			
	Joint Family	151	37.8	4.08*
	Nuclear Family	249	62.3	
6	<u>Number of Siblings</u>			
	One	24	6.0	3.83*
	Two	113	28.3	
	Three	143	35.8	
	Four	120	30.0	

Note * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 4.3: (a) Figure showing distribution of respondents by their annual family income

Fig. 4.3: (b) Distribution of respondents by their parent's occupation

Fig. 4.3: (c) Distribution of respondents by their parent's education

Fig. 4.3(d) Distribution of the respondents by their domicile

Fig. 4.3(e) Distribution of respondents by their family type

Fig. 4.3: (f) Distribution of respondents by the number of siblings in their house

It is observed from the above table-4.5 that more than one fourth of the respondents (32.8%) come from families having an annual income as less than Rs. 10,000/-, while 20.3% of the respondents hail from the families whose income is between 10,001 to 20,000/- and only 9.5% of the respondents come from families whose annual income is between 30,001 to 40,000 this reveals that majority of the respondents come from families whose annual income is less than the poverty line. While the study of adolescents and their knowledge and attitude it is essential to understand the parents occupational status.

The above Fig no-4.3(b) reveals that nearly half of the respondents' fathers (49%) are engaged into small business while 26.5% of them are daily labours and 21% of them are working in Government Sector and only 3.5% of the fathers are engaged into maid servants. Among the mothers of the respondents while less than half of them 43.8% of the engaged into daily labour and little more than one fourth of the respondents 26.3% are engaged into small business and 18.% of mothers are engaged into Govt. jobs only 12% of mothers are engaged as maid servants.

Parent's Educational status as the independent variable is critically important as the study deals with adolescents.

It is seen from the above table no.4.5 that among the fathers of the respondents less than (44%) are educated up to Higher Secondary; while 21.0% of them stopped their education at SSLC level and only 2.8% have completed their graduation; 5.8% of the fathers are post graduates, where 8.5% of the fathers are illiterate. Among the mothers educational status shows a little more than one fourth (26.8%) are educated up to higher secondary; while 23.5% are educated up to primary and little less than one fourth of them are illiterate and only 2.8% of them are post graduates. This reveals that women reaching up to higher education from the families of these adolescents are less than their counterparts. Studies dealing with knowledge attitude of adolescents required to have knowledge about the domicile of the respondents. The respondents in this study are distributed between rural and urban domicile. It is observed that a majority of the respondents (64.5%) belong to rural domicile; while only 35.5% of them are form urban areas. This reveals that majority of the respondents come from

areas where channels of communications for generating knowledge about HIV/AIDS is limited while the remaining respondents belong to the urban limit, where exposure to mass media is significant in generating knowledge among them.

Type of family plays a vital role in influencing the adolescents' knowledge, attitude and practices towards HIV/AIDS. It is observed from the table-4.5 that the respondents are distributed between nuclear and joint family system. Among the total respondents more than half of the respondents 62.3% are from nuclear family while 37.8% of the respondents are from joint family system. This reveals that the joint family system that prevails in our society is vanishing with the increase in nuclear family system. This may also be the impact of globalization. This can yield in increasing more myths as the parents may not allow much of their time to their children as they have to find for the family needs. Number of siblings in the family does have an impact on the adolescents' knowledge attitude and practices towards their sexuality. The below given chart describes the particulars about the number of siblings in the house of adolescents under study.

It is observed from the above table no 4.5 that 35.8 percent of the respondents are from families having three siblings, while 30 percent of the respondents are from families having four children and 28.3 percent of the respondents have two children as siblings and only 6 percent of the respondents have one child as sibling. This states that almost all the adolescents included in the study have one or more siblings in their home. Increased possibility for gaining more knowledge about HIV/AIDS, developing positive attitude towards sexuality can be available as all adolescents have siblings. Money earned by the family in a year through various sources like daily wages or kind, monthly salary, income from business, land property and other sources of income was considered as yearly income of the family.

4.2 MIGRATION STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Human migration is physical movement by humans from one area to another, sometimes over long distances are in large group. Migration is a positive phenomenon and if regulated and managed properly can reap in benefits for both the sending and recovering regions. Inter-state labours migration is an important feature of the Indian economy. Migration in Odisha has a long history. The Odia merchants had trade links with other parts of the country as well as within states during different seasons. The process of migration is deeply rooted in the socio-economic patterns of tribal as well as rural life style because they are illiterate. As the majority (64.5) of the respondents are from rural area of Aska and Bhanjanagar Block of Odisha for which they are illiterate sufficient livelihood incomes are that met for sustainability. 90% labours migrate to other state with eye-ful dream of better life but to the misfortune and bad name of the district they do return with HIV/AIDS. Sometimes unmarried young girls visited to their relative houses on special occasions and mean while attained the fair and festivals they do merry-making and engaged in other activities apart from their study at that time they were free from the attention of their parents.

Table No- 4. 6: Migration status of the Respondents

Sl. No	Migration status	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1.	<u>Migration Status of Parent's</u>			
	Migrant	54	13.5	1.36*
	Non-Migrant	346	86.5	
2.	<u>If Migrant, Migrate From:</u>			
	Village	254	63.5	2.10*
	Slum	106	26.5	
	Town	40	10.0	
3.	<u>Reasons of Migration:</u>			
	Displace due to Development Project	52	13.0	5.22*
	Refugee	30	7.5	
	Displaced due to Disaster	92	23.0	
	In search of Livelihood	101	25.3	
	Attracted Towards City	57	14.3	
	Displace Due to Communal Violence	39	9.8	
	Other reasons	29	7.3	

Fig. 4.4: Distribution of the respondents by their migration status of their families

It is seen from the above chart that more than three fourth of the respondents (86.5%) are from families whose parents are non-migrants and belong to native of Ganjam district, while the remaining 13.5% of the respondents are migrants and the maximum such as 63.5% migrated from the village areas in the same time little more than a quarter 26.5% migrated from slum areas whose occupations are daily labour and maid servant. Hence it is concluded that majority of the adolescents under the study are permanent residents from Ganjam district.

Reasons of Migration: From our study, it is observed that 13% displaced due to development of project, 23% due to disaster and 9.8% due to communal violence.

Whereas 7.5% of the respondents parents refugees. However one-fourth of the respondents migrated in search of their livelihood whereas 14% attracted towards city life, similarly 7.3% of them migrated for other reasons. Nearly one-fourth percent migrated, out of them 63.5% are from village area, and one-fourth (26.5%) are from slum area, only 10% reflected from town they are service holder.

4.3 KNOWLEDGE REGARDING HIV/AIDS:

Adolescent's knowledge about HIV/AIDS is important especially when it is considered a major challenge posing threat to their development. Lack of knowledge about HIV/AIDS regarding the basic knowledge about the curability nature of AIDS, causes, channels of transmissions, vulnerable population, risk behavior, treatment, the preventive measures and sources of information may lead to risky sexual behaviour resulting into HIV or the opportunistic infection. The table below describes about the knowledge prevailing among adolescent girls regarding HIV/AIDS.

4.4.1 Basic knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS: Basic knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS is a serious infection for which there is no cure till death. Each one of us has to protect ourselves from the deadly virus. That is why everyone should know about AIDS. The short form of AIDS – Acquired bears something you get from others; immune means capability of the human body to fight against disease; deficiency means shortage; reduction and syndromes means a group of diseases. HIV is the virus, which causes AIDS. HIV stands for Human Immune Deficiency virus. It is so small that we cannot see it through naked eyes. HIV infection remains till death and there is no medicine to get rid of HIV and cure AIDS. Prevention is the only cure. Thus everyone must test whether the virus is present in the body or not so, there are 30 nos. of integrated counseling testing centre (ICTC) is in each district of Odisha State. With the use of condoms a sex partner is 100% not sure to infection with HIV or other STD's; condoms provide protection from STD's also. In Hospital and medical shops condoms are available. Organization at the National and State level is responsible for the prevention of the spread of HIV, treatment and support to PLWHAs are UNICEF, INP + LEPR India, Action Aids, BISWA, Ashraya OSACS, etc. As adolescents' grow up in their life it is important that the need to develop knowledge about HIV/AIDS. Knowledge about the HIV/AIDS female adolescents is given below.

Table No - 4.7: Basic knowledge regarding HIV/AIDS

S. No	Knowledge	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Knowledge about Abbreviation of HIV:			
	Right answer	174	43.0	7.89*
	Wrong answer	226	57.0	
2	Abbreviation of AIDS :			
	Right answer	140	35.0	3.33*
	Wrong answer	260	65.0	
3	AIDS is Curable or Not:			
	Curable	136	34.0	2.42*
	Not-Curable	226	56.5	

	No Idea	38	9.5	
4	Location of ICTC:			
	Yes	60	15.0	1.42*
	No	340	85.0	
5	Availability of condoms:			
	Right answer	135	33.75	11.25*
	Wrong answer	153	38.25	
	No Idea	112	28.0	
6	National Level Organization involved in Preventing HIV & Support PLHIVs:			
	Right answer	108	27.0	2.17*
	Wrong answer	292	73.0	
7	Organization of state level Responsible for HIV/AIDS:			
	Right answer	309	77.0	1.82*
	Wrong answer	91	23.0	
8	A person infected with HIV/AIDS is called			
	HIV Positive	164	41.0	
	HIV Negative	101	25.3	
	HIV Neutral	40	10.0	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

The above table reflects on the knowledge about abbreviation of HIV/AIDS. Slightly more than two-fifth of the respondents had right knowledge about HIV abbreviation whereas 35% of them had right knowledge about AIDS abbreviation stand for in the same time almost 60% adolescents had wrong knowledge about HIV/AIDS abbreviation stand for. From the analysis it is concluded that a significant proportion of the adolescent girls do not have correct knowledge about the abbreviation of HIV/AIDS. This can lead adolescent girls to increased myths, practice risky sexual behavior that can result with HIV/AIDS infection ultimately causing burden to their life and society.

Regarding adolescent's knowledge about curability nature of AIDS; more than half of the respondents (56.5%) reported that AIDS cannot be cured, while slightly less than one third of the respondents (34.1%) reported that AIDS is curable and the remaining (9.5%) of the respondents reported of having no idea about the curable nature of AIDS. This reveals that a little less than half of the respondents don't have adequate knowledge about the curable nature of AIDS. One of the main services towards the prevention and treatment of persons infected and affected by HIV need counseling and testing offered by the Integrated Counseling and Testing Centre (ICTC) located in the Public Health facilities such as District Headquarter Hospital (DHH), Medical College Hospital, Primary Health Centers (PHCs), etc. About 34% of the respondents say that condoms are available in governments hospitals and only medical shops which is 100% correct answers where as 14% had

given a completely wrong answers, a good number of them (28%) had no idea about condom or its availability.

In the context of HIV/AIDS prevention refers to certain practices to be followed to stop the spread of the infection from one to another person. The national level and state level organization involved in preventing HIV and support positive people in Odisha. It comes out in the study that only 27% girls had right answer about the national level agencies involved in preventing and supports PLWHAs whereas nearly three-fourth (73%) of adolescent had wrong answer about the involvement of national level organization. However 77% adolescents had right answer about the organization of Odisha responsible for HIV/AIDS related programme. Only one fourth of the students had known about the organization responsible for HIV/AIDS. It is observed from the above table that only less than half of the respondents (41%) reported HIV infected persons as HIV positive while the remaining did not have knowledge about it and gave different status as HIV negative (25.25%) having no idea or neutral i.e. 33.75%, this reveals the poor knowledge about HIV infection.

4.4.2 Knowledge regarding channels of Transmission of HIV/AIDS: Knowledge regarding channels of transmission of HIV/AIDS new studies from across the globe established that the vast majority of young people have no idea how HIV/AIDS is transmitted or how to protect themselves from the disease. HIV/AIDS can be transmitted from person to person only if the body fluids like blood, semen and vaginal fluids come in contact with body fluids of an HIV infected or AIDS patients. The causing virus is not transmitted through the air, casual contact, by insects, by food or water. Important thing is to have correct knowledge, take essential precautions and save life from AIDS (UNAIDS 2002).

Several studies conducted on Indian adolescents have found that many male adolescents are sexually active and are likely to indulge in unsafe sexual activities making them vulnerable to STDs including HIV infections (Prabhakar 2009). Children vulnerable to HIV infection may fall under one or more of the following categories: street children, working children, children of sex worker, trafficked children, runaway children, abandoned children, sexually abused children, sexually active children, children using substances and orphans. Bi sexual men who have sex with men (MSM) and injecting drug user (IDUs), sex worker or migrants labourers. Sexual minorities including people who are lesbian, gay, bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT) and covers men, women and all those who don't identify either as men or women (that is transgender). Among the transgender are Hijras, Hijras are essentially biologically born males who don't not identified as men and prefer to identify as women (Rama Murti, 2008).

Table No - 4.8: Knowledge regarding channels of transmission of HIV/AIDS

S. No	Channel of Transmission	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1.	From one Person to Another			
	Mosquito Bite	69	17.0	3.06*
	Sharing Utensil Used by HIV Person	65	16.0	
	Sharing Dress Used by HIV Person	19	5.0	
	Sharing Toilet Used by HIV Person	30	7.5	
	Sexual Intercourse	123	31.0	
	Infected Mother to Child	37	9.0	
	Blood Transfusion with Infected Blood	26	6.5	
	Sharing of Infected Needles and Syringe	20	5.0	
	Kissing	04	1.0	
	Sneezing	07	2.0	
	Right answer	206	51.5	
	Wrong answer	194	48.5	
2.	Vulnerable population for HIV AIDS Infection			
	Migrant Worker	156	39.0	3.35*
	Low Status of Women	74	18.5	
	Prisoners	19	4.8	
	Adolescents	58	14.5	
	Street Children	29	7.3	
	All the Above	64	16.0	

Note:* 0.01 level of significant.

Fig. 4.5(a) Channel for HIV Transmission from one Person to Another

With regard to respondents' knowledge about the channels for HIV transmission, it is observed from the above table that 31% percent of them reported the channels of transmission through sexual intercourse, while 9.0 percent of them reported as infected mother to child, 6.5% of the respondents reported it to be transmission of infected blood. On the other hand 17 percent of the respondents reported mosquito bite as channel for HIV transmission and 16.3 percent reported as sharing utensils used by HIV person; 12.5% reported sharing dress and toilet used by HIV person. This shows that knowledge about mode of HIV transmission is still poor among the adolescent girls continuing their education in the urban based schools and colleges of Ganjam District.

The above table also shows the respondents knowledge about different vulnerable groups to HIV infection. It is seen that 39 percent of the respondents perceived migrant workers to be the vulnerable groups while 18.5% of the respondents reported that women living in low status as the vulnerable groups and this reveals that the respondents do not have adequate knowledge about the groups of people vulnerable to be infected by HIV. Whereas only 16% results have given by the respondents and which is the hundred percent right answers.

HIV does not spread like a cold and is therefore relative difficult to catch. No one case has been reported of HIV being transmitted by contact with air, tears, sweat, shaking hands, hugging, coughing, sneezing, using swimming pool, toilet seats, sharing towels, bed, linen, utensils, being bitted by mosquitoes or other animals, or any other form of everyday contact. Saliva, uncontaminated by blood, has not been implicated as a mechanism of transmission.

4.4.3 Knowledge regarding causes of HIV/AIDS HIV-1 and HIV-2 both cause HIV infection and AIDS. Most AIDS cases in India are due to HIV-1. Human Immuno deficiency virus enters the human body and gradually damages the immune system that fights infection and diseases. The immune system becomes less and less capable to protect against illness and with the result even minor infections can lead to serious life threatening conditions. Typically, HIV lives in an infected person's body for months or years before any signs and symptoms of illness (AIDS) appear.

Poverty is often cited as a cause of child prostitution lack of information is the way and means of HIV transmission leads to vulnerability of people to get HIV infection. Biological factors another aspect to get HIV infection. Biologically women are twice more likely to become infected with HIV through unprotected heterosexual intercourse with men. Apart from this social stigma and discrimination lack of awareness, psychological harassment leads to HIV infection.

Table No - 4.9: Knowledge regarding causes of HIV/AIDS

S. No	Activities spreading HIV AIDS	Frequency N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	✓ Having Sex with an Infected Person with Condom	193	48.0	3.39*
	✓ Penetrative Sex with Multiple Partners	35	9.0	
	✓ Oral Sex with an Infected Person	30	7.5	
	✓ Sharing an Unsterilized Needle	87	22.0	
	✓ Baby in the womb of infected mother and breast feeding to her baby	34	8.5	
	✓ Anal sex without Condom	21	5.0	
	➤ Right answer	207	52.0	
➤ Wrong answer	193	48.0		
2	Bacteria/parasites/virus spreading HIV/AIDS:			
	• Gods Anger	5	1.3	1.43*
	• Bacteria	35	8.8	
	• Parasites	12	3.0	
	• Virus (right answer)	318	79.5	
	• Wrong	52	13.1	
	• No idea	30	7.5	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

It is observed from the above table that little less than half of the respondents (48.3%) reported that they perceived penetrative sex with multiple partners as risk behaviour leading to HIV, while 21.8% of them perceived sharing an unsterilized needle to be the risk behaviour for contracting HIV infection. Nearly 10% girls have wrong knowledge about the causes. Whereas more than 90% of adolescents having right knowledge about the causes of HIV/AIDS.

It is inferred from the above table that a considerable majority of the respondents (79.5%) reported virus to be cause of HIV infection which is correct answer where as others reported it wrongly as bacteria (8.8%) again few of them reported HIV/AIDS spread because of god's anger or parasites and 7.5 percent of them did not have any knowledge about it.

4.4.4 Knowledge regarding problems and prevention of HIV/AIDS

Knowledge regarding problems and prevention of knowledge about health and health related issues plays a vital role in maintaining health and preventing disease. HIV/AIDS is an epidemic that stands to destroy the human race on earth. This is an outcome of the risky behavior exhibited by human beings. During the beginning years of its identification, people thought AIDS was a disease striking mainly men. Later it was assessed to be a myth and in reality women are at higher risk of being infected by AIDS as well as increasingly bearing the burden of its impact.

Stigma and discrimination are very common among PLWHAs to family function many female formed to do extra work because of their HIV positive status, at last their confidentiality broken and frequent loss of income in the service sector. In Kendrapara and Jagatsighpur districts of Odisha there are about 72 couples in the past 12 months, two dozens of women have had abortions because they were afraid of passing infection on to their children; the abortions were conducted in conformity with the medical termination of pregnancy Act, 1972. In recorded statements, the forced women expressed their willingness to abort their pregnancies (Samaj 1.12. 2011). Since misconception and ill-conceived notion about HIV/AIDS are common in rural areas some of the couples who are HIV carriers are scared of being branded as AIDS patients. There are instances of AIDS patient here being ostracized. Their family members also are ostracized as their neighbors maintain distance in their relationship.

The Government provides free treatment and requisite medicines to the patients but many feel reluctant to come up openly to avail this medicine due to social stigma and security. Private source of medicines which are expensive in Indian companies as the requisite raw materials for manufacturing these medicines to treat the dreaded disease come from abroad and that is quite expensive and not cost effective (Newmann, S. & Sarin, P., 2006) the impact of AIDS on children continuous to count in various part of the world. Currently children under 15 years account for one in six AIDS related to deaths worldwide and one in seven new HIV infections after illness and death itself the harshest impact on children is the loss of their parents' affection, support and protection; separation from siblings is frequent as orphans from large families are often send to live in different households. In addition to the psychological trauma suffered by these children poverty and social dislocation as well as stigma and discrimination may also be added to their woes and in turn increases their vulnerability to HIV. Children alone face the brunt of dread disease their lives are cut short before they begin to understand the world for that neither what has happened to them, while some other live longer only to suffer worst of social ostrasization and humiliation .

Members belonging to the families of HIV/AIDS from the urban clusters of different districts of Odisha refused to receive the monthly pension scheme meant for such infected

people. The fear of getting identified and targeted and the consequent social stigma has forced the targeted beneficiaries to shun the plan. In the context of HIV/AIDS, prevention refers to certain practices to be followed to stop the spread of the infection from one to another person. It includes the methods used to protect one's own health and the health of others in the family and in the community. It also refers to the steps undertaken 'to halt and reverse' the infection by government or other organizations as public health policies.

Table No -4.10: Knowledge regarding problems and prevention of HIV/AIDS

S.No	Problems / preventions	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Problem face by HIV Positive people at Home & Society			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Isolation • Discrimination • Stigma • Hatred • Humiliation • Loss of Job • Poor Health • Financial Constraints • Depression • Suicidal tendency 	118 74 20 93 10 12 43 6 4 20	29.5 18.5 5.0 23.0 2.5 3.0 11.0 1.5 1.0 5.0	3.09*
2	Preventive measures against HIV /AIDS Infection			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wash Sex Organ with Soap after Sex • Sex Only with Young Person • Live in Clean Environment • Avoid Sex with Sex Workers • Confine Sex Only within Marriage • Use Condom for Safe Sex • Be faithful to Single Partner • Abstain from Sex • Never Share Needles use by another person <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Right answer ➤ Wrong answer 	67 8 122 57 42 46 13 23 22 203 197	16.75 2.0 30.5 14.25 10.5 11.5 3.0 6.0 5.5 50.5 49.5	3.42*

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 4.5(b): Mental, Physical and Social Problems of PLWHAS

Evaluation of the 400 respondents which showed that 29.5% reflects isolation faced by HIV+ people at home and society, only one percent blamed depression, 1.5% financial constraints, 5.5% loss of job and humiliation, where as little more than a quarter (28%) hatred and compel suicidal tendency. Children alone face the brunt of dreaded diseases of their lives are cut short before they begin to understand the world after being aware HIV positive status. In the same time 5% do suffer stigma towards HIV positive at home and society.

Fig. 4.6 : Knowledge about Preventive Measures from getting infected HIV/AIDS

It is interesting to note that only a very small portion of the respondents have the knowledge specific of the most effective way of prevention, namely, “Be faithful to Single Partner”, “Abstain from Sex” and “Use of Condom for Safe Sex” (13.8%, 5.8% and 11.5% respectively).

At the same, it is to be noted that a good number of them (30.5%) think that “Living in a Clean Environment” alone could be effective in the prevention, whereas a sizable number (16.8%) think “Wash Sex Organ with Soap after Sex” will prevent HIV infection, and some of them (14.3%) know that “Avoiding Sex with Sex Workers” will prevent from getting infected.

4.5 Knowledge Regarding Treatment of HIV/AIDS Population: Knowledge regarding treatment of HIV/AIDS population, currently there is no way to get rid of entire viral load once a person is infected. However, new medicines called Anti Retroviral Therapy (ART) can slow the damage that HIV causes to the immune system reduce the viral load and increase the longevity and improve the quality of life of the PLWHAs. Doctors are well informed now at treating the illnesses that are caused by HIV infection. Many people now consider HIV infection manageable, long-term illness (OSACS 2014). Adolescent girl’s knowledge about treatment availability for HIV infected person is given in the table below.

Table No - 4.11: Knowledge regarding treatment of HIV/AIDS Population

S.No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	‘t’ Test
1	The Treatment Available for HIV Infected Person			
	Traditional	30	7.5	3.55*
	Allopathic Medicines	93	23.3	
	Chemotherapy	16	4.0	
	Anti Retroviral therapy	63	15.8	
	➤ Right answer	63	15.8	
	➤ Wrong answer	139	34.7	
	➤ No idea	198	49.5	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 4.7: Treatment available for HIV infected persons

It is observed from the above table that nearly half of the respondents (49.5%) reported that they did not have any idea about the availability of treatment for HIV infected person, while (23.3%) of the respondents reported that allopathic medicines are available to treat HIV infected person and only (15.8%) of the respondents had right knowledge and reported Antiretroviral Therapy as the treatment for HIV infected person. This reveals that a major proportion of the female adolescents do not have adequate knowledge about treatment available to treat a person infected by HIV.

4.6 Knowledge Regarding Sources of Information about HIV/AIDS; Knowledge regarding sources of information regarding HIV/AIDS from the previous study efforts was made to understand the current information needs to adolescents on sexual and reproductive health needs. Adolescents are very curious to know about reproductive and sexual health issues. Young people thinking and behaviour are influenced not only by their family and peers but also by their exposure to mass media. It has been established that adolescents are less likely than people over age 20 to use contraceptive methods. Reasons for this include lack of information and misinformation, poor access, which lack of ability to negotiate. The significance of reaching out to adolescents in rural areas by them gets partial and incorrect information through movies. Also most of them got married in their adolescent stage without proper information on sex and sexuality. Awareness is the safest way to avoid HIV/AIDS. HIV/AIDS are not taboo words anymore. The treat of the pandemic is a real one. This has gradually been penetrating into the hinterlands. The need for awareness about it can hardly be over emphasized. “Filon” being the most popular medium in India, however did not pick up the subject for any serious treatment.

It is worse for the adolescents who hail in the rural areas as they do not have any access to information, training and awareness programmes except for some information which they gain through the mass media. AIDS education in school has been taken up to sensitize the students from Class – IX onwards. The electronic media, print media and other field based organizations of the Government have been involved in awareness generation on HIV/AIDS. Counselor had been trained in various states at the grass root level under the

National Training Programme of NACO. Although Government has been spreading a lot of money on HIV/AIDS awareness programmes, people were not that much aware in the rural areas, where the HIV/AIDS is more widespread.

It is high time that we introspect our AIDS awareness programmes and realize that there is an urgent need to seek other types of people centric media campaign available to the rural community.

Adolescent girls acquired knowledge about the incurable disease is given in the table below:

Table No - 4.12: Knowledge regarding sources of Information about HIV/AIDS

Sl. No	Sources of knowledge	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Sources of information from the individuals of service sectors:			
	• Doctor	306	76.5	1.37*
	• Integrated Counseling and Testing Centre ICTC	58	14.5	
	• Teachers	9	2.3	
	• Parents	4	1.0	
	• Friends	6	1.5	
	• Positive Network	17	4.3	
2	Source Enable to Understand HIV/AIDS:			
	• Electronic Media	45	11.0	2.26*
	• Health Care Professional	99	25.0	
	• Public Awareness Programme	128	32.0	
	• Print Media	11	3.0	
	• School	80	20.0	
	• Parents	8	2.0	
	• Friends	4	1.0	
	• None	25	6.0	
	➤ Right answer	375	94.0	
	➤ Wrong answer	25	6.0	
3	Through participation of events Conducted by School/College on HIV/AIDS Awareness			
	➤ Seminar on HIV / AIDS	42	10.5	2.33*
	➤ Awareness Generation Camp on HIV/AIDS	50	12.5	
	➤ Rally Campaigning HIV/AIDS	52	13.0	
	➤ Film Show on HIV/AIDS	27	6.8	
	➤ No such Programme on HIV/AIDS	229	57.3	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 4.8(a): Source of knowledge about HIV/AIDS

Fig. 4.8(b): Participation in awareness programme on HIV/AIDS

It is interesting to note that nearly one fourth i.e. 23.5% of the respondents have sources of knowledge from other sources like teachers, parents, friends, positive net works and Integrated Counseling and Testing Centre (ICTC) out of them (14.5%) students, reported ICTC was the sources of information from the individuals of services sector. However at the same, it is to be noted that a good number of them i.e. 76.5% acquired information from doctor.

It is understood from the above table that 32 percent of the respondents gained their sources of knowledge about HIV/AIDS through public awareness programmes, while 24.8% of the respondents obtained knowledge through source as health care professionals, 20 percent of the respondents derived their knowledge about HIV/AIDS through the source school and 11.3 percent obtained knowledge about HIV/AIDS through electronic media which includes television, radio and internet. It is also derived that only 2 percent of the respondents obtained knowledge about HIV/AIDS from their parents.

From the above table it is inferred that more than half of the respondents (57.3%) have never participated in any of the awareness generation programmes. Further the table also reveals that (13 percent) of the respondents have generated awareness through their participation in the rally, campaigning; while (12.5%) of them are aware of HIV/AIDS through their participation in the awareness generation camp and (10.5%) of the respondents are aware of HIV/AIDS through seminar and only (6.8%) of the respondents are aware of HIV/AIDS through their participation in staged film shows. This reveals that the opportunity for participation in the awareness generation programmes on HIV/AIDS is very limited that a considerable majority have not participated in any of the awareness generation programmes on HIV/AIDS.

5. ATTITUDE OF FEMALE ADOLESCENTS TOWARDS HIV/AIDS

Adolescents form a sizeable proportion of the population. The National Family health Survey (NFHS – 3), 1998-99, found approximately 22% India's population comprise of the 15-19 age group. Adolescence is the most volatile period of life, with the children attempting to shed parental restriction while seeking new identity or making new contacts. Peers and friends from opposite sex become more important who seem to exert more influence than the previous role models (parents and teachers). Experimentation with new friends, new behaviour with drugs, and even sex, pose additional challenges for adolescents and parents alike. Girls suffer more acute and dramatic physical, mental and emotional change with little support forthcoming from parents, families or teachers. Because of their greater vulnerability, they may fall prey to exploitation during this period, which may culminate into an unwanted pregnancy or a sexually acquired disease including HIV. Attitude and behavior surrounding sexuality carry profound meaning for men and women in every society and affect the quality of life in fundamental ways. In some cultures ideologies of sexuality stress female resistance, male aggression and mutual antagonism in the sex act (Kiska and Standing 1989).

The study attempted to elicit the adolescents attitude and practices regarding various aspects of sex and sexuality, such as attitude towards relationship with opposite sex, perception about conception and virginity, exposure to pornography literature, sexual experiences, condom use, awareness about mode of transmission as well as preventative measures of HIV/AIDS and safe sex. During adolescence, the individuals face a wide range and variety of emotions. These include both Positive emotions like love, happiness, joy as well as negative emotions like, sadness, depression, unhappiness, anxiety. In addition, feelings of anger, rebellion and protest also emerge. Interestingly, emotions of loyalty patriotism and sacrifice for the nation also develop during adolescence (IGNO, 2011).

To understand the attitude of adolescents towards people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHAs) The respondents in this study were asked about how far they approved the positive attitude, negative attitude and misconception about the HIV/AIDS disease and positive people.

Table No – 5.13: Attitude towards HIV/AIDS as a Disease

Sl. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	HIV/AIDS is a Punishment given by God for Immoral Behaviour			
	• Agree	105	26.3	3.99*
	• Disagree	200	50.4	
	• Not Sure	95	23.8	
2.	Feel Uneasy to Discuss about Sex and HIV / AIDS			
	• Agree	164	13.3	3.65*
	• Disagree	157	39.5	
	• Not Sure	79	27.5	
3.	No need to know HIV if you are leading a good life?			
	• Agree	156	39.0	
	• Disagree	215	54.0	
	• Not Sure	29	7.3	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 5.9: Attitude towards HIV/AIDS

HIV/AIDS is “God’s punishment for immorality.” About 27% of the respondents either strongly agree or just agree with the perception that HIV infection is a punishment from God for one’s immoral behaviour. Almost 50% of them disagree with this perception, and about 23% of them are not sure about level of agreement or disagreement with this perception.

“Feel uneasy to discuss about Sex and HIV”. Good many of the respondents (42%) are in agreement with this statement, whereas a sizable number of them (39%) disagree with the statement. And nearly 17% of them are not sure about their feeling towards sex and HIV.

“No need to know about HIV/AIDS, if morality is practiced”: about 39% of the respondents feel aligned to this statement, but the majority of them (54%) do not agree with this statement. A small number of them (7%) feel unsure about their stand in relation to this statement. They might least bothered about the disease and its consequences.

Table No-5.14: Positive attitude of Female Adolescents towards HIV/AIDS Victims

1.	Sex Education for Adolescents is Important in Reducing Risky	F	(%)	
	Agree	261	65.0	
	Disagree	84	21.0	
	Not Sure	55	13.8	
2.	I Feel That HIV Infected Person Should Treated Like Other			
	Agree	199	49.5	
	Disagree	139	35.0	
	Not Sure	62	15.5	
3.	Condom can prevent spread of HIV			
	Yes	155	39.0	
	No	208	52.0	
	No idea	37	9.0	

4.	Faithful to one partner will help in the prevention of HIV			
	Agree	200	50	
	Disagree	111	28.0	
	Not Sure	89	22.0	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

The majority of the respondents about (65%) do strongly agree with the statement “Sex Education can reduce risky behavior”; whereas (14%) were not sure about it, in the same time half of the respondents understand that using condom can prevent HIV, but (35%) do disagree about the statement. Though the majority of them (52%) said HIV infected person can lead a normal life, however (39%) of them had positive attitude towards them infect (9%) have no idea about the statement. About (50%) of the respondents had strongly agreed that “Being faithful to one’s own spouse help in prevention of HIV” however (28%) of them disagree and (22%) of them were not sure about the statement.

Table No-5.15: Negative attitude towards HIV/AIDS Victim

Sl. No	Variable	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	
1	I Feel Scared About Having Sex With My Life Partner			
	Agree			
	Disagree	123	31.0	
	Not Sure	165	41.3	
		112	28.0	

2	Strongly Feel that HIV Spread through Truck Driver & Sex Worker			<p style="text-align: center;">HIV Spread Through</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>31.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>54.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Not Sure</td> <td>14.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	31.6	Disagree	54.5	Not Sure	14.0
Response	Percentage											
Agree	31.6											
Disagree	54.5											
Not Sure	14.0											
3	I feel that a Person Infected by HIV Cannot Lead a Normal Life			<p style="text-align: center;">Can't Lead a Normal Life</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>42.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>41.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Not Sure</td> <td>17.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	42.0	Disagree	41.0	Not Sure	17.0
Response	Percentage											
Agree	42.0											
Disagree	41.0											
Not Sure	17.0											
4	Avoid of Person Infected with HIV			<p style="text-align: center;">Avid Persons</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>37.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>45.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Not Sure</td> <td>18.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	37.0	Disagree	45.0	Not Sure	18.0
Response	Percentage											
Agree	37.0											
Disagree	45.0											
Not Sure	18.0											

5	<p>Feel Frightened to Meet any HIV Infected person</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Not Sure</p>	<p>167</p> <p>147</p> <p>86</p>	<p>42.0</p> <p>36.5</p> <p>19.0</p>	<p>Frightened to meet</p> <p>■ Agree ■ Disagree ■ Not Sure</p>
6	<p>Poor People are More Vulnerable to HIV infection</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Not Sure</p>	<p>134</p> <p>153</p> <p>104</p>	<p>36.8</p> <p>38.0</p> <p>26.0</p>	<p>Poors are Vulnerable</p> <p>■ Agree ■ Disagree ■ Not Sure</p>
7	<p>All HIV Positive People Should be Killed</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Not Sure</p>	<p>81</p> <p>255</p> <p>64</p>	<p>20.0</p> <p>64.0</p> <p>16.0</p>	<p>+ People should be Killed</p> <p>■ Agree ■ Disagree ■ Not Sure</p>

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

This study reveals that less than half (41%) of the respondents disagree about their feeling towards having sex, but 31% of them agree to have sex with their life partner. In the same time little more than a quarter (28%) have neutral answer or not sure about the statement. More than half of the respondents disagree about the infection that spread through truck driver or sex worker. Whereas (31.6%) of them feel that truckers and sex workers are the carrier of HIV virus. Almost same (agree 42% disagree 41%) of the students feel that the infected person can't lead normal life. Whereas 17% of them are not sure about the positive people and 45% of them agree that they should be avoided to meet. However 18% are not sure what to do with them.

About 42% were fear to meet HIV+ people and 36.5% were not fear to meet with them 21.5% have neutral feeling for them only 26% of those adolescents girls were not sure about the statement that "Poor people are prone to get HIV infection" whereas 36% agree and a similar proportion 38% disagree with the statement. "PLHIVs should be killed": about 63.8% of the respondents either disagree or strongly agree with this statement. Nearly 20% agree or strongly agree whereas 16% were not sure of what to feel towards the statement.

4.5.4 Myths and Misconceptions associated with HIV/AIDS: The broad introduction on myths and misconceptions of HIV/AIDS and STDS deals effectively with the inaccurate information which is quite often believed and passed on without the authenticity of the source. In this light, you have to focus on the various routine activities that are done with the anticipation of getting infected by HIV/AIDS person out of their fear, ignorance, anxiety, etc. Myth and misconception prevailing about HIV/AIDS, sometimes brings about negative response to the extent of cases reported in the newspapers on disowning persons by their own family members.

There is still no clear picture evolved about the concept of "safer sex" within the context of HIV/AIDS among high- risk groups and general population. Abstinence from sexual activities before marriage and being faithful to his/her spouse after marriage is the tradition of living in Indian context believe like quarantine, circumcision, level of education, faithful observance of religious prayer, good food practice and modern way of living. Healthy and wealthy living style cannot be a criterion for awareness and cannot protect HIV/AIDS. They need proper knowledge and practice (AFE-1-2001). Adolescents are many times guided by their peer members and as a result of this myths stem out of them in many ways. The below given table shows respondents Knowledge about the statement 'sex with virgin girl can cure HIV'.

Table No – 5.16: Myths and Misconception associated with HIV/AIDS

S. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Sex with virgin girl cure HIV :			
	• Agree	48	12.0	2.33*
	• Disagree	241	60.3	
• No idea	110	27.5		
2	Sex with Young Boy Will Not Cause HIV:			
	• Agree	45	11.3	2.34*
	• Disagree	239	59.8	
• No idea	115	28.8		
3.	No need to know HIV if you are leading a good life?			
	• Agree	156	39.0	2.42*
	• Disagree	215	54.0	
• Not sure	29	7.3		
4	Faithful observance of religious prayer protect HIV infection			
	• Agree	106	26.5	2.61*
	• Disagree	232	58.0	
• Not sure	62	15.5		

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 5.10: Myth on HIV/AIDs

It is observed from the above table that more than half of the respondents (60.3%) disagreed to this statement and had the correct knowledge that having sex with a virgin girl cannot cure HIV, while 27.8 percent of them reported of having no idea and 12 percent of the respondents agreed that sex with a virgin can cure HIV. This reveals that respondents' who disagreed and had no idea does carry myths about sex which may be out of their poor knowledge. Adolescents are many times guided by their peer members and as a result of this myths stem out of them in many ways. The below given table shows respondents Knowledge about the statement 'sex with a young boy does not cause HIV. It is seen from the above table that more than half of the respondents (59.8%) disagreed to the statement that sex with a young boy will not cause HIV and 28% of them had no knowledge about it and this reveals that still there is an imbalance prevailing to their knowledge base. Adolescent girls' knowledge about HIV infected person leading a normal life can help in reduction of stigma and myths. The below table shows the respondents knowledge about HIV infected person leading normal life. It is observed from the above table that more than half of the respondents 52 percent reported that a HIV infected person cannot lead a normal life while 38.8 percent of the respondents reported that HIV infected person can lead a normal life and the remaining 9.3% of the respondents did not have any knowledge about HIV infected person leading normal life. This reveals that a considerable majority did not agree to the statement and few of them had no idea about HIV infected person leading a normal life. This can lead to increased stigma and discrimination among respondents.

6. PRACTICE ADOPTED TOWARDS HIV/ AIDS BY THE FEMALE ADOLESCENTS RESPONDENTS:

Human sexual activities or human sexual behavior refers to the manner in which humans experience and express their sexuality. People engage in a variety of sexual acts from time to time, and for a wide variety of reasons. Sexual activity normally results in sexual arousal and physiological changes in the aroused person, some of which are pronounced while others are more subtle. Sexual activity also includes conduct and activities which are intended to arouse the sexual interest of oneself and/or another. Adolescence can be seen as a time when many sexual attitudes and reactions that were rehearsed in childhood begin to reveal their true meaning. Most important of all, it is a period in which experimental and exploratory sex play turns into purposeful adult sexual behavior. In this context the study attempted to know the different sexual activities the respondents indulged in. Misconceptions and misbeliefs on sexual issues are not uncommon among adolescents. Sometimes lack of adequate information and opportunities prompt these young people to turn to literature (often pornographic), experimentation with prostitutes, friends or relatives of opposite sex and at times the same sex, and observation of sexual activities and masturbation. Many studies reflect that female fantasies are largely romantic and emotional in nature. There is often a tendency to assume that the members of the opposite sex thinks and feels the same as oneself. This assumption, which is far removed from reality, results in a lot of confusion, misunderstandings and tensions, especially, during the process of dating.

Sex and relationships is still a taboo subject between parents and teenage daughters, despite access to formal education and wider exposure to the realities of life through media. Hence there have been efforts to provide proper education on matters related to human

sexuality and reproductive health through the educational system. In this background it is important to assess the level of understanding of HIV/AIDS and to ascertain the attitude towards persons living with HIV/AIDS. Therefore, 14 statements related to sex education, sexual practice, and PLHIVs were given to the respondents to reflect their attitude on the basis of a 5-point scale.

Table No – 6.17: Exposure and experience of sex

S. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1.	Hugging a Person of Opposite Sex			
	Yes	185	46.3	13.32*
No	215	53.8		
2	Kissing A Person of Opposite Sex			
	Yes	185	46.3	13.32*
No	215	53.8		
3	Fondling Genitals of a Male Person			
	Yes	172	43.0	7.14*
No	228	57.0		
4.	Sleeping Together with a Male Person			
	Yes	160	40.0	5*
No	240	60.0		
5	Masturbation			
	Yes	194	48.5	33.33*
No	206	51.5		
6	Watching Pornography			
	Yes	184	46.0	12.5*
No	216	54.0		
7	Reading Sex Books/Magazine			
	Yes	219	54.8	10.52*
No	181	45.3		

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 6.11: Different Sexual Activities

The above table indicates the number of persons in different sexual activities. It is observed that a majority of the respondents (54.8%) have taken to reading sex books or magazines. A good number of them (48.5%) have indulged in masturbation, while kissing, hugging, fondling genitals of a person of the opposite sex, and watching pornography have been the activities of many of them with the range of 43% - 46%. Sleeping together with a person of opposite sex was also seen as an activity mentioned by 40% of the respondents.

4.6.2 Interest in Pornography: Pornography is explicit sexual writing or visual materials, often considered obscene, most societies have always regarded any disturbance of pornography as potentially dangerous and corrupting. Particularly to young people they may believe that whatever is shown in pornography is the real thing and try to imitate them in real life.

Table No – 6.18: Interest in Pornography

S. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Have You Ever Seen any Pornography or Blue Film			
	Yes	67	16.8	1.50*
	No	333	83.3	
2	If Yes what is the Frequency of Watching			
	Daily	86	21.5	6.03*
	Weekly	89	22.3	
	Monthly	76	19.0	
	Occasionally	149	37.3	
3.	Habit of Reading Pornography Book or Magazine			
	Yes	83	20.8	

	No	317	79.3	1.70*
4	If Yes, What is the frequency			
	Very Frequent	114	28.5	9.11*
	Frequent	124	31.0	
	Occasionally	162	40.5	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

4.6.3 Proposal for seduction by the Female Adolescents: A few recent studies indicate, however that the sexual practices are not uncommon in both educated and uneducated and in both urban and rural population. In fact, sexual experiences are important elements of being an adult and young people do not practice problems that may come in future, especially when they concern them as sexual beings. In the recent study area a minimum girls reported having penetrative sex and experienced touching of private parts. Such types of sexual experiences were more reported among out of school girls than those attending schools. Penetrative sex was experienced by them and reported experienced of touching body parts was also higher among out of school girls (Khan 2005).

Adolescents are the age when physical and psychological changes occur in individuals. It is also found that incidences of abuse happen to adolescents in many ways. Experiences of being tried by someone for sex are also an indication of experiencing abuse during adolescents. The table given below shows the experiences of adolescent girls being tried for sex.

Table No-6.19: Proposal for seduction by the Female Adolescents

S. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Have You Ever Tried by Someone to Have Sex?			
	Yes	40	10.0	1.25*
	No	360	90.0	
2.	If Yes, Specify the Relation of That Person Who Tried for Sex			
	Person Known to me of same Sex	26	6.5	1.41*
	Person Unknown to me of same Sex	19	4.8	
	Person Known to me of Opposite Sex	26	6.5	
	Person Unknown to me of Opposite Sex	23	5.8	
	Have Never been tried by Someone for Sex	306	76.5	
3.	Forced by Someone in the Following manner			
	Fondled Genitals Forcefully	32	8.0	1.39*
	Caress Breast	27	6.8	
	Stimulated my Sexual Desire	21	5.3	
	Force me & Penetrated to my Vagina	6	1.5	
	Motivated to have sex with someone else	9	2.3	
	I have never been forced	305	76.3	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 6.12: Manners of forced sex

It is observed from the above table no. 4.19 that a vast majority of the adolescent girls reported of not having been tried by someone for having sexual intercourse, while 10 percent of the respondents reported of having been tried by someone for having sexual intercourse. To a question whether the respondents were ever forced into sex, about 76% replied that they had no any such experience, but 95 respondents of them (24%) admitted that they had the experience of forced sex. Regarding the manner of the 'forced sex', these 95 respondents mentioned the specific manner as fondling the genitals forcefully (8%), caressing the breasts (6.8%), stimulating sexual desire (5.3%), penetrative sex (1.5%) and forcing to have sex with another person (2.3%). This reveals that risky sexual encounters continue to exist among adolescent girls.

4.6.4 Acceptance of Seduction by the Female Adolescents

Majority of the respondents have heard of sexual health, but did not practice the sex, or discuss about the sexual matter. The study revealed that maximum adolescent have no knowledge on how their reproductive system functions and how pregnancy occurs. Though there had been restriction laid by the family after they attend puberty, the girls have reported of intimate sexual relationships. While the number of respondents who had reported of having sexual relationships is less, it is worthy to make a note of it. The respondents have conveyed that it started as from neighbours and relatives which later became a practice.

Table No- 6.20: Acceptance of Seduction by the Female Adolescents

S. No	Variables	Frequency (N=400)	Percentage (%)	't' Test
1	Ever Had Sexual Inter Course with a Person Well Known to You			
	Yes	38	9.5	1.23*
	No	362	90.5	
2	If Yes, Approximately how Many Times			
	Only Once	144	36.0	

	Twice	101	25.3	6.30*
	Thrice	72	18.0	
	Many Times	83	20.8	
3	What Preventive Measure Used During Sex With Well Known Person			
	Traditional Method	21	5.3	1.67*
	Safe Day Method	25	6.3	
	Tablet to Prevent Conception	22	5.5	
	Withdrawal at Climax	8	2.0	
	Condom	17	4.3	
	Never used Anything	47	11.8	
	Never had Sexual Intercourse	260	65.0	
4	Specify the Total Number of well Known Person You Had Sex			
	One	127	31.8	10.45*
	Two	100	25.0	
	Three	88	22.0	
	Many Times	85	21.3	
5.	Have You Ever Had Sexual Intercourse with a Unknown Person			
	Yes	42	10.5	
	No	358	89.5	
6.	If Yes, Approximately how Many Times Specify			
	Only Once	120	30.0	4.80*
	Twice	67	16.8	
	Thrice	64	16.0	
	May times	149	37.3	
7.	Can You Specify Total Unknown Person You had Sex			
	One	130	32.5	9.91*
	Two	90	22.5	
	Three	87	21.8	
	Many Times	93	23.3	

Note: * 0.01 level of significant

Fig. 4.13: Sexual intercourse with a person of opposite sex

Almost 16% of the respondents said that they had sexual intercourse with a male person, whereas the remaining 85% said that they had no experience of sexual intercourse.

Fig. 4.14: Preventive measures used to avoid conception

The respondents who positively said that they have had sexual intercourse were asked about the use of any method to avoid conception, and if so, what was the method. Their responses are presented as withdrawal at the time of climax (25%); male wearing a condom (23%), safety day method (22%), taking tablet (18%) and remaining never used anything (12%).

About 63% of the respondents seemed to have made use of some methods considered to be safe, namely, condom withdrawal at climax, tablet to prevent conception, and safety day method. One fourth of them said that they had attempted withdrawal at the time of climax, a method that is not very reliable. The response of some of them (12%), namely, that they had not used any method indicates their high risk behavior. This reveals that although conception can be prevented among adolescent girls still there is an issue of risk associated with sex especially for contracting STD/HIV/AIDS.

Though there had been restriction laid by the family after they attend puberty, the girls have reported of intimate sexual relationships. While the no of respondents who had reported of having sexual relationships is less, it is worthy to make a note of it. The respondents have conveyed that it started as from neighbors and relatives which later became a practice.

SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS

A. Personal profile of the Respondents:

- As high as 80.8 % of the respondents belong to the age group of 13 to 16 years (12% belongs to 13 years, 20.5% belongs to 14 years, and 24% belongs to 15 years and 24.3% from 16 years).
- The majority 41.8 % of the respondents belong to the general communities and 9.8% of them belong to the Scheduled Caste communities.
- The good majority 61.8% (31.5%-class IX and 30.3%-class XI) belong to mainly two classes, namely standard 9th and standard 11th.
- The majority 52.5% respondents' families have less than Rs. 20,000/- per annum as their family income (32.2% less than Rs. 10,000 and 20.3% little more than Rs. 10,000). It demonstrates that more than half of the total respondents, families belong to the Below Poverty Line (BPL) category.
- Nearly half (49 %) of the respondents' fathers are engaged in petty business and very insignificant (3.5%) of the respondents' mothers do the maid servants' work.
- The majority (41.3%) respondents' parents have completed their Higher Secondary Education. And the insignificant (2.8%) respondents' parents have access to the higher education.
- As high as (64.5%) of the respondents belong the rural area and the rest of them belong to the semi urban area.
- From the total respondents more than half (62.3%) of the respondents belong to nuclear family. The traditional Indian concept of joint family system is losing its relevance.
- All the adolescents included in the study have one or more siblings in their home (35.8% having three siblings, 30% four children, 28.3% two children and only 6% have one child). It reveals that there is possibility of gaining more knowledge on human sexuality as the majority of the respondents' families having more than one child.
- The district of Ganjam is well-known for its high rate of migration in the state of Odisha but fortunately in the area where the research study was conducted the majority (86.5%) respondents' families are not migrating to other places in search of better livelihood options.
- The respondents' families those who have migrated to other places; 23% because of natural disaster and 25.3% in search of better livelihood option to the urban areas.

B. Knowledge Regarding HIV/AIDS-

- A significant proportion of the rural adolescent girls do not have correct knowledge about HIV/AIDS. This can lead adolescent girls to increased myths, practice risky sexual behavior that can result with HIV/AIDS infection ultimately causing burden to their life and society.

- Slightly a little less than one third of the respondents (34.1%) reported that AIDS is curable and the remaining (9.5%) of the residents reported of having no idea about the curable nature of AIDS. This reveals that little less than half of the respondents don't have adequate knowledge about curable nature of AIDS.
- Interestingly (28%) of adolescent respondents had no idea about what is condom, its use or its availability.
- Only 27% of the respondents have some knowledge about the involvement of National and State level bodies working for the people living with HIV/AIDS.
- Less than half of the respondents (41%) reported HIV infected persons as HIV positive while the remaining did not have knowledge about it and gave different status as HIV negative (25.3%), no idea (23.8%). This reveals the poor knowledge about HIV infection.
- Knowledge about mode of HIV transmission is poor among the adolescent girls continuing their education in the Ganjam District.
- The respondents do not have adequate knowledge about the groups of people vulnerable to be infected by HIV/AIDS.
- A considerable majority of the respondents (79.5%) reported virus to be the cause of HIV infection which is correct and others reported it wrongly as bacteria (8.8%) and 7.5 percent of them did not have any knowledge about it.
- At least 90% adolescent girls disagree about the discussion on sex and HIV/AIDS because it seems they believe that HIV/AIDS is not punishment given by God for immoral behaviour. Simultaneously, they do feel there need to know HIV though they lead a good life. Less than 40% of the respondents considered as HIV/AIDS is a God's punishment for immoral behaviour. Also they feel uneasy and to discuss about the disease even they feel no need to know about HIV.
- Members belonging to the families of HIV/AIDS from the urban clusters of different districts of Odisha refused to receive the monthly pension scheme meant for such infected people. The fear of getting identifies targeted and the consequent social stigma has forced the targeted beneficiaries to shun the plan.
- A good number of respondents responded that the major problem faced by the people living with HIV/AIDS is the discrimination in the society. It is not the disease that kills but a HIV positive rather it is the attitude of the people.
- Interestingly only a very small portion of the respondents have the knowledge specific of the most effective way of prevention, namely, "Be faithful to Single Partner", "Abstain from Sex" and "Use of Condom for Safe Sex" (13.8%, 5.8% and 11.5% respectively).
- Nearly half of the female adolescent respondents (49.5%) do not have adequate knowledge about treatment available to treat a person infected by HIV.
- HIV/AIDS awareness generation programmes.

C. Attitude of female adolescent towards HIV/AIDS and its victims

- Almost 50% of the respondents expressed their feelings that being infected with HIV virus is not God's punishment for one's immoral behavior.
- A Good number of the respondents (42%) expressed that open discussion on human sexuality could help them in understanding the cause and prevention of HIV/AIDS.

- 63.8% of the respondents expressed their views that the people with HIV/AIDS must not be discriminated. They are to be protected and cared for.
- As there are various types of myths found in different societies with regard to HIV/AIDS. Most commonly a myth prevails in South African communities that having sex with the virgins will cure from HIV/AIDS. The same question was also asked to the respondents. But surprisingly more than half of the respondents (60.3%) disagreed to this statement and have the correct knowledge that having sex with a virgin girl cannot cure one from HIV/AIDS.
- Very positively 38.8 percent of the respondents reported that HIV infected person can lead a normal life provided that the community supports for the person living with HIV/AIDS.
- Nearly ¾% adolescents feel sex education is most needed for reduce the risky behaviour while more than 50% of them do feel faithful to one another will be the better prevention of the disease. Less than 40% respondents have negative attitude towards the HIV infected people, they avoid such people and they also frightened to meet with them even they feel that all HIV positive people should be killed, because they cannot lead a normal life. There are some myths and misconception associated with HIV/AIDS thus nearly 40% of respondents do believe that sex with virgin boys or girls can cure HIV and also they believe religious prayer can protect people from HIV infection.

D. Experience and Exposure to HIV/AIDS

- A majority of the respondents (54.8%) have taken to reading sex books or magazines. A good number of them (48.5%) have indulged in masturbation, while kissing, hugging, fondling genitals of a person of the opposite sex, and watching pornography have been the activities of many of them with the range of 43% - 46%.
- From the total (24%) admitted that they had the experience of forced sex. They mentioned the specific manner as fondling the genitals forcefully (8%), caressing the breasts (6.8%), stimulating sexual desire (5.3%), penetrative sex (1.5%) and forcing to have sex with another person (2.3%). This reveals that risky sexual encounters continue to exist among adolescent girls.
- Maximum adolescent have no knowledge on how their reproductive system functions and how pregnancy occurs.
- Majority of the respondents are heard of sexual health, but did not practice the sex or discuss on the sexual matter.

Chapter 5: Conclusion Recommendation & Implication of the Study

CONCLUSIONS:

Adolescents are an important part of the population, yet they are not properly addressed. Adolescents should not be isolated and sheltered from issues such as sexuality and reproductive health since they are at an age when they may begin experimenting and could be misguided and confused in their choices. The life of adolescents are at risk because society does not provide them with the information, skills, services and support they need to postpone sex until they physically and socially mature and able to make well-informed decisions about their sexual behavior. A young person with high self-esteem and good social skills, who is clear about his or her basic values, and has access to relevant information is more likely to make positive decisions about his or health and personal development. But these decisions are not taken on in a vacuum. External factors have a tremendous impact on how adolescents think and behave. These include: social environment, family, peer pressure, educational opportunities, career opportunities, social status, recreational activities and so on.

These young people are at the centre of the HIV/AIDS epidemic in terms of transmission, vulnerability, impact and potential for change. Recent epidemiological data indicates that in this part of the world almost one fourth of those living with HIV are under age of 25 years. In fact, among the new sexually transmitted infections, about 60 percent occur among young people between 15-24 years. During the years of rapid physical and psychological development in the South Asian context, many factors increased young people's vulnerability to HIV/AIDS. These factors include: lack of knowledge about HIV/AIDS; lack of education and life skills, poor access to health services and commodities; early sexual activity; early marriage; sexual coercion and violence; trafficking, and growing up without parents or other form of protection from exploitation and abuse.

In recent past, there has been a tremendous explosion of research on sexual orientation and lifestyles in different parts of the world (Allgeier & Allgeier, 2000; Hawkins & Stackhouse, 1998). This has included examination of the development of homosexual or bisexual identity, dimensions of sexual orientation, relationship dynamics, and a historical emergence of a gay culture, possible etiologic factors, and variety of related social issues, as well as basic descriptive research on the incidence or prevalence of sexual behavior. However, in counties like India, the issue of sexuality has yet to be explored in different dimensions in order to develop greater understanding of these issues. The adolescent girls need to be looked at not just in terms of their own needs but also as individuals who can be productive members of the society. The practice of early mirage and child-bearing that persist puts adolescent girls and children at increased risk of adverse outcome in later life. Adolescents continue to remain at risks, thus calling for development and strengthening of need based interventions. Nevertheless, adolescents do die prematurely due to accidents, suicide, violence, pregnancy related complications and illness that are either preventable or treatable. Many more suffer chronic ill health and disability. In addition, many serious diseases in adulthood have their roots in adolescence. For example, tobacco use, sexually transmitted infections including HIV, poor eating and exercise habits, lead to illness or premature death later in life (Mukharjee 2013).

Thus the main factors that contribute to the magnitude of the problem of adolescent girl vulnerability to HIV and STIs infections are poverty, illiteracy, caste system, and lack of economic opportunities, rural-urban migration, population explosion, weak political will and half-hearted implementation of legal provisions. Thus it can be concluded from the findings of the present study that the knowledge of the adolescent girls under study is as follows-

- A significant proportion of the rural adolescent girls do not have correct knowledge about HIV/AIDS. This can lead adolescent girls to increase myths, practice risky sexual behaviour that can result with HIV/AIDS infection ultimately causing burden to their life and society.
- Knowledge about mode of HIV transmission is poor and interestingly (28%) of adolescent respondents had no idea about what is condom, its use or availability whereas (49.5%) do not have adequate knowledge about treatment.
- Knowledge about mode of HIV transmission is poor among the adolescent's girls continuing their education in the Ganjam District.
- A considerable majority of the respondents (79.5%) reported virus to be the cause of HIV infection which is correct and others reported it wrongly as bacteria (8.8%) and 7.5 percent of them did not have any knowledge about it.
- Interestingly (28%) of adolescent respondents had no idea about what is condom, its use or its availability

With regards to the attitude regarding HIV/AIDS of Adolescent Girls:

- A good number of respondents responded that the major problem faced by the people living with HIV/AIDS is the discrimination in the society. It is not the disease that kills an HIV positive person rather it is the attitude of the people. Nearly 75% of adolescents feel sex education is most needed to reduce the risky behaviour while more than 50% of them do feel faithful to one another will be the better prevention of the disease. Less than 40% respondents have a negative attitude towards the HIV infected people, they avoid such people and they are also frightened to meet with them even they feel that all HIV positive people should be killed, because they cannot lead a normal life. There are some myths and misconceptions associated with HIV/AIDS thus nearly 40% of respondents do believe that sex with virgin boys or girls cures HIV and also they believe religious prayer can protect people from HIV infection.
- At least 90% adolescent girls disagree about the discussion on sex and HIV/AIDS because it seems they believe that HIV/AIDS is not punishment given by God for immoral behaviour. Simultaneously, they do feel there is a need to know HIV though they lead a good life. Less than 40% respondents considered HIV/AIDS as a God's punishment for immoral behaviour. Also they feel uneasy and do not discuss about the disease even they feel no need to know HIV. Members belonging to the families of HIV/AIDS from the urban clusters of different districts of Odisha refused to receive the monthly pension scheme meant for such infected people. The fear of getting identified, targeted and the consequent social stigma has forced the targeted beneficiaries to shun the plan.

- A good number of respondents responded that the major problem faced by the people living with HIV/AIDS is the discrimination in the society. It is not the disease that kills an HIV positive rather it is the attitude of the people

With regards to practice adopted by young adolescent Girls are:

- More than 50% reported that they have not experienced towards a approach for sex or involved themselves in the sexual matter like kissing, hugging, fondling genitals of opposite sex person, sleeping together with them and indulged in masturbation and where as they were interested on watching pornography. In the other hand, 83% denied about the watching pornography or blue film and rest of them watching occasionally. Majority of the respondents have heard of sexual health, but did not practice the sex or discuss about the sexual matter. A vast majority (76.3) of the adolescent girls reported of not having been tried by someone for having sexual intercourse, but 95 respondents of them (24%) admitted that they had the experience of forced sex.
- One fourth i.e. 23.5% of the respondents have sources of knowledge from other sources like teachers, parents, friends, positive net works and integrated counseling and Testing Centre (ICTC) out of them 14.5% students, reported ICTC was the sources of information from the individuals of services sector. However at the same, it is to be rated that a good numbers of them 76.5% acquired information from doctor. More than half of the respondents (57.3%) have never participated in any of them. The major conclusion of the study can be elicited as follows:

This study conducted on the adolescents, it has been notice that most of the adolescents tend to be largely unaware of human sexuality and reproductive health .So their knowledge on HIV/AIDS is incomplete and insufficient to live a healthy life without being succeed to various different community setting with the helped off the peer educators. Government should be single handedly committed to tackle the arrangements of strong and informative mass media campaign for care and treatment of HIV positive person should be advocated and undertake innovative sex education programmes for adolescent girls. To promote these systems, structure and personnel in health as well as non health sectors will be adequately reoriented and sensitized on social, biological, emotional and health risk of the young people on stigma, discrimination, gender violence, human rights etc.

The need of the hour is to consider the context, socio-economic-cultural environment, receptiveness of adolescents and their parents, and the various rich experiences gained through the implementation of different programmes on adolescents' reproductive and sexual health provide valuable insights. A review on the secondary sources, relevant policies and programmes on the issues of adolescents' reproductive and sexual health done by Goyal and Khanna (2005) throw some light on the various critical issues pertinent to adolescents' reproductive and sexual health. Some of the issues are being contextualized on the research area and some of the important issues are being identified and highlighted for further speculation.

- During the past decades the Union Government has launched a number of educational policies and programmes; which has tremendously raised the literacy rate among the

women. Yet the adolescent girl enrollment in the educational institutes is miserable and dropout rate is very high in comparison to boys of the same age. The urban-rural dichotomy again pushes the rural poor adolescent girls to the realm of negligence and ignorance. The education remains a far reaching dream for the rural poor adolescent girls.

- The people of rural Ganjam district are very traditional in their outlook and orthodox religious believers. The district is well-known for its rich cultural traditions, language and literature, food and festivals. The Indian traditional concept of joint family system is losing its grips and due to various socio-economic reasons people are willing to go for a nuclear family. It means the traditional value system is also on the road of erosion.
- Adolescent girls in the Ganjam district especially in the rural area have unlimited exposures to the various means of mass communication. The information on reproductive and sexual health is generally obtained from peer groups. The gained knowledge lacks scientific validity which may in turn lead to the development of myths and confusions.
- Adolescents' awareness level of the issues related to health, nutrition and family life is low. The rigorous efforts made by the NGOs, Govt. Organizations, international agencies and mass media, etc. have been able to generate some awareness of HIV/AIDS. But the understanding of the causes, modes of transmission and preventive measures, treatment of HIV/AIDS is still low.
- Although social and religious values strongly discourage sexual relationship before marriage, but available evidences suggest that premarital sex is not uncommon among adolescent boys and girls both in the urban and rural areas. The majority of the respondents reported indulging in some or the other sexual activities as; masturbation, kissing, hugging, fondling genitals, caressing the breasts, stimulating sexual desire, penetrative sex, etc.
- Sex is considered to be a taboo in the traditional rural society. The talk on sex in front of the elders is considered to be unethical and those who are engaged in such kind of discussion are seen as loose in their character and have corrupt morality. A large proportionate of the girls during the research work suggested that open discussion on human sexuality could become a great help to them in understanding STIs, RTIs, HIV/AIDS, etc. and prepare to prevent from these dreaded diseases.
- Most of the efforts, whether by the government or by voluntary organizations, are made to increase the level of awareness and knowledge. However, the issue of sexuality and reproductive health requires going beyond that. Most appropriate interventions at the educational institutes and community level should be designed keeping in view the socio-cultural context.
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As a whole, adolescents have to be given opportunities to develop so that they can be empowered with the knowledge and skills that will help them lead a more fulfilling social and personal life and take responsible and well-thought decisions. This will enhance the quality of life for adolescents at both societal and the personal level and help them realize their right to exercise autonomy and self-determination and responsible decision-making their sexual and reproductive life.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the knowledge gained from the field with regard to the knowledge, attitude, and practices of adolescent girls about HIV/AIDS; certain recommendations are inferred from the observation. From the study as we come to know that the rural adolescent girls do not have adequate knowledge on human sexuality and reproductive health. Similarly their knowledge on HIV/AIDS is incomplete and insufficient to live a healthy life without being succumbed to various deadly infections. On the other hand the information they obtained from the various channels are not authoritative. The adolescent girls in schools or out of schools do not have access to sex education which sometimes leads them towards risky behavior. The teachers are also not so comfortable and competent enough to provide sex education to the students, and especially to adolescent girls. Sexual health being a sensitive issue in the traditional society; it is neither the parents nor the teachers who feel comfortable in providing education to the adolescent girls on sexual and reproductive health. Thus the knowledge could be imparted in different community setting with the help of the peer educators. Following recommendations to different stake holders can be explained as follows:

For Governmental Departments:-

- Formulation of comprehensive policies and stringent implementation of legislations for preventive measures of HIV/AIDS and rights of the positive persons should be advocated.
- Budgetary allocation and release of adequate funds for effective and comprehensive programmes for HIV/AIDS epidemic compatible to regional, social and cultural demands are recommended.
- Establishment of an HIV/AIDS and migrant task force at block level of those districts where both in and out migration is prevalent. The task force should be vigilant, be legally supported and well prepared to manage any kind of civil situations in the districts. There ought to be effective communication channels and a strong collaboration among the members of the task force and the authorities.
- Government should be single handedly committed to tackle the stigma and discrimination associated with HIV/AIDS at the highest level by promotion and propagation of strong political will.
- The political promise must be reinforced to provide improved qualitative public health services in national policies and programmes made at different levels.
- Use of obtainable, and develop new advocacy tools to sensitize decision-makers to the urgency of the problem, the consequences on development targets of neglecting the role of nutrition and not including it within the overall care and support package and the opportunity to improve care.
- Resource allocation must be increased to advocate and support for improved nutrition, in general and tackling the nutritional needs of HIV-affected and infected populations.
- The needs of children affected and made vulnerable by HIV/AIDS should be given priority. Clarify and improve multispectral collaboration and coordination between the agricultural, health, social services, education and nutrition sectors.
- Traditional and alternative therapies need to be explored, popularized and legalized for better effective implementation of programmes and policies.

- In regular intervals review and update of existing guidelines should be conducted (e.g., guidelines on integrated management of adolescent and adult illness, antiretroviral treatment, and nutrition in emergencies).
- Existing interventions should be expanded and make them accessible to the vulnerable communities and people already infected with HIV/AIDS
- Identify and use local expertise to improve response to emergency conditions.
- Strengthening of services and awareness programs provided by the Government.
- Provision of accurate and handy information about the use of contraceptives, safe sex, risk of mother to child transmission, anti retroviral therapy (ART) and HIV/AIDS transmission.
- Strong and rigorous counseling to those who are on ART.
- Enlarged accessibility of information for the pregnant women and the couples who are planning for pregnancy, they should counsel on PPTCT services to stop the infection to the child.
- STDs and HIV/AIDS services are widely accessible and available in the rural area.
- HIV counseling and testing must be expanded so that individuals can make informed decisions and receive appropriate advice and support.
- Easy available of comprehensive and free drug supply with rehabilitation centers at the district level.
- A medical insurance policy for HIV positive persons should be made available to cover their medical care costs. This is very much imperative as HIV positive people face multidimensional problems in addition to HIV including unemployment, rejection and stigma. After declaration of their status, patients are surrounded by unhealthy and unwanted environment.
- Development of health service policies and programmes designed to provide the equal standard of care and services for all the clients irrespective of their HIV status, o Plan for a revised and improved financial assistance to give them an easy life. For overcoming the financial problems, there should be a proper planning to bear the expenses of their treatment.
- There is need for increasing the availability and accessibility of special AIDS cares clinics or separate section in the hospital only for HIV positive persons in the block and panchayat level.
- Arrangements of strong and informative mass media campaign for care and treatment of HIV positive persons should be advocated.
- Provision of scholarship to school going children of HIV positive persons to facilitate their education is essentially important.
- Provision of medical care and psychological support to the concerned individuals and their families.
- Provision of supplying the staple foods to the HIV positive persons who are very needy and in the disease condition not able to get two times meal. Supply of cereal and protein mix powder to the HIV infected persons to enhance their immunity power should be advocated, free supply of multivitamin tablet can be introduced.

For Civil Society Organizations:-

- It is an urgent need to provide trainings for HIV support groups: AIDS service organizations and health care providers and NGO workers to provide accurate, comprehensive up to date and easy to understand information on causes, prevention and treatment of this lethal disease.
- NGOs and the civil society organization must formulate compressive policies for the persons living with HIV/AIDS and go for a very strong lobby and advocacy to protect the rights of HIV infected persons.
- The assistance that is required from relevant authorities, NGOs, civil society to ensure adequate care and support along with follow up actions should be made available.
- To go for rigorous campaigns in order to educate and create awareness about legal right of marginalized so as to empower them to seek justice and legal protection; for example women be made aware of their legal rights of inheritance, matrimonial home and maintenances will be an important step addressing the issue of HIV/AIDS.

For Mass Media:

An affective media can raise the awareness level and can also bring about sustainable behavior change there by reducing vulnerability to the virus. Media is capable of performing the following role in preventing HIV/AIDS.

- A channel for communication and discussion: On the role of media is to open the channels for communication and foster discussions about HIV and interpersonal relations. Addressing HIV/AIDS in the entertainment programmes can have an enormous impact on the society at risk.
- A vehicle for creating a supportive and enabling environment: Mass media can be instrumental in breaking the silence that envelopes the disease and in creating an encouraging behavior for combating with existing social norms and making positive changes in the society.
- WHO has various extraordinary stories of HIV people who are not only fighting the virus but are also playing an integral/role in prevention of HIV/AIDS.
- A tool for creating a knowledge base for HIV/ AIDS related services. The collaborative efforts of all models of media in association with NGO's state organizations, service providers have brought to the limelight, the availability and sources of beneficial services like counseling, testing and condom provision, treatment and social care. The broadcasters and print media have a specific role to play as their efforts have tremendous recall value.
- Education through entertainment. For creating an efficacious awareness about HIV/AIDS, the messages need to be informative, educative as well as entertaining as these are mutually exclusive.
- Thus a holistic approach for dealing with the emotional, psychological and physical realities is to be adopted.
- Putting of HIV/AIDS on the news agenda and encouraging learners to participate.

- Capacity building: Successful partnership need to be with other media outlets. Alliances of NGOs, Government departments and foundations can bring significant benefit for both the parties.
- Media as an institution of oversight, restraint and collaborative effort; the media has the potential to influence public opinion and attitudes about HIV/AIDS, including attitudes towards people living with HIV/AIDS. The media can be a great facilitator for preventing process while imparting the need for a healthy behavior towards the section of the society and those individuals most vulnerable to HIV/AIDS and those individuals affected by it.

For Panchayati raj Institutions:-

- There is a provision of maintaining the records of migrants. Number of migrants going outside and coming inside, the departure and arrival date etc.
- Provision of appointment of a person who will counsel them about the deadly disease and the preventive measures and about safe sex.
- Provision of a compulsory blood test of the migrants when they come to the village at the immediate step and if found positive the same to be conveyed to their spouse to stop the infection.

For Public at large:-

- Increase access to information related to safe sex, family planning, safe pregnancy, and safe abortion as preventive measure for the general population, including adolescents, the elderly and people living HIV/AIDS should be ensured.
- Increase access to information on voluntary and confidential HIV testing and counseling by the general population should be made available.
- Undertake innovative sex education programmes.
- Increase access to education campaign program families, communities, schools, workplaces, health care providers and the mass media people so they have clear understanding of HIV/AIDS which can reduce stigmatization, discrimination and cases of abandonment.
- There is a need to change the social barrier and create the conducive environment for women, so that they can negotiate for safer sex practices and to find relevant information easier and even to say no against unsafe sex.
- Anything related to reproduction and menstruation is usually kept under the wraps in India society. But breaking such barriers are innovative concepts like the low-cost sanitary napkins that are a double boon to the poor women of rural India, helping them lead a hygienic lifestyle and earn a living too.

For Future Research:-

- Further experimental studies should be carried out scientifically in different parts of the country both in the urban and rural settings to find out a proper channel of provide education on human sexuality and reproductive health to the adolescent girls.
- In the studies to be done in the future, other implications of the society like religious, political and impacts of health care system specifically should be advocated in details. Further studies are needed to identify age and gender implications of HIV/AIDS. For

example study with HIV man to study with their sexual choice, need and decisions as well as to highest important gender difference and similarity. These studies will also provide important information for AIDS service organizations and policy makers to develop the better set up for patients and their families.

- Further studies should able to extract all aspects of stigma and discrimination associated with HIV/AIDS and infected people. Studies should be conducted to tackle the stigma. Supplementary studies should be conducted to all the aspects which expose a person to high risk of getting HIV/AIDS should be explored. Further studies to be conducted to explore the factors that encourage sustain of stigma and discrimination in the society people affected with HIV/AIDS

IMPLICATIONS OF THE PRESENT STUDY:

It has been noticed that most of the adolescents tend to be largely unaware of their sexual health and reproductive system. One of the reasons for lack of awareness is poor exposure to mass media or other means of information. The meager accessibility and total inaccessibility to the effective means of mass communication, especially television and news paper; adolescents are most likely to depend on the information obtained from peer group. In the cultural context of India, in which sex is considered to be a taboo; adolescents are not in a position to discuss sexual and reproductive health issues with parents or other elders. In most cases, peers constitute the reference group for seeking information about sexuality and reproductive matters. But the information obtained from peer groups or other such sources may not necessary be correct, and can create confusion and misconceptions. In India youth is not a homogenous group and different sub-populations of young people are exposed to different risk settings. Thus, the risk perception and behavior of the young people (13-35) are likely to determine the future direction of HIV/AIDS in the country

It is suggested to establish Youth Friendly Information Centre/Services (YFIC) at the community level to provide youth oriented counseling, life skill education, recreation and guidance in a confidential and enabling environment. This approach will cover the non-health youth sector in universities, colleges, youth clubs, NGOs/CBOs and organizations of youth volunteers. The youth volunteers trained in the Youth Friendly Information Centers who will be adequately reoriented and sensitized on social, biological, emotional and health risks of the young people, on stigma, discrimination, gender violence, human rights, etc. and become the change agents to stop the spread of HIV/AIDS.

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